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Research and innovate

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EXPLORING THE ENTREPRENEURIAL CULTURE AMONG FARMERS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR APPLYING PRECISION FARMING IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW BUSINESS MODELS

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ABSTRACT

The digitization of European agriculture in the last few years has enabled precision farming to fulfill its potential in organizing the production and marketing of agricultural products. Farmers who are already using precision farming technologies see the main advantages of this type of production management. In economic terms, these technologies make it possible to minimize production costs, achieve economies of scale, overcome labor shortages, etc. In environmental terms, precision farming technology enables the farmer to reduce pressure on the environment. All these benefits provide motivation for more and more new entrepreneurs to adopt precision farming technology. Due to digitalization, we are witnessing the emergence of new business models being developed by a new generation of farmers in the EU. The aim of this paper is to analyze and assess the entrepreneurial culture of farmers and on this ground to identify opportunities for the use of precision agriculture in the creation of new business models. The main methods used are survey methods and graphical analysis. The results of the study show that entrepreneurs tend to develop skills in precision agriculture that will give them abilities to impose and develop new business models.

KEYWORDS: entrepreneurship, precision agriculture, business models, digitization of agriculture, SWOT

ABSTRAKT

Die Digitalisierung der europäischen Landwirtschaft in den letzten Jahren hat es der Präzisionslandwirtschaft ermöglicht, ihr Potenzial bei der Organisation der Produktion und Vermarktung landwirtschaftlicher Erzeugnisse auszuschöpfen. Landwirte, die bereits Precision-Farming-Technologien einsetzen, sehen die wichtigsten Vorteile dieser Art des Produktionsmanagements. In wirtschaftlicher Hinsicht ermöglichen diese Technologien eine Minimierung der Produktionskosten, die Erzielung von Skaleneffekten, die Überwindung von Arbeitskräftemangel usw. In ökologischer Hinsicht ermöglicht die Präzisionslandwirtschaft dem Landwirt, die Umweltbelastung zu verringern. All diese Vorteile motivieren immer mehr neue Unternehmer, die Technologie der Präzisionslandwirtschaft einzusetzen. Im Zuge der Digitalisierung entstehen neue Geschäftsmodelle, die von einer neuen Generation von Landwirten in der EU entwickelt werden. Ziel dieses Beitrags ist es, die unternehmerische Kultur der Landwirte zu analysieren und zu bewerten und auf dieser Grundlage Möglichkeiten für den Einsatz der

Präzisionslandwirtschaft bei der Schaffung neuer Geschäftsmodelle zu ermitteln. Die wichtigsten verwendeten Methoden sind Umfragen und grafische Analysen. Die Ergebnisse der Studie zeigen, dass Unternehmer dazu neigen, Fähigkeiten in der Präzisionslandwirtschaft zu entwickeln, die ihnen die Fähigkeit verleihen, neue Geschäftsmodelle durchzusetzen und zu entwickeln.

STICHWORTE: Unternehmertum, Präzisionslandwirtschaft, Geschäftsmodelle, Digitalisierung der Landwirtschaft, SWOT

RÉSUMÉ

La numérisation de l'agriculture européenne au cours des dernières années a permis à l'agriculture de précision de réaliser son potentiel en matière d'organisation de la production et de la commercialisation des produits agricoles. Les agriculteurs qui utilisent déjà les technologies de l'agriculture de précision voient les principaux avantages de ce type de gestion de la production. Sur le plan économique, ces technologies permettent de minimiser les coûts de production, de réaliser des économies d'échelle, de pallier la pénurie de main-d'œuvre, etc. Sur le plan environnemental, les technologies de l'agriculture de précision permettent à l'agriculteur de réduire la pression sur l'environnement. Tous ces avantages incitent de plus en plus de nouveaux entrepreneurs à adopter les technologies de l'agriculture de précision. En raison de la numérisation, nous assistons à l'émergence de nouveaux modèles d'entreprise développés par une nouvelle génération d'agriculteurs dans l'UE. L'objectif de ce document est d'analyser et d'évaluer la culture entrepreneuriale des agriculteurs et, sur cette base, d'identifier les possibilités d'utilisation de l'agriculture de précision dans la création de nouveaux modèles d'entreprise. Les principales méthodes utilisées sont les méthodes d'enquête et l'analyse graphique. Les résultats de l'étude montrent que les entrepreneurs ont tendance à développer des compétences en agriculture de précision qui leur permettront d'imposer et de développer de nouveaux modèles d'entreprise.

MOTS-CLÉS: entrepreneuriat, agriculture de précision, modèles d'entreprise, numérisation de l'agriculture, SWOT

INTRODUCTION

The farmer's entrepreneurial culture determines his potential to develop a successful business model in agriculture. In the context of digitalization of the agricultural sector, entrepreneurial culture should change by seeking increasingly attractive forms of organization and management of agricultural business models (Stoeva, Dirimanova, and Borisov, 2021). Within the framework of his entrepreneurial culture, the farmer is aware of his needs regarding the skills and opportunities to gain experience in managing his farm. In the current conditions, agriculture as a business alternative is developing in the context of digitalization of management processes and the use of precise technologies, which enable competitiveness in the market. The digitalization of production and business processes as well as the introduction of precise technologies are only the potential for achieving competitive development of the farm's business model. An adequate entrepreneurial culture is also needed, which should be harnessed to create value for the customer through the use of precise and digital technologies in the industry. Entrepreneurial culture is mainly determined by two groups of factors that have an impact on the motivation of the entrepreneur (Khattam, 1999). This division of the factors that build this culture (environment) is conditional using the criterion of "to what extent the factors have a direct impact" on

the entrepreneurial skills of the farmer. As a result, entrepreneurial culture can be considered as a set of two groups of factors that determine it. The first group are factors that have a direct impact on the motivation of the entrepreneur. These factors determine his ego, namely the opportunities for taking risks, developing business acumen, personal development and achieving a high standard of living, overcoming poverty and escaping destitution, the desire for change and achieving personal development in both material and spiritual aspects, showing and maintaining leadership among society and the business elite (Segal, Borgia and Schoenfeld, 2005). These factors have a direct and systematic impact on the motivation of the entrepreneur and can be defined as the main drivers of the motivational process in the long term (Drucker, 2001); (Borisova, 2024). The second group of factors can include all those that indirectly affect the motivation of the entrepreneur and most often when we talk about agribusiness these are the subsidies that the entrepreneur can receive if he is engaged in agriculture; the opportunities for higher profitability and return, determined by various financial mechanisms for supporting the implementation of the agrarian business; the creation of jobs for family members and the community; to impose one's own style of work and following personal interest - in agricultural business very often the owner of the production resources is both a manager and a worker, that is, the farmer combines all these characters in his entrepreneurial profile and plays their role (Kamenov, 1999). These factors have a strong motivational character in the short term and through them the entrepreneurial behavior of the farmer at a certain point in his business development can be studied and explained.

The factors that are part of the entrepreneurial culture have a complex interaction and can be defined as having a direct impact at one point and an indirect impact at another. Therefore, the regulatory framework for the development of the entrepreneurial culture in Bulgarian agriculture needs to be regulated in a way that encourages the farmer, rather than hindering his motivation to develop and achieve business success.

Entrepreneurs in the agricultural business are facing with different challenges compared to other participants who develop business in other economic sectors (Borisova, 2015). Agriculture is a specific business activity that sets high requirements for the entrepreneurial skills of the farmer (Lins, 1989). In agriculture, the participation of living organisms in the production process, as well as the participation of the land, through its soil fertility, determine strictly specific conditions for the development of each business model (Kanchev, 1996). In agriculture, these factors give rise to seasonality in the production and trade of agricultural products and services, which are also the reason for a clearly expressed seasonality in the revenues generated in the farm during the business year (Woehe, 1993). Expenses have sustainable levels, because they are carried out almost daily in order to achieve high levels of productivity and quality of agricultural production, while revenues are generated for only three to four months during the business year. This determines a lower financial stability of the agricultural business compared to the established models in other economic sectors of the national economy. The discrepancy in the intensity of incoming and outgoing cash flows in the management of the business model also gives rise to a lower return on investment in agriculture. (Borisov, Radev and Koprivlenski, 2014). This is also a factor that determines a significant barrier to large-scale investment in the industry and the development of successful innovations. Another important aspect of the agrarian business is that there will always be a sustainable demand for produced agricultural products, which are part of the food products of a national economy (Tsoneva, 2001). This determines a good prospect for investments in the development of new business

models in the industry, but only experienced entrepreneurs can take advantage of this business opportunity. It should be noted that agriculture is directly dependent, despite the processes of digitalization and new technologies, on natural factors, namely climate change and the frequent occurrence of extreme natural events that can economically devastate the farmer (Fidanska, Borisov and Nikolov, 2021). Due to climate change, it is increasingly difficult for farmers to plan the specialization of production. Another important factor, a challenge for the farmer-entrepreneur, is the new market requirements and government regulations, which require him to be flexible and adaptable in managing his business model (Kolaj, Borisov, Arabska and Radev, 2023). Managing the business model is becoming increasingly complex due to the increasing competition in the agricultural product market. A major factor for this is subsidies, which motivate more and more new players to join the industry (Osmani, Kolaj, Borisov and Arabska, 2021). This undoubtedly benefits the consumer, but it makes it increasingly difficult to manage the farm and the business model. All these challenges in the industry determine and oblige the farmer to have a high entrepreneurial culture and business acumen for successful development. Awareness of the requirements of the business environment determines and motivates the farmer to develop his entrepreneurial skills. New technologies and digitalization raise the bar even higher, requiring the farmer not only to be a good and effective entrepreneur, but also a good engineer and technologist who can take advantage of innovations and generate higher competitiveness of his business model. The business environment is complex and has a complex influence, which obliges the entrepreneur to develop in all the mentioned areas.

This **study aims** to identify the main factors (direct motivators) determining the farmer's entrepreneurial culture, taking into account the opportunities that digitalization and precision agriculture provide and assessing the entrepreneurial environment for implementing new business models.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main approach used to implement the research is the systems approach. Within this approach, the entrepreneurial culture of the farmer is perceived as a system built from multiple elements (factors) that have a complex influence and degree of control on the part of the entrepreneur who develops his business in agriculture (Pamukchiev, 1978).

Within this approach, 2 methods are used, namely the survey method and SWOT. In the first stage of the research, the aim is to collect data on: (1) the factors determining the motivation of farmers to be entrepreneurs; (2) data on the perception of the farmer who plays the role of an entrepreneur; (3) data on the gaps in the entrepreneurial skills of farmers when applying precision agriculture technology. All this data is collected using the survey method. The object of the survey are 125 farmers who are studying in various specialties at the Agricultural University - Plovdiv.

The second stage of the study aims to collect data on the state of the entrepreneurial culture of farmers. Based on this data, the opportunities and threats in the development of new business models in agriculture, based on the principles of precision technologies, are studied and determined. In order to collect the necessary information, the focus group method is used.

Organization of the survey. To evaluate participants' entrepreneurial mindset, we exploited the Entrepreneurial Motivation Scale developed by (Vijaya and Kamalanabhan, 1998), see table 1. The 26 items of the scale are presented below. Respondents rated each factor using a 5-point rating scale as

follows: 1- not important; 2 – slightly important, 3 – important, 4 – very important and 5 – extremely important.

Table 1. Matrix for evaluation of participants' entrepreneurial mindset. Source: Vijaya and Kamalanabhan (1998)

	Not important	Slightly important	Important	Very important	Extremely important
1. Make effective use of my risk-taking ability and succeed					
2. Be independent					
3. Provide good service or products to the community					
4. Help people by providing them employment					
5. Utilize the concessions or loans from the Government, banks, etc.					
6. Compete with others and prove to be the best					
7. Get complete satisfaction					
8. Utilize my keen business sense					
9. Exploit my innate talent and potential in a profession					
10. Do something creative/innovative					
11. Do something/Achieve something that others usually do not					
12. Use my decision-making/problem-solving skills to profit in a career					
13. Be a leader					
14. Be an employer					
15. Attain high social status					
16. Show that I am inferior to none					
17. Earn the respect of people					
18. Acquire lots of wealth for yourself					
19. Have your own preferred work style and lifestyle					
20. Enjoy the best luxuries of life					
21. Get over monotony, experience change					

22. Get over the shortage of money					
23. Make my family rich					
24. Get the best monetary returns for my talent					
25. Supplement the family income					
26. Make money to clear debts					

Organizing focus groups and applying SWOT. In order to identify the most attractive opportunities for farmers to apply precision farming technologies and develop new business models on this basis, SWOT is used. SWOT is among the most popular methods in the scientific literature, which is used to assess the opportunities arising from the business environment (Borisov, Radev and Nikolov, 2014). The SWOT analysis technique requires knowledge of all specific factors that have a direct and indirect impact on the business model in order to analyze them in detail so that the farm can easily adapt to their requirements. This study defends the idea that entrepreneurs are the ones who most fully know the internal factors of the business environment that determine the future development of business models. Therefore, entrepreneurs are used as the main source of information for determining the strengths and weaknesses, as well as the opportunities and threats for the development of new business models in precision farming.

The strengths and weaknesses, as well as the opportunities and threats arising from the external environment, are determined based on the results obtained from the surveys conducted. The conclusions from the scientific research are the subject of discussions by the entrepreneurs in focus groups specially set up for this purpose. Figure 1 presents the methodological approach for determining the problems and potential solutions for the development of new business models, through the use of precision agriculture methods. The approach includes a total of 4 stages for diagnosing the business environment.

The first stage (A.) from the application of the methodological approach consists in identifying the strengths/weaknesses as well as the opportunities and threats to the new business models in agriculture, resulting from the research conducted.

Through focus groups, the strengths and weaknesses as well as the opportunities and threats to the new business models are discussed and determined. Group discussions (focus groups) are used as a method in the research, which allows for in-depth entry into the research topic, while at the same time using the advantages of the group effect. During the discussions, through spontaneous and extensive discussion of previously determined conclusions from the scientific research in small groups of people, it is clearly formulated what the strengths and weaknesses of the farmers are and what opportunities and threats the external environment provides for the development of new business models based on the principles of precision agriculture. The discussions are organized and guided by a moderator who sets the questions for discussion, ensures equal participation of the individuals, and directs in new interesting directions, spontaneously expressed by the participants.

Figure 1. Methodological approach for implementing SWOT. Source: Borisov, Radev, Nikolov, 2014

During the second stage (B.) aims to construct a SWOT matrix, which is the result of the discussions held in the focus groups. The most frequently mentioned strengths/weaknesses as well as opportunities and threats from the focus group participants find a place in the matrix. This matrix is subsequently used as a technique for determining two important elements in identifying possible future alternatives for the business, namely: 1) what are the most important strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats and 2) what is the interaction of the strengths and weaknesses with the mentioned opportunities and threats.

During the third stage (C.) the most significant factors for success are sought. The method of expert assessment ranks the most significant strengths, weaknesses, opportunities and threats in a SWOT matrix. The role of experts in assessing these four building blocks of the SWOT matrix is played by the farmers themselves. The expert assessment organized in this way aims to determine the most significant factors for success in the market development of new business models. The organization of the expert assessment itself includes the following: instructing the experts (farmers) on how to express their expert opinion; choosing and applying an assessment scale; developing an expert opinion map and carrying out the expert assessment itself by the respondents. Each expert independently fills in a specially created expert opinion map. The SWOT matrix constructed in the previous stage of the study is used as such. In this matrix, the respondent assesses the interaction of strengths and weaknesses with the identified opportunities and threats. The expert uses a 4-point rating scale, which contains the following ratings: 0 – no interaction, 1 – weak interaction, 2 – strong interaction and 3 – very strong interaction between the studied factors.

Four types of interactions between the factors in the matrix are examined as follows: (1) interaction between strengths and identified opportunities. This research relationship seeks to answer the question: to what extent the identified strengths can be used to realize the identified opportunities; (2) interaction between strengths and threats, the assessment thus derived, seeks to answer the question: to what extent the identified strengths can be used to protect against the threats that the external environment contains; (3) interaction between weaknesses and identified opportunities, thus seeking to answer the question: to what extent the weaknesses can prevent the realization of the identified opportunities and (4) interaction between weaknesses and identified threats. This relationship indicates to what extent the weaknesses will prevent entrepreneurs and their business models from adapting to the threats of the external environment.

During the fourth stage (D.) the application of the SWOT analysis determines the interaction of the factors in the SWOT matrix. At this stage, the results of the expert assessment are summarized. The individually completed SWOT matrices by each respondent are aggregated into a summarized SWOT matrix, which is a map of the summarized results of the expert assessment. In the “Sum” row, the individual assessments in the cells by columns of the matrix are summed up. This row identifies the most significant opportunities and threats to the future development of new business models. The higher the sum for the respective opportunity or threat, the more significant it is according to the experts. In the “Sum” column, the individual assessments in the cells by rows of the matrix are listed. This column identifies the most significant strengths and weaknesses that can be used to absorb the identified opportunities. The higher the sum for the respective strength or weakness, the more significant it is according to the experts. The generalized matrix can be used as a tool for identifying the strategic orientation of the business model. In other words, by compiling this matrix, two useful effects are achieved – (1) the direction of the future development of the business model is determined and (2) a set of alternative business strategies for the development of this business model is identified (Nikolov, Radev and Borisov, 2014)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Farmers were asked about the possibility of starting their own enterprise in the near future. The results shown on figure 2 express that for 35.2% of all farmers to run their own enterprise in very likely and 26.4

claims – it is likely in near future. Only 12% of farmers declare that they will not take such an initiative in the near future. This attitude is probably due to the knowledge and skills deficit in entrepreneurship and to lack relevant orientation during their studies.

Figure 2. Possibility of starting own business in the near future. Results from 125 respondents – answers are presented as (%). The results of the study are funded by project BOOST, Erasmus+ program, Project Number: 101056291.

Concerning the Entrepreneurial Motivation Scale (see figure 3), which assesses farmers' entrepreneurial mindset, the highest mean scores were noticed in the items "Be independent" (M=3.75), "Provide good service or products to the community" (M= 3.48), and "Earn the respect of people" (M=3.30), indicating that farmers' intention to engage in entrepreneurship is motivated by their desire to offer high quality services, while, in parallel, expressing their creativity and gaining independence and this way to gain respect of people.

The following figure 3 shows the assessment of the surveyed farmers regarding the factors that motivate them to be entrepreneurs. The results show that all the studied factors have a structurally determining role in forming the motivation of farmers to be entrepreneurs. It is noteworthy that all the factors received a score that defines them as having an important role. The ratings of the factors range from 2.65 to 3.75 points. The factor rated with the highest score is "to be independent" – with a score of 3.75 points. Farmers want to be entrepreneurs because this role gives them the opportunity to be independent in their lives. The strictly individual entrepreneurial spirit is clearly expressed and supported by the results obtained from the survey. The motivation of farmers to be entrepreneurs is also determined by their desire to provide quality services and products for the community. This factor was rated with 3.48 points and ranks it in second place in importance in the motivation process. In addition, farmers strive for

a social position in which other people respect them (score – 3.30 points). Public attention and respect for farmers, as producers of basic food products and raw materials for their production, is a real motive for entrepreneurial activity in the sector.

The results indicate that the farmer's desire for lower indebtedness is also an important factor determining their motivation to be entrepreneurs and take risks by organizing agricultural production (this factor is rated with 3.31 points). In addition to these factors, the farmer's desire to create jobs is a major motivating factor of importance (rated – 3.26).

Another factor that received a high rating and is important in shaping the farmer's motivation is the work style and lifestyle - it was rated with 3.20 points. Following one's own work style strongly motivates the entrepreneur in agriculture.

The analysis of the obtained scores on individual factors for the formation of an entrepreneurial culture indicates that farmers are entrepreneurs who are concerned about the local community and are drivers of local development in both economic and social aspects.

The validation of the results of the analysis of the factors determining the entrepreneurial culture of farmers is carried out through the application of the focus group method. Through discussions with farmers, the factors building the entrepreneurial environment for the imposition of new business models using the precision agriculture approach are determined. The following figure 4 shows the constructed SWOT matrix, showing the state of the entrepreneurial environment at the level of summarized results from the focus groups. The matrix constructed in this way makes it possible to propose measures and initiatives to increase the competencies of entrepreneurs and their skills in order to have market success. Farmers highlight the following strengths as the most important:

- **Farms (micro and small) are adaptable and motivated** to achieve sales growth;
- **Farms are defined by good liquidity.** Entrepreneurs claim to have high overall liquidity;
- **Farmers strive to innovate in production.** Farmers claim that they are investing primarily in technological innovation that will enable them to implement the precision farming approach on the farms they manage;
- **Entrepreneurs seek to diversify sources of financial risk** using both equity and debt (external) capital for the market development of their business model;

The industry is dominated by a large number of small and medium-sized farms that have a relatively small market share and a very small number of large farms that control a large part of the market. Small farms are distinguished by a sustainable market share (i.e. they have built a small but loyal group of consumers of their products);

Figure 3. Factors and their contribution to the motivation process of agricultural entrepreneurs. Five grade entrepreneurial motivation Scale: 1- not important; 2 – slightly important, 3 – important, 4 – very important and 5 – extremely important. Results from 125 respondents (mean score and standard deviation – SD). The results of the study are funded by project BOOST, Erasmus+ program, Project Number: 101056291.

As weaknesses, focus group participants point out the following (see Figure 4):

- **High indebtedness to major suppliers of raw materials and finance** Indebtedness is mainly to financial enterprises, which is a major barrier to reorganizing the business model by using the advantages of precision agriculture;
- **Entrepreneurs have insufficient working capital**, which will enable them to pay on time and thus improve their solvency;
- **Entrepreneurs do not diversify sources of market risk.** They work mainly with one or two clients, on whose solvency they are directly dependent;
- Entrepreneurs make systematic omissions in terms of the strategic planning activities they implement when imposing their business models on the market. Most of the farmers (1/3 of the total number) in the focus groups shared that they mainly emphasize activities in the area of strategic business planning, but not in terms of strategic control of their business model;
- **Entrepreneurs cannot provide the necessary conditions** to attract experienced and capable personnel who can work with digital technologies and use the advantages of precision agriculture.

The potential for the development of new business models is significant in terms of constant and loyal demand for agricultural products and services. These products have a traditional importance in the Bulgarian menu. The existence of potential is not a sufficient condition for market presence and superiority, it is necessary to explore and identify the opportunities for the realization of this potential. As a result of the discussions held and the conclusions formulated from the analytical study, the following opportunities for imposing new business models on the market have been identified:

- **Creating skills and competencies in entrepreneurs** to use the advantages of precision agriculture. Most entrepreneurs share that the lack of experienced personnel in this area hinders the market development of the business model and the introduction of new business models. Providing the farm with experienced specialists will increase the competitiveness of the business model and create conditions for the introduction of new business models.
- **Cooperation along the value chain.** This cooperation will not be in full aspect, but only in terms of the implementation of marketing activities and in terms of the concentration of capital, thus seeking the opportunity to saturate the farms with equipment and technologies in the field of precision agriculture. Thus, these farms will have a greater chance of developing in a market dominated by several large players;
- **Sharing the financial costs of creating and implementing innovations.** Entrepreneurs have the desire, but not the ability, to be innovative and, in this regard, to successfully compete in the market with large farms. A major limiting factor in the innovation process in small farms is the significant amount of costs for financing innovations needed to adapt their production and implement precision agriculture. In many other sectors, the sharing of financial costs for the creation and implementation of innovative products is available. In this way, major competitors in the market cooperate in terms of costs for innovation activities in order to achieve higher market competitiveness of their business models. Following this model can be applied to micro, small and medium-sized farms, which should form cluster formations for scientific and development and innovation activities in partnership with scientific organizations in our country;

- **Know-how alliances.**Very often, innovative solutions in the sector encourage entrepreneurs who are participants in the value chain to merge and/or integrate in the value-adding process. These strategic alliances allow entrepreneurs to present innovative business models to the market that can realize a sustainable rate of market development and competitiveness.

STRENGTHS	OPPORTUNITIES
Adaptable and motivated to achieve sales growth	Creating skills and competencies to leverage the benefits of precision agriculture
Liquid	Cooperation along the value chain
Striving to implement innovations in production	Sharing the financial costs of creating and implementing innovations
Diversify sources of financial risk	Creation of mutual financial funds to finance innovations
They have a sustainable market share	New business models that allow for increased company competitiveness
WEAKNESSES	THREATS
High indebtedness	Monopolistic market structure
Insufficient working capital	Strong dependence on the credit policy of commercial banks
They do not diversify the sources of market risk.	Insufficient supply of experienced specialists on the labor market
Systemic gaps in the implementation of strategic planning activities in the market implementation of the business model	Intensification of competition, large players are becoming increasingly aggressive towards the market share of small players in the market
They do not have the conditions to attract experienced staff	Unequal access to state financial aid and subsidies

Figure 4. SWOT – matrix for identifying the factors of the entrepreneurial environment for increasing the competitiveness of farms by imposing new business models using precision agriculture. Source: Summarized results of focus groups. (summary of the opinions of 55 farmers, distributed in 3 focus groups).

Threats are factors that can significantly worsen the entrepreneurial environment as well as the entrepreneurial ability of farmers. The analysis of the conclusions from the focus group discussions identifies the following significant threats:

- **The market has a monopolistic structure.** There are a few large players that dominate the market. Small and medium-sized market participants operate in conditions of fierce price competition. The expansion of the market share of the large ones is at the expense of pushing the small ones out of the sector. This leads to the seizure of consumer surplus;
- **Strong dependence of entrepreneurs on the credit policy of commercial banks.** Within the framework of the research conducted, it was determined that enterprises in the sector /regardless of whether they are small or large/ have a significant debt to the banking sector. In the current economic conditions, when interest rates are still low and credit expansion is underway in the sector, enterprises are looking for ways to repay old debts to banks through additional bank financing. This dependence, if the credit policy of commercial banks changes in

the direction of increasing interest rates on granted investment or business loans, will play a bad joke on most enterprises in the sector;

- **Insufficient supply of experienced specialists in the field of precision agriculture on the labor market**The lack of sufficient specialists in this field worsens the entrepreneurial environment and limits the entry of new business models;
- **Sharpening competition**, large entrepreneurs are becoming increasingly aggressive towards the market share of small players in the market. A significant threat that will lead to market bankruptcies and restructuring of the market into a monopoly structure;
- **Unequal access to state financial assistance and subsidies**. Among the owners of small and medium-sized farms in the sector, there is a feeling of injustice in terms of the distribution of subsidies. According to them, larger entrepreneurs absorb most of the financial support and thus achieve even higher competitiveness. In these structures there is a strong concentration of financial capital, which allows them to form a strong lobby in the face of the state;

The elements formulated in this way in the SWOT matrix determine the critical factors for the creation and development of new business models, through the precision agriculture approach. The next stage in the analysis is the validation of the success factors of the new business models. Figure 5 shows the summarized assessment of the interaction of the factors (strategic decision map) determining the success of the new business models.

SWOT matrix		OPPORTUNITIES					THREATS					Σ of the grades in the row
		Creating skills and competence for the implementation of precision agriculture	Cooperation along the value chain	Sharing the financial costs of creating and implementing	New business models enabling increased	Creating know-how alliances	Monopolistic market structure	Strong dependence on the credit policy of commercial banks	Insufficient supply of experienced specialists in the	Intensification of competition, large players are becoming increasingly aggressive	Unequal access to state financial aid and subsidies	
STRENGTHS	Adaptable and motivated to achieve sales growth	66	30	71	79	95	30	33	19	95	33	551
	Good liquidity	33	59	81	30	60	25	91	26	19	11	435
	Striving to implement innovations in production	95	55	75	15	55	91	75	57	85	28	631
	Diversify sources of financial risk	91	99	61	45	45	9	87	8	30	55	530
	They have a sustainable market share	80	65	59	12	11	15	65	16	20	13	356
WEAKNESSES	High indebtedness	60	91	71	44	41	30	99	65	11	15	527
	Insufficient working capital	95	33	81	15	19	59	54	11	57	51	475
	They do not diversify the sources of market risk.	15	30	11	19	25	81	77	19	83	77	437
	Systemic gaps in the implementation of strategic activities for market implementation of the business model	59	79	35	63	51	11	61	71	95	11	536
	They do not have the conditions to attract experienced staff	93	31	9	33	33	9	11	85	28	89	421
Σ of the grades in the column		687	572	554	355	435	360	653	377	523	383	

Figure 5. Map of strategic solutions to encourage entrepreneurs to organize and develop new business models based on precision agriculture. Source: Summary of focus group results. (summary of the opinions of 55 entrepreneurs, distributed in 3 focus groups).

The strategic decision map is analyzed in the following aspects: 1) determining the most significant strengths and weaknesses of entrepreneurs and 2) determining the most significant opportunities and threats to the development of new business models.

The strategic decision map shows that entrepreneurs (focus group participants) determine the preponderance of strengths over weaknesses (see Figure 5) with a strength score of 2503 points, which is higher than the weakness score of 2396 points. These results from the assessment indicate that entrepreneurs have the potential to successfully organize and impose new business models on the market by attacking opportunities with their most significant strengths. Entrepreneurs identify the following as the most significant strengths:

- **Their desire to innovate in production** (see Figure 5, respondents give a score of - 631);
- Entrepreneurs who own small farms are adaptable and motivated to achieve sales growth by increasing their market share by diversifying their products (see Figure 5, the total score of respondents is 551).

The most significant weaknesses that can hinder the process of organizing and imposing new business models on the market are:

- **Systemic gaps in the implementation of strategic planning activities**, for imposing new business models. Respondents gave a score of – 536.
- **The high indebtedness of entrepreneurs** to banks and the suppliers of resources that support their activities (see Figure 5, entrepreneurs gave a score of 527).

In the process of identifying the market success factors of new business models that use the advantages of precision agriculture, the most important elements are the opportunities and threats that arise from the external entrepreneurial environment. These are factors that cannot be controlled by entrepreneurs. The strategic decision map highlights the following two significant opportunities for enhancing the entrepreneurial culture of farmers in order to successfully implement new business models:

- **Creating skills and competencies for precision agriculture** This opportunity was rated with the highest importance by entrepreneurs - 687 points;
- Cooperation along the value chain (see Figure 5, entrepreneurs give a total assessment of this opportunity – 572 points).

In the next stage of the analysis, entrepreneurs identify the most significant threats hindering the process of successful market introduction and development of new business models, namely:

- **The strong dependence of entrepreneurs on the credit policy of banks.** Respondents gave this threat a rating of – 653;
- **The intensification of competition in the market.** The sum of the respondents' ratings is 523.

CONCLUSION

The entrepreneurial factor in Bulgaria is characterized by a high degree of individualism. Farmers are motivated to participate independently in entrepreneurial activity without having a particular desire to share market risk. The low level of cooperation among entrepreneurs will somewhat hinder their aspiration to impose new business models based on digital technologies and precision agriculture. Not

only is training necessary to create new necessary skills and competencies on the part of entrepreneurs, but also strong support from the state to create an even better entrepreneurial environment by lending a hand to small entrepreneurs, who make up about 80% of farms in Bulgaria. Entrepreneurs who manage large-scale farms are already successfully implementing new technologies of precision agriculture and benefiting from its advantages, but they represent only a small part of the entrepreneurial community in the country. Entrepreneurs in agriculture are aware of their responsible and prestigious role in society, which is one of the main motivators for the development of entrepreneurship in rural areas. This role will be one of the main factors for the development of the entrepreneurial spirit in the future.

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COMMUNICATION EFFECTIVENESS AS A DETERMINANT OF COMPETITIVENESS IN WINERIES: EVIDENCE FROM BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

The wine industry remains one of the few agricultural sectors capable of offering products with high added value in contemporary markets. In recent years, the wine market has been characterized as dynamic and highly competitive, not only in terms of price but also in terms of product quality. Consumers have become increasingly discerning, exhibiting heightened expectations regarding wine quality. They are more informed about the characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages of various wine types, which necessitates that wineries and wine-producing enterprises place greater emphasis on effective communication with their customers.

The primary objective of this study is to identify and analyze the main factors influencing communication effectiveness and to examine their relationship with the competitiveness achieved by wine-growing enterprises.

This study provides empirical evidence that communication processes are a critical factor in enhancing the competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises. The strategic management of both internal and external communications has a direct and measurable impact on key economic performance indicators, including sales revenue, profitability, and market share.

KEYWORDS: communications effectiveness, competitiveness, wine industry

ABSTRAKT

Die Weinindustrie ist nach wie vor einer der wenigen landwirtschaftlichen Sektoren, der in der Lage ist, auf den heutigen Märkten Produkte mit hohem Mehrwert anzubieten. In den letzten Jahren hat sich der Weinmarkt als dynamisch und wettbewerbsintensiv erwiesen, nicht nur in Bezug auf den Preis, sondern auch auf die Produktqualität. Die Verbraucher sind immer anspruchsvoller geworden und stellen höhere Erwartungen an die Weinqualität. Sie sind besser über die Eigenschaften, Vor- und Nachteile der verschiedenen Weinsorten informiert, was es erforderlich macht, dass Weinkellereien und weinproduzierende Unternehmen mehr Wert auf eine effektive Kommunikation mit ihren Kunden legen.

Das Hauptziel dieser Studie besteht darin, die wichtigsten Faktoren zu identifizieren und zu analysieren, die die Effektivität der Kommunikation beeinflussen, und ihren Zusammenhang mit der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit von Weinbaubetrieben zu untersuchen.

Die Studie liefert empirische Belege dafür, dass Kommunikationsprozesse ein entscheidender Faktor für die Steigerung der Wettbewerbsfähigkeit von Weinbaubetrieben sind. Das strategische Management sowohl der internen als auch der externen Kommunikation hat einen direkten und messbaren Einfluss auf wichtige wirtschaftliche Leistungsindikatoren wie Umsatz, Rentabilität und Marktanteil.

STICHWORTE: Kommunikationseffizienz, Wettbewerbsfähigkeit, Weinwirtschaft

RÉSUMÉ

L'industrie du vin reste l'un des rares secteurs agricoles capables d'offrir des produits à forte valeur ajoutée sur les marchés contemporains. Ces dernières années, le marché du vin s'est caractérisé

par son dynamisme et sa forte concurrence, non seulement en termes de prix, mais aussi de qualité des produits. Les consommateurs sont devenus de plus en plus exigeants et leurs attentes en matière de qualité du vin sont de plus en plus élevées. Ils sont mieux informés sur les caractéristiques, les avantages et les inconvénients des différents types de vin, ce qui oblige les caves et les entreprises viticoles à mettre davantage l'accent sur une communication efficace avec leurs clients.

L'objectif premier de cette étude est d'identifier et d'analyser les principaux facteurs influençant l'efficacité de la communication et d'examiner leur relation avec la compétitivité atteinte par les entreprises viticoles.

Cette étude fournit des preuves empiriques que les processus de communication sont un facteur critique dans l'amélioration de la compétitivité des entreprises viticoles. La gestion stratégique des communications internes et externes a un impact direct et mesurable sur les principaux indicateurs de performance économique, notamment le chiffre d'affaires, la rentabilité et la part de marché.

MOTS CLÉS: efficacité de la communication, compétitivité, secteur vitivinicole

INTRODUCTION

The wine industry remains one of the few agricultural sectors capable of offering products with high added value in contemporary markets. In recent years, the wine market has been characterized as dynamic and highly competitive, not only in terms of price but also in terms of product quality (Borisov and Radev, 2020). Consumers have become increasingly discerning, exhibiting heightened expectations regarding wine quality. They are more informed about the characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages of various wine types, which necessitates that wineries and wine-producing enterprises place greater emphasis on effective communication with their customers.

While consumers can swiftly adapt their purchasing preferences, wine-producing enterprises tend to restructure more slowly, constrained by a range of internal and external factors (Petrov and Borisov, 2021). Adapting supply to meet changing market demand requires time and resources—investment acquisition, recruitment of personnel with specialized competencies, and the procurement and installation of necessary equipment. All these elements are essential for the production of goods that fully meet consumer expectations. This transformation process is not only time-intensive but also financially demanding. Mismanagement of this transition can lead to significant financial loss or even business failure. Thus, strategic and effective communication with consumers emerges as a critical factor in achieving competitive positioning within the wine market.

Moreover, communication is not solely an external function. It is also an internal organizational process that is triggered by changes in the external environment (Borisova, 2025). This internal communication process is of strategic importance, as it reflects the organization's responsiveness and adaptability. Successful adaptation requires that managers act as effective communicators who can engage employees and align them with the company's evolving objectives. Organizational change typically provokes two key challenges: employee resistance to change and the emergence of conflicts. These dynamics underline the necessity for managers across all levels to possess and cultivate skills in communication, conflict resolution, and negotiation.

These outlined factors form the objective basis for the relevance of the present research. The central thesis posits ***that communication is a fundamental component of effective management in wine-growing enterprises, and its strategic application enhances organizational competitiveness.***

The primary objective of this study is to identify and analyze the main factors influencing communication effectiveness and to examine their relationship with the competitiveness achieved by wine-growing enterprises.

METHODOLOGY FOR TESTING THE MAIN HYPOTHESIS

Communication within a business enterprise is a multifaceted process influenced by both internal and external environmental factors (Borisova, 2025). Accordingly, the study focuses on analyzing the internal environment of wine-growing enterprises through an internal audit of their communication processes.

For the purposes of this study, a clear definition of the unit of analysis is essential. A wine-growing enterprise, in the context of this research, is defined as a business entity in which revenues from the sale of wine and related products constitute at least 50% of its total annual revenues. These enterprises must comply with the Accounting Act and publicly disclose their financial and accounting reports, accessible through the Registry Agency of the Republic of Bulgaria.

The sampling frame was derived from the register of the National Chamber of Vine and Wine – Sofia, which includes all officially registered wine-growing enterprises as of 31 December 2021. The total population consists of 11,231 enterprises. A simple random sampling method was employed, using a non-replacement selection approach (Borisov and Shilev, 2024). The resulting sample comprises 52 wine-growing enterprises.

To assess the level of competitiveness among these enterprises, the following key indicators were utilized (Borisov, Stoeva and Dirimanova, 2021):

- (1) Sales revenue (in BGN);
- (2) Sales profitability (as a percentage);
- (3) Market share (as a percentage).

Table 1. Statistical model for testing the main hypothesis of the study. Source: Own.

Factors - cause	Impact on sales revenue	Impact on sales profitability	Impact on market share
The type of communication channels	X	X	X
Disruptions in the communication process	X	X	X
The type of organizational and management structure	X	X	X
Leadership style	X	X	X
The sources of conflict	X	X	X
Customer communication channels	X	X	X
Communication message and effective feedback /clients/	X	X	X
Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders	X	X	X

The diagnostic assessment of the communication process in wine-growing enterprises is conducted through the examination of interactions between two categories of factors: causal factors and outcome factors. The **causal factors** encompass those variables that determine the effectiveness of internal and external communication processes, whereas the **outcome factors** refer to the indicators that reflect the competitiveness of the enterprises.

The statistical model used to characterize the interactions between these factors is presented in **Table 1**. The relationship between communication effectiveness and competitiveness is further analyzed using the **Chi-square (χ^2) statistical method**.

The **Chi-square method** is particularly well-suited for identifying correlation-type relationships, which are prevalent in socio-economic research. This method seeks to determine the extent to which a

presumed relationship exists objectively and non-randomly within a given dataset. It provides a framework for evaluating whether the observed association between variables arises from an actual underlying dependence or is simply a product of random variation.

Application of the Chi-square method requires a prior **cross-classification (grouping)** of the units of analysis based on the values of the features being studied. This results in **two-dimensional, three-dimensional, or multidimensional empirical frequency distributions**, typically represented in tabular form. The method involves comparing two distributions: one **empirical**, derived from observed data, and one **theoretical**, which assumes no relationship between the variables. By contrasting these distributions, the method establishes a **test statistic (χ^2)** that serves as a criterion for confirming or rejecting the existence of a statistically significant relationship between the studied variables.

The subsequent stage of the analysis focuses on **determining the strength of the relationship**, or the degree of association between the variables. In the context of the Chi-square method, this is achieved through the use of specific **association measures (coefficients)**, which are generally divided into two categories:

1. **Measures based on the estimated χ^2 value**, including:
 - Phi-square coefficient (ϕ^2)
 - Tschuprow's coefficient (T^2)
 - Cramér's V coefficient (V^2)
 - Pearson's contingency coefficient (C)
2. **Measures not based on the χ^2 value**, including:
 - Kendall's coefficient (Q)
 - Pearson's coefficient (A)
 - Yule's coefficient (γ)

The selection of the appropriate coefficient depends primarily on the structure of the contingency tables—specifically, whether the number of rows equals the number of columns. In this study, since the number of rows differs from the number of columns ($p \neq k$), the **Cramér's V coefficient (V^2)** is employed to assess the strength of the relationship.

Cramér's V is particularly advantageous in cases where contingency tables are asymmetrical. It ranges from **0 to 1 ($0 \leq V^2 \leq 1$)**, offering a standardized measure of association regardless of table size. The closer the coefficient is to **1**, the stronger the relationship between the variables; conversely, values approaching **0** indicate a weak relationship. The coefficient quantifies the proportion of variation in one variable that can be explained by variation in the other, thereby providing meaningful insight into the extent of the interdependence between communication effectiveness and enterprise competitiveness.

$$V^2 = \frac{\chi^2_{em}}{\sum \sum f_{ij} [\min(p-1) \text{ or } \min(k-1)]}$$

where:

$[\min(p-1) \text{ or } \min(k-1)]$ is the smaller of the two differences $(p-1)$ or $(k-1)$." (Saykova, 2002)

Based on the constructed statistical model, the following statistical hypotheses are defined, through the verification of which the main hypothesis of the dissertation is sought to be proven or rejected:

Table 2. Working hypotheses of the study – description and verification methods. Source: Own.

Working hypotheses	Relationship description	Method for testing the validity of the hypothesis
<p>H11 <i>The choice of communication channel in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H10 <i>The choice of communication channel in the organization does not determine the achieved competitiveness</i></p>	The assumption is that the type of communication channel that personnel use determines the effectiveness and competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H21 <i>Disruptions in the communication process impair competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H20 <i>Disruptions in the communication process do not impair competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that disruptions in the communication process are the cause of deterioration in the efficiency and competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H31 <i>The choice of communication network in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H30 <i>The choice of communication network in the organization does not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that the communication network determines the effectiveness and competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H41 <i>The leadership style in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H40 <i>The leadership style in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that leadership style determines the effectiveness and competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H51 <i>The sources of conflicts determine the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H50 <i>The sources of conflicts do not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that sources of conflict impair efficiency and may be a prerequisite for reducing the competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H61 <i>The channel for communication with customers determines the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H60 <i>The customer communication channel does not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that the communication channel determines the effectiveness and competitiveness of the organization	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H71 <i>The communication message and effective feedback with customers determine the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H70 <i>The communication message and effective customer feedback do not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that the communication message and effective customer feedback determine the effectiveness and competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators
<p>H81 <i>Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders worsen the achieved competitiveness;</i></p> <p>H80 <i>Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders do not impair the achieved competitiveness;</i></p>	The assumption is that the communication process determines the effectiveness and competitiveness of the organization.	Chi-square analysis with Cramer's coefficient to test the strength of the relationship between the studied indicators

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The principal hypothesis tested in this study posits that **communication is a critical component of the effective management of wine-growing enterprises**, and that its **strategic implementation serves as a source of competitive advantage** in the marketplace.

Based on the results of the statistical analysis, it was established that **all causal factors** included in the statistical model presented in **Table 2** (in the methodological section) exert a **systematic influence on sales revenue**. This finding underscores the integral role of communication-related variables in shaping enterprise performance outcomes.

The strength of the relationship between the causal factors and the sales revenue indicator was evaluated using **Cramér's V coefficient**. The coefficient values indicate a **strong association**, suggesting that, *ceteris paribus*, the factors under investigation significantly affect the **competitiveness** of the wine-growing enterprises, as reflected by their **sales revenue** (see **Table 3**).

Further analysis reveals that **two specific factors** have a systematic impact on the **profitability of sales**:

1. **Customer communication channels**
2. **Disruptions in communication processes with stakeholders** (see **Table 3**)

In addition, **three key factors** were found to influence **market share**:

1. **Leadership style**
2. **Customer communication channels**
3. **Communication messaging and effectiveness of feedback mechanisms**

These results provide empirical support for the argument that strategic communication practices—both internal and external—contribute meaningfully to various dimensions of competitive performance.

Overall, the **main hypothesis** of the study is **partially confirmed**. Out of a total of **24 working hypotheses**, **13 demonstrated statistically significant relationships** between the communication variables and indicators of competitiveness (see **Table 4**). This partial confirmation highlights the complexity of the relationship while affirming the importance of communication as a driver of enterprise success in the wine sector.

Table 3. Results of testing the relationship between the studied factors, using the chi-square analysis method. Source: Own.

Factors - cause	Impact on sales revenue	Impact on sales profitability	Impact on market share
The type of communication channels	connection (0.515)*	no connection (0.105)*	no connection (0.111)*
Disruptions in the communication process	connection (0.465)*	no connection (0.109)*	no connection (0.123)*
The type of organizational and management structure	connection (0.489)	no connection (0.111)*	no connection (0.120)*
Leadership style	connection (0.399)*	no connection (0.133)*	connection (0.377)*
The sources of conflict	connection (0.251)*	no connection (0.155)*	no connection (0.125)*
Customer communication channels	connection (0.583)*	connection (0.454)*	connection (0.618)*
Communication message and effective feedback /clients/	connection (0.399)*	no connection (0.125)*	connection (0.759)*
Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders	connection (0.413)*	connection (0.257)*	no connection (0.0008)*

* value of Cramer's coefficient V2

Table 4. Hypotheses proven in the course of the study. Results of applying the statistical method chi-square analysis

Working hypotheses	Proven hypotheses
<i>H11 The choice of communication channel in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H10The choice of communication channel in the organization does not determine the achieved competitiveness</i>	<i>H11 The choice of communication channel in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness expressed through the sales revenue indicator.</i>
<i>H21 Disruptions in the communication process impair competitiveness;</i> <i>H20Disruptions in the communication process do not impair competitiveness;</i>	<i>H21 Disruptions in the communication process worsen competitiveness as expressed by the sales revenue indicator</i>
<i>H31 The choice of communication network in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H30The choice of communication network in the organization does not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i>	<i>H31 The choice of communication network in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness expressed through the sales revenue indicator.</i>
<i>H41 The leadership style in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H40The leadership style in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness;</i>	<i>H41 The leadership style in the organization determines the achieved competitiveness expressed through the indicators of sales revenue and market share.</i>
<i>H51 The sources of conflicts determine the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H50The sources of conflicts do not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i>	<i>H51 The sources of conflicts determine the achieved competitiveness expressed through the sales revenue indicator</i>
<i>H61 The channel for communication with customers determines the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H60The customer communication channel does not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i>	<i>H61 The channel for communication with customers determines the achieved competitiveness expressed through the indicators of sales revenue, sales profitability and market share.</i>
<i>H71 The communication message and effective feedback with customers determine the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H70 The communication message and effective customer feedback do not determine the achieved competitiveness;</i>	<i>H71 The communication message and effective feedback with customers determine the achieved competitiveness expressed through the indicators of sales revenue and market share.</i>
<i>H81 Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders worsen the achieved competitiveness;</i> <i>H80 Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders do not impair the achieved competitiveness;</i>	<i>H81 Disruptions in the communication process with stakeholders worsen the achieved competitiveness expressed through the indicators of sales revenue and market share.</i>

CONCLUSION

This study provides empirical evidence that **communication processes are a critical factor in enhancing the competitiveness of wine-growing enterprises**. The **strategic management** of both **internal and external communications** has a direct and measurable impact on key economic performance indicators, including **sales revenue, profitability, and market share**.

Drawing on data from a representative sample of **52 enterprises** and employing **Chi-square analysis** in combination with **Cramér's V coefficient**, the following key conclusions were reached:

- The **strongest influence on enterprise competitiveness** is exerted by four primary factors:
 1. **Customer communication channels**
 2. **Leadership style**
 3. **Communication messaging and the effectiveness of feedback mechanisms**
 4. **Disruptions in communication processes with stakeholders**
- Of the **24 working hypotheses** tested, **13 revealed statistically significant relationships** between the **effectiveness of communication** and **enterprise performance outcomes**.
- **Internal (intra-organizational) communication** plays a particularly important role in processes of **adaptation and organizational change**. Its quality can act either as a **catalyst** for improvement or as a **barrier to operational efficiency**.

In conclusion, effective communication management should be regarded not only as a supporting function but also as a **strategic resource**. In the context of a highly dynamic and competitive market environment, **well-structured and responsive communication systems** are essential for **sustainable development** and can serve as a **distinct source of competitive advantage** for wine-growing enterprises.

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INTEGRATING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE INTO LOCAL DEVELOPMENT: THE POTENTIAL OF AI TO IMPROVE THE MANAGEMENT AND EFFECTIVENESS OF LOCAL ACTION GROUPS (LAGS)

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ABSTRACT

This publication explores the potential of artificial intelligence (AI) to transform the activities of Local Action Groups (LAGs). Through qualitative and conceptual analysis based on contemporary scientific literature and good practices from Europe and around the world, a framework for possible applications of AI in five key areas is developed: automation of administrative processes, intelligent analysis of community needs, digital consulting support, predictive analysis and modeling, and identification of new partnerships. The study offers an interpretative reading of the opportunities, but also of the barriers to AI implementation, including technological, institutional, social, and ethical aspects. Recommendations for future action are formulated, including pilot implementation, capacity building, and strategic coordination at the national and local levels. The results highlight the need for an integrated and carefully structured approach to the digital transformation of local development, in which AI serves as a support to human participation rather than a substitute for it.

KEY WORDS: artificial intelligence; local development; local action groups; regional development

ABSTRAKT

Diese Veröffentlichung untersucht das Potenzial künstlicher Intelligenz (KI) für die Transformation der Aktivitäten lokaler Aktionsgruppen (LAGs). Anhand einer qualitativen und konzeptionellen Analyse auf der Grundlage aktueller wissenschaftlicher Literatur und bewährter Verfahren aus Europa und der ganzen Welt wird ein Rahmen für mögliche Anwendungen von KI in fünf Schlüsselbereichen entwickelt: Automatisierung von Verwaltungsprozessen, intelligente Analyse der Bedürfnisse von Gemeinschaften, digitale Beratungsunterstützung, prädiktive Analyse und Modellierung sowie Identifizierung neuer Partnerschaften. Die Studie bietet eine interpretative Lesart der Chancen, aber auch der Hindernisse für die Umsetzung von KI, einschließlich technologischer, institutioneller, sozialer und ethischer Aspekte. Es werden Empfehlungen für künftige Maßnahmen formuliert, darunter Pilotprojekte, Kapazitätsaufbau und strategische Koordinierung auf nationaler und lokaler Ebene. Die Ergebnisse unterstreichen die Notwendigkeit eines integrierten und sorgfältig strukturierten Ansatzes für die digitale Transformation der lokalen Entwicklung, bei dem KI als Unterstützung der menschlichen Beteiligung und nicht als Ersatz dafür dient.

STICHWORTE: künstliche Intelligenz; lokale Entwicklung; lokale Aktionsgruppen; regionale Entwicklung

RÉSUMÉ

Cette publication explore le potentiel de l'intelligence artificielle (IA) pour transformer les activités des groupes d'action locale (GAL). À travers une analyse qualitative et conceptuelle fondée sur la littérature scientifique contemporaine et les bonnes pratiques en Europe et dans le monde, un cadre pour les applications possibles de l'IA dans cinq domaines clés est développé : automatisation des processus

administratifs, analyse intelligente des besoins communautaires, soutien à la consultation numérique, analyse prédictive et modélisation, et identification de nouveaux partenariats. L'étude propose une lecture interprétative des opportunités, mais aussi des obstacles à la mise en œuvre de l'IA, y compris les aspects technologiques, institutionnels, sociaux et éthiques. Des recommandations pour l'avenir sont formulées, notamment la mise en œuvre de projets pilotes, le renforcement des capacités et la coordination stratégique aux niveaux national et local. Les résultats soulignent la nécessité d'une approche intégrée et soigneusement structurée de la transformation numérique du développement local, dans laquelle l'IA sert de soutien à la participation humaine plutôt que de substitut à celle-ci.

MOTS CLÉS: intelligence artificielle; développement local ; groupes d'action locale ; développement régional

INTRODUCTION

In the context of increasing complexity and dynamics of socio-economic development, local communities are faced with the need to seek new, more effective approaches to planning, managing, and implementing initiatives that meet their specific needs. In this context, the LEADER approach (Liaison Entre Actions de Développement de l'Économie Rurale) and its continuation, CLLD (Community-Led Local Development), are establishing themselves as innovative instruments of the European Union for promoting sustainable and inclusive development in rural and maritime areas through the active participation of local action groups (LAGs).

LAGs are a kind of “local engine” for change, bringing together representatives of the public, private, and civil sectors to formulate and implement strategies based on local needs and resources. Despite the undeniable achievements of this model in Bulgaria, challenges such as administrative burden, limited expert capacity, and the need for more precise targeting of the real needs of local communities continue to hinder its optimal functioning.

At the same time, recent years have seen rapid development of artificial intelligence (AI), which is emerging as a transformative factor in several areas, from healthcare and education to industry and public administration. The integration of AI into local development represents an unexplored but extremely promising opportunity to increase the effectiveness, transparency, and adaptability of LAGs. This opens up potential for the automation of routine processes, intelligent data analysis, personalized communication with citizens, and strategic planning based on predictive models.

This publication aims to outline the potential applications of artificial intelligence in the context of local action groups in Bulgaria and to explore how these technologies could support the implementation of the LEADER/CLLD approach. The focus is on five key areas: administrative automation, community needs analysis, digital advisory support, predictive analysis, and partnership promotion. The study offers a conceptual framework for the future application of AI in local development and lays the groundwork for a more in-depth discussion on the digital transformation of LAGs.

Literature review. Artificial intelligence (AI) is rapidly establishing itself as a key factor for transformation in development management and public services. AI technologies not only optimize routine processes but also offer new opportunities for forecasting, adaptability, and citizen involvement in decision-making. AI could radically transform development theory and practice by prompting a rethinking of how data and algorithms are combined to generate knowledge (Bjola, 2022).

Research in the field of AI and public administration shows that the application of algorithms in the local context requires a balance between innovation and social responsibility. The introduction of AI in local administrations must balance benefits, risks, and social effects to ensure responsible innovation (Yigitcanlar et al., 2024). The concept of “algorithmic bureaucracy” is being introduced—a new model of governance in which automation and predictive analytics are integrated into the daily work of the administration (Bibri et al., 2023).

One promising direction is related to citizen participation in the co-creation of AI solutions. Community-based citizen science empowers local residents to co-create AI solutions, ensuring their relevance and social impact (Hsu et al., 2022). The citizen science approach not only improves data quality but also strengthens the legitimacy of algorithmic recommendations. This is in line with the LEADER philosophy, which places local communities at the center of planning and implementation processes.

The role of AI in the non-governmental sector also offers valuable lessons for LAGs. AI improves program design, optimizes resource management, and enables predictive analysis in the activities of non-governmental organizations (Efthymiou, Alevizos, & Sidiropoulos, 2023). In the context of public-civil partnerships, such functionalities can be directly applied to project and strategy management by LAGs.

An example of successful AI implementation in rural areas is provided by the International Fund for Agricultural Development (IFAD). Insights generated by AI help us quickly and accurately understand changes and provide targeted advice (Bousios, O'Neill, & Cepeda, 2023). Through digital analysis and monitoring tools, AI enables early identification of risks and needs, which is particularly valuable in a context of social vulnerability and limited resources.

In project management, AI facilitates informed decision-making through automated data processing, schedule forecasting, and risk identification. AI helps identify potential difficulties, manage resources more efficiently, and simulate results even before implementation (Shoushtari, Daghighi, & Ghafourian, 2024).

AI can improve local economic activity by connecting rural residents with services, education, and employment based on localized needs (Papakonstantinidis & Bogonikolos, 2025). This highlights AI's ability to address not only administrative and technical challenges but also social inequalities.

When we talk about Bulgaria, where there are serious demographic and infrastructure challenges, the need for technological support is particularly pronounced. Rural areas in Bulgaria have the highest share of the population at risk of poverty or social exclusion among EU countries (Petrov, 2021). In this regard, several authors analyze the possibilities for applying smart solutions (Tsongov, Petrov, 2022, 2023; Tsongov, Petrov, Tsvetelina-Berberova-Valcheva, 2022), including combining these solutions in a new regional policy (Borisov, Petrov, Tsongov, 2024; Petrov, Tsongov, 2025). These measures related to regional development and supporting Local Action Groups as a modern tool in this direction also include building sustainable and smart cities (Tsongov, Petrov, 2024) and the creation of a favorable business environment using new technological and smart solutions (Tsankov, 2024).

The digital and green transition will further deepen inequalities between regions in Europe (Maucorps, Römisch, Schwab, & Vujanović, 2023). This implies that innovations such as AI must be introduced with regional specificity and social contexts in mind so as not to deepen existing divisions.

Thanks to LEADER and AI, rural Finland already offers remote care for elderly and vulnerable residents (European CAP Network, 2023). Such applications show that AI can be successfully adapted to the needs of sparsely populated areas.

AI-based analytics can support the collection and assessment of sustainable indicators in rural development strategies (Memo & Pienkowski, 2023). This is particularly relevant for LAGs, which often need more accurate and easy-to-track monitoring mechanisms.

LAGs are a weak link in communicating information about the EU, its objectives, and its regional policy (Furmankiewicz, Hewitt, Jane, & Kołodzyńska, 2024). This reveals not only a deficit in communication but also in the capacity to adopt and use modern digital solutions.

"Without active convergence measures, the effects of digital innovation are likely to be unevenly distributed (EC, 2022). To avoid this, LAGs need to be targeted with policies, training, and resources.

In summary, AI can improve local development management through automation, intelligent analysis, and personalized support. However, to realize this potential, implementation must be tailored to territorial realities, social dynamics, and the need for human involvement and control.

Methodology. This study adopts a systematic and conceptual approach that aims to outline the potential of artificial intelligence for improving the effectiveness and sustainability of LAGs in the context of the LEADER/CLLD approach. The choice of this approach is justified by the innovative nature of the topic and the lack of systematic research that directly examines the interaction between AI technologies and the functioning of LAGs in Bulgarian or European countries. Rather than striving for empirical validity through field research, the study focuses on building an analytical framework that can serve as a starting point for future applied research and pilot projects.

The first stage of the study includes a review and systematization of relevant scientific literature, as well as an analysis of examples from international and European practice. Sources from peer-reviewed academic journals, reports from international organizations (such as IFAD, the European Commission, Bertelsmann Stiftung), as well as specific case studies of AI implementation in the context of public administration, local development, and the non-governmental sector are used.

In the second stage, a conceptual analysis is applied to define and structure the main areas in which artificial intelligence could have a positive impact on the functioning of the LAG. These areas are identified on the basis of existing challenges within the LEADER approach (such as administrative burden, limited access to data, low level of digitization, etc.), with specific opportunities offered by modern AI technologies. This has resulted in a framework typology of five possible AI applications, which are discussed in detail in the "Results" section.

The third analytical component of the study consists of an interpretative assessment of the obstacles and risks associated with the application of AI in local development. This takes into account both the structural inequalities between regions and the institutional readiness of LAGs, the socio-cultural characteristics of rural areas, and the ethical aspects of automated decision-making. The analysis does not claim to be exhaustive. Still, it aims to highlight the main preconditions under which the integration of AI would be not only technically feasible, but also socially legitimate and sustainable.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Five main areas have been identified where AI can be integrated to improve the effectiveness, sustainability, and strategic focus of the local initiative group approach.

Figure 1. Main areas for interaction with AI. Source: Own interpretation.

Firstly, artificial intelligence provides the opportunity to automate administrative processes related to evaluating, monitoring, and reporting project proposals. Through natural language processing and data structuring algorithms, key indicators can be identified, preliminary compliance checks can be performed, and automated reports can be generated to support the work of LAG experts and managing authorities. This reduces document processing time, minimizes administrative errors, and increases the transparency of procedures.

Secondly, AI can be applied to the intelligent analysis of local community needs. The use of data from surveys, social networks, geolocation platforms, and open statistical sources makes it possible to extract hidden dependencies, behavioral patterns, and emerging needs of specific social groups. This way, LAG strategic planning can be based not only on traditional demographic and economic info, but also on dynamic, real-time data that reflects people's attitudes and needs.

The third strand relates to personalized digital support for applicants through the introduction of AI-based advisors in the form of chatbots or digital assistants. These can provide information on application procedures, eligibility of costs, and appropriate measures within the strategy of the LAG concerned. In addition to increasing the accessibility of information, such tools can be trained to answer questions asked in plain language, simulate the application process, and direct users to the most appropriate resources. This is particularly valuable for remote areas and vulnerable groups with limited access to administrative services.

The fourth opportunity relates to predictive analysis and impact assessment. Using historical data from completed projects and local socio-economic indicators, AI can model the potential effect of future

project proposals. This helps prioritize projects with high added value and provides LAGs with simulation tools to assess different development scenarios in the context of demographic change, climate risks, or market transformations.

The last identified element is related to the use of AI to identify new opportunities for partnership and cross-sectoral cooperation. By analyzing databases of projects, strategic documents, online collaboration platforms, and geospatial data, AI can suggest new potential partners from the public, private, and civil sectors to LAGs. This encourages innovative forms of cooperation, multidisciplinary projects, and cross-border initiatives within the EU.

The proposed framework is not universally applicable, but rather conceptually oriented and subject to adaptation to the specific capacity, context, and strategic priorities of each LAG. In this sense, it provides a basis for future pilot projects and policy decisions aimed at the digital transformation of local development in Bulgaria and Europe.

The integration of artificial intelligence into the activities of Local Action Groups (LAGs) offers promising prospects for improving the effectiveness, adaptability, and strategic focus of local development. However, the implementation of such a transformation requires careful consideration of a number of interrelated factors—institutional, technological, social, and ethical.

Firstly, the technological readiness and administrative capacity of many LAGs in Bulgaria remain limited. The lack of sufficiently trained staff and the inability to finance modern software solutions create real barriers to the implementation of AI. This finding is confirmed by a study by Maucorps et al. (2023), which found that the effects of digital transformation in Europe are highly asymmetrical, with less developed regions structurally limited in their ability to reap the benefits of AI. Thus, local development led by LAGs requires not only technological innovation but also parallel investment in human capital and infrastructure.

Alongside the technical challenges, an important aspect is the need to apply AI following the principles of ethics, transparency, and personal data protection. Automated systems that support assessment, analysis, and decision-making processes must be understandable and traceable so as not to compromise trust in public fund management mechanisms. As Bjola (2022) notes, the potential of AI to transform public policy must be accompanied by a critical awareness of its limitations and risks. This requires the creation of frameworks for the responsible use of algorithms, including mechanisms for human oversight, feedback, and error correction.

The adaptability of AI solutions to the territorial and social context of LAGs is also essential. According to Petrov (2021), Bulgarian rural areas are characterized by demographic decline, an aging population, low digital literacy, and poorly developed social infrastructure. This means that any technological solution must be culturally and linguistically sensitive and complemented by a human intermediary—be it a digital mediator, local coordinator, or trained consultant—to assist end users. In this way, AI does not replace the human factor, but complements and enhances it.

The framework presented in this study should be seen as a starting point for concrete action rather than a universal solution. It is recommended that the proposed applications be tested through pilot initiatives in several LAGs with relatively high capacity, motivation for innovation, and experience in cross-sectoral partnerships. Such pilot projects could generate adaptive models and practical tools that could subsequently be scaled up to other regions. In this sense, the concept of AI integration should not be seen as a one-off intervention, but as a step-by-step process of institutional learning and technological adaptation.

Last but not least, the strategic framework for such a transformation requires political commitment and coordination between different administrative levels, from local to national. The local initiative group approach, which in principle places the local community at the center of the development process, may prove particularly suitable for AI implementation precisely because it ensures horizontal connectivity between stakeholders. However, to realize this potential, the digital transformation of LAGs should be included in national strategic documents and supported by targeted funding mechanisms, technical assistance, and interregional cooperation.

CONCLUSION

This study outlines the potential of artificial intelligence as an innovative tool for transforming the way LAGs operate within this approach. In the context of a growing need for more effective, transparent, and adaptive local development management, AI offers opportunities that go beyond purely technological dimensions and fit into the logic of sustainable, inclusive, and smart territorial policy.

Despite the opportunities outlined, the integration of AI is not without challenges. Limited administrative capacity, inadequate digital infrastructure, social inequalities, and the lack of policy mechanisms to support innovation in rural areas remain serious obstacles. In addition, the application of algorithms in processes related to public resources and civil rights requires strict compliance with ethical standards, transparency, and the possibility of human control.

To realize the vision presented, a phased and adaptive approach is needed, including pilot initiatives, transfer of good practices, building technical and analytical capacity at the local level, and systematic coordination between all stakeholders. The effective integration of AI into the activities of LAGs must be accompanied by a strategic framework at the national and European level in which digital transformation is seen not only as a technological change but also as a social and cultural change.

In conclusion, artificial intelligence should be seen not as a threat to human involvement in local development management but as a tool that can strengthen the role of the community, improve the effectiveness of public policies, and open up new horizons for interaction between people, technologies, and territories. The transition to digitally intelligent LAGs is both a necessity and an opportunity—an opportunity that should not be missed.

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OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING THE TECHNICAL INFRASTRUCTURE FOR THE MODERNIZATION OF SETTLEMENTS IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the problems of a normative-regulatory nature related to the construction of the technical infrastructure in Bulgarian settlements. The problems that need to be solved are derived from the foundation of the legislation and the imposed practice by the state as an owner and the relevant competencies assigned to the public authorities at the central and local levels. Separate parts and problems of the infrastructure are analyzed, such as gas supply, protection of the local environment and road facilities and others that are important for the functioning of settlements and settlements. The corresponding conclusions and assessments are made about the possibilities for improving the level of public works in our country, and the main challenges facing the development of settlements are outlined on the basis of the regulatory framework and the influence of the legal framework on the ongoing processes.

KEYWORDS: infrastructure, development, management, public works, construction, laws, rules and institutions

ABSTRAKT

Dieser Artikel befasst sich mit den normativen und regulatorischen Problemen im Zusammenhang mit dem Bau technischer Infrastruktur in bulgarischen Siedlungen. Die zu lösenden Probleme ergeben sich aus den gesetzlichen Grundlagen und der vom Staat als Eigentümer vorgegebenen Praxis sowie den entsprechenden Kompetenzen der öffentlichen Behörden auf zentraler und lokaler Ebene. Einzelne Aspekte und Probleme der Infrastruktur werden analysiert, wie z. B. Gasversorgung, Umweltschutz und Straßenbau sowie weitere für das Funktionieren von Siedlungen wichtige Aspekte. Die entsprechenden Schlussfolgerungen und Bewertungen werden zu den Möglichkeiten zur Verbesserung des Niveaus öffentlicher Bauvorhaben in Bulgarien gezogen. Die wichtigsten Herausforderungen für die Siedlungsentwicklung werden anhand des regulatorischen Rahmens und seines Einflusses auf die laufenden Prozesse skizziert.

STICHWORTE: Infrastruktur, Entwicklung, Management, öffentliche Bauvorhaben, Bauwesen, Gesetze, Vorschriften und Institutionen

RÉSUMÉ

Cet article est consacré aux problèmes normatifs et réglementaires liés à la construction d'infrastructures techniques dans les agglomérations bulgares. Les problèmes à résoudre découlent des fondements de la législation et des pratiques imposées par l'État en tant que propriétaire, ainsi que des compétences attribuées aux autorités publiques aux niveaux central et local. Différents aspects et problèmes des infrastructures sont analysés, tels que l'approvisionnement en gaz, la protection de l'environnement et les infrastructures routières, ainsi que d'autres éléments importants pour le fonctionnement des agglomérations. Des conclusions et des évaluations sont formulées quant aux possibilités d'amélioration du niveau des travaux publics dans notre pays, et les principaux défis auxquels le développement des agglomérations est confronté sont décrits en fonction du cadre réglementaire et de l'influence du cadre juridique sur les processus en cours.

MOTS-CLÉS: infrastructure, développement, gestion, travaux publics, construction, lois, règles et institutions

INTRODUCTION

Technical infrastructure is a system of buildings, facilities and linear engineering networks of transport, water supply and sewage, electricity supply, heat supply, gas supply, electronic communications, hydromelioration, waste treatment and geoprotection activities.

Elements of technical infrastructure are the transport technical infrastructure and its facilities (bridges, tunnels, overpasses, underpasses, crossings, etc.); transmission (supply and discharge) pipelines (networks) and their facilities in an unregulated territory; also transmission (supply and discharge) pipelines (networks) and their facilities in a regulated territory; as well as distribution pipelines and distribution devices and their facilities (transformer stations, electrical substations, drinking and wastewater treatment plants, step-down and distribution stations, etc.), including connecting pipelines to building installations and general measuring devices.

In addition to the technical infrastructure, there are also hydro-ameliorative transmission (supply and discharge) pipelines (networks) and the facilities attached to them and hydro-ameliorative structures built to protect against the harmful effects of water. Networks and facilities also include receiving and transmitting stations and the remaining physical infrastructure intended for the deployment of electronic communications networks, coastal fortification, coastal protection and geo-protection structures and facilities and installations for waste treatment.

The elements of the technical infrastructure are provided for in development plans. An integral part of the general and detailed development plans are the plan-schemes of the elements of the technical infrastructure. The pipelines and facilities of the technical infrastructure are built, maintained and repaired by and at the expense of the state, municipalities or the relevant operating companies, unless otherwise provided for in a special law.

Important for territorial planning and the development of settlements (urbanism) with subsequent amendments and additions and includes short-term, medium-term and long-term provisions, at the level of the entire basic administrative-territorial unit, regarding structural elements, forms of ownership, risk

zones, etc., as well as elements and information regarding the future development of the area and guidelines for functional development of the territory.

Street networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure. The structural analysis of Bulgarian settlements and their infrastructure will provide an indispensable picture in identifying problems and solutions for entering into a legal form. Our analysis will rest more on a normative and regulatory perspective than on economic analysis. Thus, information will be obtained that can be applicable to the modern settlement, which covers the following aspects: structure, housing development, transport arrangements, current activity status, profession, workplace, professional status, geographical location of the workplace, type of economic sector in which the active population works, people seeking work, form of social protection. The pipes of the technical infrastructure and the facilities of the transport infrastructure, related to the movement of vehicles and pedestrians, are designed and built as street networks and facilities. The location of the underground and aboveground street networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure is determined by the general and detailed development plans in compliance with the relevant technical rules and regulations. In the presence of existing pipes or facilities - public state or public municipal property, which for technical reasons are impossible to be moved, they are allowed to be preserved through their respective designation with a detailed development plan. The Minister of Regional Development and Public Works shall issue an ordinance on the rules and norms for the placement of conduits and facilities of the technical infrastructure (including electronic communications networks).

The mayor of the municipality or an official authorized by him shall ensure the necessary consistency in the laying and construction of the individual underground street networks and facilities and coordinate the underground with the above-ground street construction.

The works related to the excavation of street and sidewalk surfaces and internal neighborhood spaces shall be carried out on the basis of a construction permit. The contracting authority shall notify the relevant municipal administration of the commencement of construction after coordination with the traffic safety authorities. In the event of damage to the underground networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure, which must be repaired immediately, the contracting authority or the operating company may begin the works immediately, notifying the relevant municipal administration and the owners of the affected land properties. When, in connection with the construction, it is necessary to change the position or structure of constructed underground and above-ground street networks and facilities, the relevant works shall be carried out by the contracting authority of the new construction at its expense after approval of the necessary projects, coordinated with the operating companies whose networks and facilities are affected, and after issuing a construction permit. In the cases of pipelines and facilities provided for relocation in the detailed development plans and the specialized schemes to them, the funds for the new construction shall be at the expense of the contracting authority. In the event of non-implemented street regulation, when construction of new or reconstruction of existing pipelines is necessary for the relevant territory, with the exception of transmission pipelines, temporary supply may be allowed under the existing position of the terrain with a notarized declaration of the contracting authority (or the relevant operating company) for voluntary relocation at its expense in the future implementation of the detailed development plan. In these cases, the provisions of Art. 192 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA) shall apply. In recent years, the construction of green infrastructure has also been of

great importance, which is especially relevant in the area of tourist cities and settlements with cultural landmarks. (Kabakchieva and Vasileva, 2023)

The builder of street networks and technical infrastructure facilities is obliged, before the start of construction, to take the necessary measures to ensure safety, by erecting fences and crossings, placing warning signs, instructions for diverting traffic, etc.; to take the necessary measures to protect existing underground and aboveground networks and facilities, geodetic signs, green areas, ornamental trees, etc. from damage and displacement; to notify the municipal administration of underground and aboveground networks and facilities discovered during the implementation, not marked in the relevant specialized maps and registers; such networks and facilities shall be closed only after they have been photographed in accordance with the established procedure; to immediately notify the municipal administration and the nearest historical museum upon the discovery of archaeological finds; to immediately notify the fire safety and population protection and traffic safety authorities of the beginning and duration of construction on the relevant streets that are being excavated; to immediately notify the relevant services and operating companies of any possible damage to networks and facilities that occurred during the work, and if it concerns damage to water pipes, heating pipes or gas pipes – to immediately notify the hygienic-epidemiological and fire safety and population protection authorities; to notify at least three days in advance the municipal administration, as well as the services and operating companies that manage and operate the networks and facilities, of the upcoming backfilling of newly constructed or reconstructed underground networks and facilities; to carry out necessary restoration work at its own expense within the time limits set by the municipal administration and to eliminate the damage caused, ascertained by the municipal administration and reflected in a report of findings, within the time limits set by the municipal administration.

The municipal administration shall permit the networks and facilities to be backfilled after verifying that the specified construction line and other conditions and requirements for the implementation of the construction have been complied with, the networks and facilities have been photographed and recorded in the relevant specialized maps and registers under Art. 115, para. 4 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA). A protocol shall be drawn up for the results of the inspection. After the completion of the construction, executive documentation shall be prepared and certified in accordance with Art. 175 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA). The contracting authority shall immediately submit one copy of the documentation to the municipality and to the relevant operating companies.

Roads, streets and transport networks and facilities. The elements of the transport technical infrastructure are built on the basis of the provisions of the general and detailed development plans, linked to the structure of the territory. The transport technical infrastructure should provide the best conditions for comfortable, safe and economical transport of passengers and goods and for accessibility for persons with disabilities, while protecting the environment. The Minister of Regional Development and Public Works issues regulations on the standards for planning and design of the elements of the transport technical infrastructure. The standards for planning and design of the elements of the railway infrastructure are determined by regulation of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works and the Minister of Transport, Information Technologies and Communications.

The design and construction of motorways, expressways and first and second class roads of the republican road network through the territory of populated areas is allowed as an exception when the

following conditions are simultaneously present: very difficult terrain and other specific conditions; also proven technical and economic feasibility, compatibility with the development plans of the settlement and a positive decision on the environmental impact assessment. When the roads of the republican road network are designed and built through the territory of settlements, they are dimensioned as elements of the primary street network in compliance with the requirements for protecting the settlement environment from harmful impacts. The street network in settlements and settlement formations, according to its functional purpose, is divided into a primary street network: Class I - express city highways; Class II - city highways; Class III - regional arteries; Class IV - main streets. Another classification is of a secondary street network: Class V - collector streets; Class VI - service streets.

The primary street network is determined by a general development plan, and in the absence of such - by a detailed development plan. The class of the primary and secondary street network is determined by the detailed development plan.

Railway stations, ports and airports are built in accordance with the provisions of the development plans and are necessarily connected to the primary street network, to the lines of mass public passenger transport, respectively to the railway and road network.

Development plans should provide public parking lots, conditions for pedestrian traffic by building sidewalks, pedestrian alleys, passages, streets and zones, as well as bicycle traffic - through bicycle lanes, conducted independently or in the cross-section of the street. The width of the service streets in settlements is determined by the detailed development plan and depending on the need to build infrastructure, guaranteeing the normal functioning of the territory. For small settlements and villa areas, the width of the service streets between the regulation lines, provided without sidewalks, is at least 6 m in settlements and resorts and 5 m - in villa areas. In these cases, the minimum width of the roadway is 4.50 m, respectively - 4 m. Streets without sidewalks are not allowed in settlements with a population of over 30,000 inhabitants. The width of pedestrian alleys in settlements, resort and villa areas is at least 2.25 m. The width of sidewalks in settlements, resort and villa areas is:

- 1) at least 1.50 m - sidewalks for pedestrians;
- 2) at least 0.75 m - for service sidewalks.

Dead-end streets to provide access to a limited number of regulated land properties must have a width of at least 3.5 m, and in cities, when the dead-end street serves more than 4 regulated land properties - at least 6 m. Dead-end streets longer than 100 m end at the end with a widening, ensuring the turning of cars in the opposite direction. The specified order may have an exception and not apply to streets in settlements or parts thereof with historical, archaeological, ethnographic or architectural significance, as well as to streets in settlements or parts thereof with very difficult terrain and other specific conditions or intended for development with social housing. Regulated land properties with an exit to a dead end may have a face to it with a size not smaller than its width. When dividing a regulated land property at the request of the owner of the property, the exit to the street for the newly formed properties thereof shall be provided with the project for amending the detailed development plan of the property, and in these cases the face to the street of the newly formed properties in depth shall be not less than 3.5 m. When, when dividing a regulated land property at the request of the owner of the property, the exit to the street for the newly formed properties thereof cannot be provided under the conditions of para. 4, the draft amendment to the detailed development plan provides for the construction of a dead-end street

within the boundaries of the divided and newly formed properties. In these cases, the municipality acquires ownership of the dead-end street upon the entry into force of the plan. In settlements, in accordance with the communication and transport requirements, tunnels and transport facilities at different levels shall be designed and constructed in accordance with the detailed development plan. Rail transport lines, tunnels and other facilities under the streets, squares and neighborhood spaces in settlements shall be designed in a manner that ensures the greatest possible preservation of existing buildings and facilities, as well as existing underground networks and facilities. When, when laying lines and tunnels, it is necessary to affect already constructed underground networks and facilities, they shall be reconstructed in accordance with approved projects for their relocation by the contracting authority at its expense.

Water supply and sewerage networks and facilities. Water supply and sewerage networks and facilities are constructed according to approved designs in accordance with the general and detailed development plans and the relevant specialized schemes to them and with the vertical planning plans. Water supply and sewerage networks in settlements are designed as street networks and in compliance with the provisions of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA). As an exception, in settlements and settlement formations without vertical planning plans, water mains and partial sewerage systems may be constructed in accordance with the existing terrain relief of the streets and squares and in compliance with the requirements for future vertical planning. Water supply and sewerage pipes (networks) and facilities outside settlements and settlement formations are constructed on the basis of parcel plans.

The parcel plan defines easement strips on which construction and planting of permanent plantings are not permitted. The conditions and procedure for determining the dimensions and location of the easement strips and the special regime for exercising easements shall be determined by an ordinance of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. Persons who construct and operate common water supply and sewerage pipelines (networks) and facilities - public state and public municipal property, have the right to lay and construct pipelines and facilities for water supply or wastewater disposal and ground facilities to them. Their representatives may enter and pass through the affected properties and carry out activities therein related to the construction and/or operation of the linear objects under para. 4 and the facilities to them, including the right to pass equipment through the affected land properties. They also have the right to carry out activities to eliminate accidents. Within the boundaries of the easement strips in the affected land properties, no construction or planting of permanent crops is allowed. As well as laying of pipes of other networks of the technical infrastructure, except for cases when this is allowed by a regulatory act in compliance with the technical and other requirements. The owner of the affected property does not have the right to move the linear objects and facilities built on his property. The change of ownership does not terminate the restrictions on the use of the affected land properties.

These are the rights of the persons who build and operate water supply and sewage pipes (networks) and facilities arise with an effective parcel plan. The location and dimensions of the easement strips of the water supply and sewage pipes (networks) and facilities in the affected properties are determined and a one-time compensation is paid or deposited at the disposal of the owner and the holders of other real rights to the affected property. The determination of the amount and payment of the one-time compensations shall be carried out in accordance with the procedure laid down in Articles 210 and 211 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA). Appealing the amount of compensation by interested parties shall not

prevent the exercise of rights. The amount of compensation under paragraph 1, item 2 shall be determined by applying the following criteria – such as the area of the affected land property included within the boundaries of the easement strips, the types of restrictions on use and the term of the restriction, as well as the fair market valuation of the property or the part thereof falling within the boundaries of the easement strips..

Regardless of the compensation, the persons who construct and operate water supply and sewage pipelines (networks) and facilities are obliged to restore all damage caused to the property and to pay the owner monetary compensation for the restrictions on its use outside the easement strips for the time of the actual construction. The easement strips determined by the detailed development plan are recorded in the cadastre in accordance with Art. 31a of the Cadastre and Property Register Act. The provisions of Art. 83 and 83a of the Territorial Development Act (TDA) also apply to the reconstruction or major repair of existing water supply and sewage pipelines (networks) and facilities, when the route, scope and boundaries of the easement strips marked on a cadastral map, specialized map, cadastral plan or map of the restored property are changed. With the ordinance under Art. 83, para. 5 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA) determines the conditions and procedure under which additional (replacement) water supply and wastewater disposal pipelines may be located in the easement strips of existing water supply and sewage pipelines (networks) and facilities.

The owner of the common water supply and sewage networks and facilities is obliged to include in them the water supply and sewage installations of all real estates within the territorial scope of the networks and facilities, in compliance with the requirements of Art. 125a of the Water Act. The connection of real estates and water users to the water supply and sewage networks is carried out in compliance with the provisions of this Act and with the conclusion of a written connection agreement between the user and the operating company. The conditions, technical requirements and the procedure for connecting real estate and consumers to water supply and sewage networks and facilities, for concluding connection contracts are determined by an ordinance of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works.. The owners of built-up real estate are obliged to join the constructed water supply and sewage networks and facilities. The waters on the territory of one municipality may be used to meet the drinking and domestic needs of other municipalities, when the necessary quantities of drinking and domestic water are provided for the needs of the municipality and the environmental protection objectives set out in the Water Act are not violated. In order to protect the waters intended for drinking and domestic water supply, and the mineral waters used for medical, prophylactic, drinking and hygienic needs, from pollution and other harmful influences, the development plans shall provide for sanitary protection zones around the water sources and facilities, determined in accordance with the procedure of the Water Act. The regime of the development of the sanitary protection zones and the prohibited activities in them shall be regulated by an ordinance of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works and the Minister of Environment and Water. No permit for use shall be issued for constructed water supply facilities unless their sanitary protection zones have been adopted and mapped out on site. In settlements and settlement formations or in parts thereof without sewage, domestic wastewater in properties provided for by a detailed development plan for low-rise development shall be discharged into watertight cesspools or discharged and treated in facilities for the treatment of wastewater generated in the properties.

Watertight cesspools and facilities for the treatment of wastewater generated in the properties should meet the requirements of Art. 41 and Art. 47, para. 2 and the sanitary-hygienic and environmental requirements, as well as the technical requirements set out in the regulation of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works for the design, construction and operation of building water supply and sewage installations. In the absence of sewage or in the case of a slope of the terrain, the sewage is not able to drain the surface waters. In that case, the owners are obliged to ensure the free flow of these waters through the land properties to the relevant street facilities (sewer shafts, ditches and others). In the absence of another technical possibility, proven by a vertical planning project, the sewage of buildings in regulated land properties is allowed to be included in the street sewage, passing through neighboring properties, without hindering the possibility of carrying out permissible construction in them. In these cases, the section passing through the properties from the building to the street sewer is considered a yard network (building diversion). For the damages resulting from the construction and use of the networks, the entitled parties are compensated by the contracting authority in accordance with the procedure of Art. 210 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA), as well as in landslide areas entered in the register under Art. 95, para. 2 of the SPA, where development without a constructed sewerage system is not allowed. The construction or reconstruction of water supply and/or sewerage networks and facilities in land properties falling into landslide areas entered in the register under Art. 95, para. 2, is carried out in accordance with the procedure of Art. 96, para. 3 of the Spatial Planning Act. Pumping stations for drinking and wastewater, as well as hydrophore systems for residential and public buildings, can be located in buildings, subject to compliance with the permissible noise and vibration standards.

Energy supply networks and facilities. Energy supply networks and facilities are external (street and yard) and internal (building). The construction of external ones is carried out in accordance with Art. 74 of the Spatial Planning Act (SPA) and according to approved construction documents. General heat supply and gas supply networks and facilities and their branches are constructed outside the buildings in accordance with the general procedure determined by the Act. In built-up districts, as an exception, branches from general heat supply networks are allowed to pass through winter rooms of buildings when there is no other technical possibility. Compensation for this is determined in accordance with Art. 210 of the SPA. Internal heating installations are connected to external heat pipes through subscriber stations, the equipment of which is part of the general networks and facilities and is installed, maintained and repaired in accordance with Art. 64. The subscriber station in a building, depending on its capacity and location, may also serve other buildings, with the connection being carried out in accordance with the Energy Act. Subscriber stations are located inside or outside buildings in suitable premises with effective noise and vibration insulation according to current standards.

Transformer substations are built in open spaces or in buildings that are not intended for living. In cities, they can also be created in the undeveloped part of a regulated land property - owned by individuals and legal entities, but with their consent and in compliance with the requirements for complementary development. In built-up districts, in the absence of other technical possibilities, transformer substations can also be built in residential buildings with the consent of the owners with notarization of their signatures, with effective noise and vibration insulation and protection against electric and magnetic fields according to the established standards. The transformer substation, depending on its capacity and location, can serve more than one building. The external artificial lighting of streets, squares, parks,

gardens and other real estate - public municipal property, is mandatorily provided by the municipality in order to create conditions for safe night traffic, as well as an appropriate night-time appearance of the settlements. The external artificial lighting of individual real estates, other than these, is carried out by and at the expense of the owners and is permitted by the chief architect of the municipality. It is prohibited to place transformer devices for external artificial lighting on residential buildings.

Deployment of electronic communication networks. In regulated territories, the underground physical infrastructure intended for the deployment of electronic communication networks is built simultaneously with the other networks and facilities (water pipes, sewers, electrical, heat supply, gas supply networks and others), before the laying of curbs, sidewalks and street surfaces. In unregulated territories, the physical infrastructure intended for the deployment of electronic communication networks is built on the basis of a plan under Art. 110, para. 1, item 5. of the ZUT. In the presence of a detailed development plan for a territory in which a street network has not been laid, the physical infrastructure intended for the deployment of an electronic communication network is built in accordance with the provisions for street regulation and the provisions of Art. 210 of the ZTA at the expense of the network owner. Building designs provide for physical infrastructure intended for the deployment of electronic communications networks, which is constructed simultaneously with the building and other internal installations.

Monitoring and counteraction to landslides and other processes. Activities for registering and monitoring landslide areas on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, including abrasion and erosion processes on the Black Sea and Danube coasts, as preventive measures to prevent accidents and damage are carried out by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works through the State Society for Geoprotection and its branches. The Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works maintains a register of landslide areas in the country and areas with abrasion and erosion processes on the Black Sea and Danube coasts through the State Society for Geoprotection and its branches. Monitoring is carried out through observation, analysis and assessment of the results of detailed engineering-geological, hydrogeological and hydrological surveys, engineering-geodetic measurements and observations of established stationary reference networks and control and measurement systems. The data from the monitoring, including on territories with implemented geoprotective measures and activities for stabilizing landslides, are provided to the State Geoprotective Society and its branches for recording in a register. The terms and conditions for entering and maintaining a register, as well as for carrying out activities, are determined by an ordinance of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. Coordination between individual departments for limiting landslides on the territory of the Republic of Bulgaria, including abrasion and erosion processes on the Black Sea and Danube coasts, and for preventing accidents and damage is carried out by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works. Geoprotective measures and activities to limit landslides, erosion and abrasion processes, and to prevent accidents and damage are carried out by the Ministry of Regional Development and Public Works, the central and territorial bodies of the executive power and by the owners and users of properties under the conditions and in accordance with the procedure determined by an ordinance of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. The requirements for geoprotective measures and activities, the technical requirements for the design, implementation, operation and maintenance of geoprotective structures, buildings and facilities in landslide areas are determined by an ordinance. In landslide areas

entered in the register under Art. 95, para. 2 of the Land Use and Development Act, geoprotective measures and activities are permitted in accordance with the procedure of this Act after issuing a prior consent by the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works. The preliminary consent is issued upon application of the assignor and on the basis of a document of ownership or other act certifying the assignor's right to the property, a sketch of the cadastral map and cadastral registers, a current statement on the geodynamic condition of the landslide area by the State Geoprotection Society or its branches. It is necessary to indicate the territorial scope for conducting an engineering-geological and hydrogeological survey, determined by the State Geoprotection Society or its branches and the relevant municipality, on whose territory the investment intention is located. There must be available a sample of a current detailed development plan (when it is not changed) or a design visa issued in accordance with the procedure of Art. 140, para. 2, 3 and 4 of the ZTA, if applicable, or a draft detailed development plan for all properties falling within the territorial scope determined under item 4. It is important to have an administrative act approving a detailed development plan in the defined territorial scope together with evidence of its entry into force or a protocol for the acceptance of the draft detailed development plan by the relevant expert council. It is also necessary to carry out an engineering geological and hydrogeological survey with a study of general and local stability in a natural state, during construction and in operational state under basic and special (earthquake) combination of loads for the territory in accordance with a detailed development plan in the defined territorial scope with volume and content according to a regulation (according to Eurocode 7 and/or Eurocode 8). Protocol for acceptance of the engineering-geological and hydrogeological survey by a specialized team of the relevant expert council to the authority competent to approve the detailed development plan, including competent specialists - geologists and hydrogeologists, civil engineers and representatives of the State Geoprotection Society or its branches and other necessary documents depending on the specifics of the construction.

The construction of buildings and facilities in landslide areas, entered in the register under Art. 95, para. 2 of the ZTA, is permitted after issuing a preliminary consent by the Minister of Regional Development. This development becomes a fact after the implementation of geoprotective measures and activities, for which engineering-geological and hydrogeological surveys. It is a proven need to carry out geoprotective measures and activities, upon application by the assignor and based on:

- a document of ownership or other act certifying the assignor's right to the property;
- a permit for the use of the geoprotective structures put into operation, ensuring the stability of the territory in the specified territorial scope and guaranteeing the normal functioning of the development envisaged by the detailed development plan in the specified scope;
- a sketch of the cadastral map and cadastral registers;
- technical passport of the constructed geoprotective structures with requirements for monitoring of the landslide area and geotechnical expertise/engineering-geological and hydrogeological surveys with calculations for general and local stability, which proves that the constructed facilities guarantee stability in a natural state, during construction and in an operational state under the relevant load combinations on the territory of the defined territorial scope;
- reporting of a positive effect of the constructed geoprotective structures through monitoring under Art. 95, para. 3 of the ZUT;
- other documents related to the specifics of the construction.

In cases where it is not necessary to carry out geoprotective measures and activities, proven by engineering-geological and hydrogeological surveys, the construction is carried out upon application of the contracting authority and on the basis of the prepared documents. In areas for which a construction ban has been imposed by an order under Art. 198, para. 3 of the ZTA, preliminary consent under para. 4 is issued after all conditions of the order are fulfilled in the territorial scope. Preliminary consents are issued within one month and are entered in the construction permit.

Waste treatment facilities and installations. The location of the sites for the construction of waste treatment facilities and installations is determined by the general and detailed development plans. The distances from the sites for the location of waste treatment facilities and installations to the settlements are determined depending on the adopted technology and taking into account the established sanitary protection zones. The sites are selected, constructed and operated on the basis of projects approved in accordance with the general procedure and in accordance with requirements determined by regulations of the Minister of Regional Development and Public Works, the Minister of Environment and Water and the Minister of Health. The sites and the construction of the facilities and installations for the treatment of household and construction waste are provided by the municipality. Two or more municipalities may build common facilities and installations for the treatment of household and construction waste. The provision of the sites, the construction of the facilities and installations and the treatment of production waste, including hazardous waste, are carried out under the terms and conditions of the Waste Management Act.

Gas supply. Gas supply to urbanized areas is carried out by building a gas distribution network according to projects approved in accordance with the general procedure in accordance with the provisions of the general and detailed development plans and the specialized plan-schemes to them. In the absence of general and detailed development plans for small settlements and settlement formations, gasification projects are developed on the basis of a specialized plan-scheme, approved in accordance with the procedure of Art. 128 of the ZUT. Street gas distribution networks, their elements and adjacent facilities are built by and at the expense of the legal entity that has received a permit to build such an energy facility, in accordance with the procedure of the Energy Act. Gas distribution networks and their elements are operated, maintained and repaired by and at the expense of gas distribution enterprises (companies) in settlements. Gas pipeline installations in buildings are built, maintained and repaired at the expense of the building owners.

CONCLUSION

The design and construction of the technical infrastructure sites for the development of populated areas in Bulgaria are carried out in accordance with the general procedure set out in the provisions of the Territorial Planning Act (TPA). When, in connection with new construction, it is necessary to change the position or structure of existing constructions - underground and aboveground networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure, the relevant works are carried out by the client of the new construction at his expense after approving the necessary projects, coordinated with the operating companies whose networks and facilities are affected, and after issuing a building permit. Real estate is compulsorily connected to the constructed networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure on the basis of issued construction documents. Requirements that are not specified by the operating companies when concluding the connection contract are not grounds for refusing the connection. Underground and

aboveground common networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure are designed and constructed on municipal and state land properties. When this is impossible, the networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure are built on land properties owned by individuals and legal entities, in accordance with Art. 199 or 205 of the Spatial Planning Act. In the land properties that are located on or near underground communication or other networks and facilities of the technical infrastructure, such development is envisaged that does not adversely affect the structures of the technical infrastructure, as well as does not encroach on the easement strips for the operation and repair of this infrastructure. In order to develop qualitatively for settlements, an important step is to identify all the demographic, economic, social, patrimonial, legal and technical elements that characterize the Bulgarian settlement. The analysis of Bulgarian settlements was carried out on the basis of established research tools, such as a questionnaire applied in the community, and will be carried out at the level of administrative-territorial unit, for each situation of informality. However, the current normative approach is not sufficient in terms of regional economic development of settlements and their production in the medium term due to the importance of investors and the model of functioning of cities and villages.

In the event that it is impossible to achieve expedient development or when the easement strips occupy more than 1/3 of the area of a regulated land property, the detailed development plan shall provide the property for the relevant network, with the alienation being carried out at the expense of the relevant owner of the network or facility in compliance with the requirements of Art. 206 of the Spatial Planning Act. The investment projects of buildings and facilities of the technical infrastructure also provide for the necessary measures for the improvement of the regulated land property in which they are located, in view of the functional purpose and proper operation of the buildings and facilities. Investment projects shall not be coordinated and approved in which the necessary measures for the improvement and landscaping of regulated land properties for buildings and facilities of the technical infrastructure are not provided for; measures for improvement (restoration of the adjacent terrain for technical infrastructure networks) in regulated territories, including landscaping that is disturbed by the planned construction; projects for the restoration of the adjacent terrain for technical infrastructure networks in unregulated territories; projects for roadside landscaping in projects for transport infrastructure and republican roads, including outside the borders of the regulated territory. Since the actions to be taken by the authorities at the local level cannot have consistent and sustainable results without the support of the community, the first step could be to inform the community about the activities that will be carried out at the local level in terms of the management of the settlements and the search for their development model, usually the decisions are made by the local communities. It is important that the community members are informed why these activities are necessary, both in terms of compliance with the legal provisions in force and in terms of the benefits they will have. When building and restructuring industrial and resort zones, industrial parks and settlement formations, public development activities, including landscaping, are mandatory carried out by the owners at their expense within the regulated land property. The pipes and facilities of the technical infrastructure may be built at the expense of the owners under conditions and in accordance with the procedure determined by an ordinance of the municipal council of each municipality in accordance with the requirements of the law on territorial development.

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PERSONS EMPLOYED IN NON-AGRICULTURAL ACTIVITIES IN RURAL AREAS OF THE SOUTH-CENTRAL REGION IN BULGARIA FOR THE PERIOD 2010-2020 (IN THE CONTEXT OF THE LOCALIZATION INDEX - LI)

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ABSTRACT

The scientific work attempts to present part of the employed in non-agricultural activities in the Rural areas (RA) of the South-Central Region (SCR) in Bulgaria for a certain period of time. The aim of the work is to track the employment of the population in part of the non-agricultural activities by sectors for the period of ten years, to research and analyze the employment of the population in rural municipalities by regions.

The methodology of the work is based on the definition of rural areas (RA), application of the NUTS classification for grouping the above-mentioned territories by districts and regions. The Location Index (LI) is applied to study the employed in part of the non-agricultural activities according to the Classification of Economic Activities (CEA - 2008) in the RA of the SCR. An empirical, statistical and comparative approach is applied in research, analysis, drawing conclusions and a conclusion. The visualization of the process is presented in tables and figures, which indicate the dynamics of the numerical values of LI for the period 2010 - 2020.

KEYWORDS: rural areas, location index, employed persons and NUTS.

ABSTRAKT

Die wissenschaftliche Arbeit versucht, einen Teil der Beschäftigten in nicht-landwirtschaftlichen Tätigkeiten in den ländlichen Gebieten (RA) der Süd-Zentral-Region (SCR) in Bulgarien für einen bestimmten Zeitraum darzustellen. Ziel der Arbeit ist es, die Beschäftigung der Bevölkerung in einem Teil der nicht-landwirtschaftlichen Tätigkeiten nach Sektoren für den Zeitraum von zehn Jahren zu verfolgen, die Beschäftigung der Bevölkerung in ländlichen Gemeinden nach Regionen zu untersuchen und zu analysieren.

Die Methodik der Arbeit basiert auf der Definition der ländlichen Gebiete (RA), der Anwendung der NUTS-Klassifikation zur Gruppierung der oben genannten Gebiete nach Bezirken und Regionen. Der Standortindex (LI) wird angewandt, um die Beschäftigung in einem Teil der nichtlandwirtschaftlichen Tätigkeiten gemäß der Klassifikation der Wirtschaftszweige (CEA - 2008) in den RA der SCR zu untersuchen. Ein empirischer, statistischer und vergleichender Ansatz wird in der Forschung, der Analyse, den Schlussfolgerungen und der Schlussfolgerung angewendet. Die Visualisierung des Prozesses wird in Tabellen und Abbildungen dargestellt, die die Dynamik der numerischen Werte des LI für den Zeitraum 2010 - 2020 aufzeigen.

STICHWORTE: ländliche Gebiete, Standortindex, Erwerbstätige und NUTS

RÉSUMÉ

La production de biens destinés au marché peut comporter des aspects de biens publics, par exemple lorsque la production de certains produits agricoles ou les paysages créés par les exploitations

agricoles font partie de l'identité locale. La culture locale souvent associée à l'agriculture est un type de bien public.

L'objectif de l'étude est d'évaluer la contribution de l'agriculture à la formation de biens publics et les facteurs permettant d'optimiser ce processus.

Le résultat de la recherche est que le secteur agricole de la région de Smolyan est activement impliqué dans la fourniture de biens publics, qui sont très appréciés par les agriculteurs locaux. Une partie importante du processus de fourniture de biens publics est leur combinaison appropriée avec les biens du marché, qui contribuera à l'obtention d'un avantage concurrentiel pour la région. Les agriculteurs attendent le soutien des institutions publiques pour explorer ces avantages concurrentiels. Ainsi, en soutenant le développement des entreprises qui ont un caractère d'intérêt privé, on maintiendra également les biens publics dans la région.

MOTS CLÉS: biens publics, qualité de l'eau, sécurité alimentaire, paysage

INTRODUCTION

The diversity of forms of spatial organization of society and their components determines the need for various basic regional studies related to social sciences studying – territory, population and specific socio-economic activities, formed and developing for a certain period of time. The characteristic of regional development, as a scientific discipline, is determined by the integrality of the approach to the studied objects and subjects, their relationship in time and space (Bertalanffy, 1962). In this regard, the study, analysis and subsequent drawing of conclusions and conclusions is based on a part of the employed in non-agricultural activities related to the RA of the South-Central Region for a certain period of time. The territorial-structural approach is related to the sectoral-concentric differentiation of regional territorial systems with prominent functions between the center and the periphery. In order to establish the nature and regularities of formation and development of regional territorial systems, it is necessary to determine the composition of the elements and connections uniting these elements into a system. The main elements of the regional territorial system are the objects of material production (all its forms) and the geodemographic resource (Petrov & Tsonkov, 2022).

The definition of the concepts of "rural areas", "rural territories" and "rural municipality" is of key importance for revealing regional differences in the above-mentioned concepts. In most economic studies, the understanding of rural areas in its geographical sense prevails, it is associated rather with a certain territory in which there is diverse and dispersed economic activity with a clear predominance of primary economic activities (agriculture, mining activities, forestry and others), with low population density and relative independence from the influence of urban centers. Criteria for the classification of rural areas should take into account the significant connections between these areas and urban centers.

The development of regional policy in the Community focuses on a set of spatial priorities, including: economically and socially underdeveloped regions, restructuring of urban and industrial areas, development of rural areas, development of human resources and improving the living standards of the population in the specified areas, for this purpose - the EU Regulatory Commission with Decision № 1059/2003, grants NUTS status. Based on the above classification and the Regional Development Act of 2008, the following territorial units are distinguished on the territory of Bulgaria: NUTS 0 - Republic of Bulgaria, NUTS 1 - two statistical zones, NUTS 2 - six statistical regions, NUTS 3 - 28 districts and LAU 1 264

municipalities, 231 of which are defined as rural areas for the entire country. Of the 231 rural municipalities with a total area of 89,910 km² or 81% of the country's territory by 2021, 215 of them remain or 16 are eliminated, as set out in the Strategic Plan for the Development of Agriculture and Rural Areas (PDARA 2023 - 2027), they are not in the category of rural municipalities, with an area of 14,705 km² or 13,24%.

Table 1. District, territory, number of municipalities and population in the country, for 2020

District	Territory		Settlements		Place	Population	
	km ²	%	numeral	%	numeral	numeral	%
Bulgaria	110 993,6		5 047		231	6 916 548	
SCR	22 369	20,15	1 012	20,05	57	1 405 311	20,31
RA in SCR	18 219,1	70,18	905	89,42	48	548 527	39,03
RA in Kardzhali	2 635,8	11,78	351	34,68	6	89 461	6,36
RA in Pazardzhik	3 822,7	17,08	75	7,41	10	112 675	8,01
RA in Plovdiv	5 204,6	23,26	154	15,21	16	216 756	15,42
RA in Solyan	4 228,8	18,91	152	15,01	9	66 599	4,73
RA in Haskovo	2 237,2	10,01	173	17,09	7	63 036	4,48

Source: NSI and author's calculations

The territory occupied by rural areas according to the new definition from 2022 is 75,205 km² or 67.75% of the country. As of 31.12.2022, according to the National Register of Settlements (NRS) and the National Statistical Institute (NSI), there are 5,257 settlements in 28 districts on the territory of the country, of which 257 are cities, 4,998 are villages, 265 are municipalities, of which 215 are rural areas, and two monastery complexes with the status of a settlement: Klisura and Rila. The average density of settlements in Bulgaria, as of the same year, is 4,7 settlements per 100 km².

Table 1 visualizes the rural areas of the South-Central Region, as well as the same ones in the country. As can be seen in percentage terms, rural areas occupy a large percentage of the territory of the region, as well as of the country. The population inhabiting these areas develops various socio-economic activities related to livelihoods. In recent decades, the number of people has decreased in the South-Central Region, as well as in the country, due to the lack of a number of socio-economic activities, a high rate of migration (NSI, 2024), a change in the mentality of society and, last but not least, the lack of any protectionist policy on the part of the state. The population living in rural areas is looking for ways to make a living, striving to develop activities outside the generally accepted ones related to agrarian entrepreneurship. Diversification in rural areas (Madzharova and eat., 2013), in particular the above-mentioned municipalities of the South-Central Region, is directly related to the natural features and landscape features. The need for activities (beyond those traditionally accepted for RA) related to and directed at the socio-economic status of society are necessary to increase the living status, on the one hand, and on the other, to preserve traditions and, last but not least, ethno-cultural affiliation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When processing the material, the author is based on the definition of rural areas adopted in Bulgaria: "...rural areas - municipalities of (LAU 1), in which there is no settlement with a population of over 30,000 people..." (DRA, 2007-2013), refers to the Law on Regional Development of 31.08.2008,

Chapter Two - Territorial Basis of Regional Development, Art. 4. (2), (4) and (5), (Supplemented - State Gazette, issue 21 of 2020, in force from 13.03.2020).

In the development, the Localization Index (LI) is applied, an indicator that analyzes socio-economic activities at the regional level (Izard, 1956). The aim of the scientific work is to study the employed in part of the non-agricultural activities in the SR of the South-Central Region in the field of Services: Transport, storage and post (H) Hotel industry (I 55), Restaurant industry (I 56) and Education (P) in the RA of the South-Central Region for a period of ten years 2010-2020. In the specific case, if LI is greater than 1 (unit), the employed in the relevant sectors or regions have a high concentration. With a coefficient less than 1, localization processes are absent, respectively, specialization for the territory.

$$IL = (S_j / N_j) / (S / N) = (S_j / S) / (N_j / N)$$

Where:

IL – location index;

S_j – number of employed persons/enterprises in industry j in the region;

S – number of employed persons/enterprises in the manufacturing industry in the region;

N_j – number of employed persons/enterprises in industry j in the country;

N – number of employed persons/enterprises in the manufacturing industry in the country.

The Classification of Economic Activities of 2008 is used; it is a regulation of EC № 1893/2006 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20.12.2006. In the publication for greater credibility, the author refers to Section II, Art. (9 to 21) and Annex I and II of the above-mentioned classification.

The study used the NUTS classification in the specific case for the smallest administrative territorial units LAU 1. Regulation (EC) № 1059/2003 of the European Parliament, Regulation (EC) № 176/2008 of the European Parliament. Statistical information from the National Statistical Institute (NSI) number of employed persons by districts in the RA of the South-Central Region for 2010-2020 and calculations of the author. Microsoft Word and Excel were used in data processing.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The application of modern approaches to the integration of rural areas is a potential guarantee for overcoming the differences in this type of space. To support rural areas, for their implementation in social and economic growth, for increasing employment (in non-agricultural activities) and the standard of living, the policy of (CAP, 2023-2027) for the same, sets three main directions for implementation:

- 1) Improving the competitiveness of agriculture.
- 2) Achieving sustainable management of natural resources and climate action.
- 3) Balanced territorial development of rural areas. In parallel with the various types of recommendations, programs and all kinds of activities aimed at rural areas at the EU level or locally, the model/form of diversification is required - different types of activities from the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors.

The creation or opening of non-agricultural activities in the RA will lead to a sustainable socio-economic environment, the creation of additional GVA and the retention of a population of childbearing age, which is the key element for preserving the territorial integrity of rural areas (Mutafov, 2021).

In the scientific paper, the author makes an attempt to analyze and present some of the non-agricultural activities, such as diversification of the sectors in the RA: Transport, Storage and Post (H), Hotel Industry (I 55), Restaurant Industry (I 56) and Education (P) in the RA of the South-Central Region within a ten-year period and their place and influence in society. A comparative analysis of the activities in the RA of the South-Central Region is applied, compared to the same at the national and regional levels.

Figure. 1 Persons employed in the Transport, warehousing and postal services (H) sector in SR by region, compared to Bulgaria and South-Central Europe for the period 2010 – 2020

Source: NSI and author's calculations

For the RA of the South-Central Region, employment in the sector for the first year compared to the country and the region LI is below one, and in the following years it is above one, or the sector has specialization in this area. The strengthening of the interest of society in RA, due to a number of socio-economic reasons, over the past ten years has an impact on this type of activity. In the RA of Kardzhali district, LI throughout the entire study period reports an index below one or there is no specialization in this sector. A large number of settlements in this region have under 20 inhabitants (depopulation of territories), which reflects on the cessation of socio-economic activities serving society. The population of childbearing age migrates to urbanized areas, which further worsens the geodemographic and settlement structure. For the RA of Pazardzhik district, during the study period LI is above one or there is specialization. The rural areas of Plovdiv district in the first year LI is below one for the sector. During the following stages of the study, LI is above one, the territories report concentration, and here the main reason can be indicated by the increased interest in RA as a place to live and develop business. In the RA of Smolyan district, LI throughout the entire study period reports an index below one or there is no specialization in this sector. A large number of settlements in this region have a population of less than 10 people, the distance from urban areas and the altitude have a direct impact on the activities of the sector, which leads to their closure (low profitability) and, consequently, depopulation of RA. For the RA of Haskovo district, LI is above one for the entire study period, the main reason can be indicated by the fact that the region is border, which contributes to the specialization and development of activities and the retention of the economically active population.

In recent decades, with the "opening" of the RA to activities outside the generally accepted ones related to agriculture, the Services sector has been one of the leading ones that provides high employment for the population in the RA. The natural features of the RA of the region are the basis for the development of the entire range of tourist activities. Approximately more than 60% of the economically active population work in the Services sector. The scientific work visualizes the hotel and restaurant sectors (employed persons), which are structurally determining for the socio-economic development of society for some areas in the South-Central Region.

Figure 2. Employed persons in the Hotel sector (I 55) in RA by region, compared to Bulgaria and SCR for the period 2010 – 2020

Source: NSI and author's calculations

The location of the South-Central Region and in particular the rural areas, provides a great opportunity for the development of hotel activities based on natural resources (all varieties) and, accordingly, the creation of jobs to serve this sector, ensuring the socio-economic involvement of the population.

Fig. 2 visualizes the employed persons for this type of activity, LI shows the specialization of the rural areas, compared at the national and regional levels. For the rural areas of the district, throughout the entire period of the study, LI is above one at all levels or there is specialization and the necessary workforce. The rural areas of Kardzhali district for the country, LI is above one, that is, there is specialization. In the analysis for the region, LI is below one or there is a minimal shortage of labor in the industry. For the rural areas of Pazardzhik district, LI compared to the country and the region reports a high index, due to the natural specificity of the territory. The rural areas of Plovdiv district, LI itself is high during the period of the study, related to the natural, geographical, historical and ethno-cultural resources. The proximity of the most ancient inhabited city in Europe - Plovdiv, also influences the high index for this sector. For the RA of Smolyan district, LI is the highest compared to other regions at all levels. The location, as well as the presence of a large variety of natural features and ethno-cultural landmarks, create prerequisites for the development of this type of sector and the employment of a large number of workers. The rural areas of Haskovo district during the study period compared to other RAs, LI has the

lowest values for the country and at the regional level. The main reason is the transit feature of the territory.

The high LI of employed persons in the RA largely depends on the concentration of enterprises in the Services sector, serving the RC of the South-Central Region. For the RA of the South-Central Region, LI during the entire period of study compared to the country and the region has a high specialization above one. For the RA of Kardzhali district, LI is above one during the ten years of reporting (Borisov and eat, 2020). For the RA of Pazardzhik district, LI compared to the country reports specialization above one, compared to the region it is below 1. In the study, the municipality of Velingrad does not fall into the definition of RA, where a large part of the activities in the field of Services is concentrated. For the RA of Plovdiv district, LI is identical to that of the previous district. Urbanized spaces are competition for the RA for this sector. Family hotels develop in parallel a restaurant activity, which overlaps the employed persons in both industries.

Figure 3. Employed persons in the Restaurant sector (I 56) in RA by region, compared to Bulgaria and South-Central Region for the period 2010 – 2020

Source: NSI and author's calculations

For the RA of Smolyan district, LI compared to the country is above one, there is specialization, but compared to the region the index is below one for the last two years. Here too, there is an overlap of activities on the part of family activities in the field of Services. In the RA of Haskovo district, LI compared to the country is above one for the entire period of the study, for the region it is below one, there is an overlap of activities - restaurant and hotel management.

The Education Sector in the RA of the South-Central Region has an extremely important social function for the population, especially in childbearing age. A large part of the employed persons in the RA fall into the List of Protected Kindergartens and Protected Schools in the Republic of Bulgaria, on the basis of Art. 54, para. 4 of the Law on Preschool and School Education in connection with Decree № 121 of the Council of Ministers of 2017 on the adoption of criteria for determining protected kindergartens and protected schools and on the terms and conditions for their additional financing.

Figure 4. Employed persons in the Education sector (P) in RA by region, compared to Bulgaria and South-Central Region for the period 2010 – 2020.

Source: NSI and author's calculations

The RA of the South-Central Region includes 79 educational institutions (a total of 164 in the country) with the relevant staff, as visualized in Fig. 4, LI is below one for the entire period of succession at both levels. For all RAs of the region, LI is below one, the small number of employed persons perform a social function, this is caused by the low birth rate and the minimum number of populations of childbearing age. This social function of the state to retain employees in the Education sector has a direct impact on other socio-economic activities in these areas. The state's protection policy is necessary to prevent the depopulation of areas that are remote from urban areas.

CONCLUSIONS

With the new socio-economic, climatic, geodemographic, etc. changes in the RA at global and local levels, diversification in these areas is a key moment for preserving the structure of these areas. The natural specificity, specifically for the RA of the South-Central Region, is a basic prerequisite for the development of the above-mentioned non-agricultural activities, which appear as socio-economic alternatives to the agricultural tradition and livelihood. The employed in sector (H) according to the CEA - 2008 in the RA of the South-Central Region, on the one hand, satisfy narrow economic needs, and on the other, carry out social activities in the field of Services in the RC, which are remote from urban areas (Millusheva, 2024). The change in LI in this sector is largely due to the distance between the "center and the periphery" of the region. The employed in sector (I 55) are also largely dependent on natural resources, in particular the RA located in the mountainous and semi-mountainous regions. This sector reports a high LI, due to the specific nature of the relief and the development of tourism. The localization index in the RA of Haskovo district in sector (I 55), reports low values due to the transit location. In the Catering sector (I 56), the LI of the employed is identical to the previous one and largely depends on the same characteristics. In both sectors (I 55) and (I 56), there is an overlap of activities by the employed from family activities. In sector (P), LI reports the lowest index, there is no specialization in RC (Markov and Toneva, 2018). A large part of the educational infrastructure falls under Decree No. 121 of the Council

of Ministers of 2017. This sector performs social activities aimed at the population of childbearing age remaining to live in the RA of the South-Central Region. Diversification in the coming decades will have an increasing impact on the socio-economic life of the population in the RA not only locally, but also globally. These will be activities that will "keep" the economically active population in areas that are remote from large urban centers.

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ANALYSIS OF MODELS FOR ASSESSING THE RESILIENCE OF MUNICIPALITIES IN CRISIS

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ABSTRACT

This study is not comprehensive, but is dedicated to a problem that is especially relevant for countries like Bulgaria, where crisis management readiness and disaster management are a complex and laborious issue. Thus, in this presentation, we will examine the problems of regional development in the context of the established framework for disaster and accident management. The next part is devoted to the attempt to analyze the models for assessing the resilience of municipalities in crises in the municipalities of Bulgaria. After which the relevant conclusions and recommendations are made for improving the work of institutions in crisis management. The relevant conclusions and recommendations are made.

KEYWORDS: crises, disasters, accidents, public sector, regions, development, management.

ABSTRAKT

Diese Studie erhebt keinen Anspruch auf Vollständigkeit, widmet sich aber einem Problem, das insbesondere für Länder wie Bulgarien relevant ist, da Krisenmanagementbereitschaft und Katastrophenmanagement dort komplex und aufwendig sind. Daher untersuchen wir in dieser Präsentation die Probleme der Regionalentwicklung im Kontext des etablierten Rahmens für Katastrophen- und Unfallmanagement. Im nächsten Teil werden die Modelle zur Bewertung der Resilienz von Gemeinden in Krisensituationen in Bulgarien analysiert. Anschließend werden relevante Schlussfolgerungen und Empfehlungen zur Verbesserung der Arbeit von Institutionen im Krisenmanagement abgeleitet.

STICHWORTE:: Krisen, Katastrophen, Unfälle, öffentlicher Sektor, Regionen, Entwicklung, Management.

RÉSUMÉ

Cette étude n'est pas exhaustive, mais elle se concentre sur une problématique particulièrement pertinente pour des pays comme la Bulgarie, où la préparation à la gestion des crises et des catastrophes est complexe et complexe. Dans cette présentation, nous examinerons les problèmes de développement régional dans le contexte du cadre établi pour la gestion des catastrophes et des accidents. La partie suivante est consacrée à l'analyse des modèles d'évaluation de la résilience des municipalités bulgares en cas de crise. Des conclusions et recommandations pertinentes sont ensuite formulées pour améliorer le travail des institutions en matière de gestion de crise.

MOTS-CLÉS: crises, catastrophes, accidents, secteur public, régions, développement, gestion

INTRODUCTION

The increase in the number and intensity of hazards in recent years puts pressure on public institutions to work in a constantly unstable environment, which is also reflected in the increase in problems at the regional level, and in the case of Bulgaria, the focus on municipalities and crisis management caused by problems of an environmental, political and social nature. Thus, the topic that we will bring up is to analyze factors that influence the readiness of communities for emergencies or extraordinary situations (disasters and accidents), which will impose a new model of work in municipalities in terms of preventive and organizational activities for prevention and quality management of processes related to the emergence and resolution of crisis situations. In order to identify the problems of this article, we will focus on the analysis of the environment and the possibilities for resolving emergency situations in Bulgaria. In this context, municipalities occupy a central place as the main unit of local self-government, which is closest to the population. The role of municipal authorities is crucial both in prevention and preparation before the occurrence of crisis events, and in response and recovery after them. The resilience of municipalities – their ability to withstand the shocks of disasters, to quickly recover and adapt – is becoming a strategic goal at the national and local levels. International framework documents such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030 emphasize the importance of local authorities and communities in reducing risk and building resilience. Our country joins this process. In this presentation, we will try to bring out several correct solutions to the ongoing deep political transformation and the increasingly acute resource problems of the regions (decreasing fossil hydrocarbon reserves and water scarcity) generating conflict at all levels – from local to regional in terms of crisis and disaster management. In general, the processes in Bulgarian municipalities regarding crisis and disaster management are moving towards a chaotic arrangement, with nominally preserved boundaries, but arbitrarily crossed by anyone who decides to implement crisis management measures or policies. Therefore, it is necessary to conduct a comprehensive process of assessing the state of the municipalities, their population and business structure and regional economic activity (Georgieva, 2023). Natural and man-made hazards threaten people, property, the environment and cultural heritage. Climate change will increase disaster risk by increasing the impact of extreme weather events, floods, droughts and wildfires unless adaptation and mitigation measures are taken. Disaster risk management aims to address these hazards and the risks they pose. Climate change adaptation and disaster risk reduction should be closely linked, with active community engagement and a shared understanding of the risks.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Crisis management is to bring the evolution of the crisis process under control. The information system necessary for cognitive management provides data on the situation, possible solutions and options for actions to be taken. Coordination of intelligence activities is carried out and preparation for interaction in resolving and deepening the crisis is coordinated. Experience shows that disasters cause serious disturbances in the mental state of the population, including among the management staff, which often leads to inadequate actions and behaviors and affects the organization and conduct of rescue operations. This requires improving the forms of increasing the moral and psychological resilience of the population to manage their behavior in critical situations. The overall activity in this regard is led on the ground by the local and state administration and all mass media. To achieve consensus national policies, it is

necessary to deduce the current state of the Bulgarian nation-state and how it looks from the outside and, above all, to outline how it would and would bear reforms that could change its development (Petrov, 2023). In this direction, it is important to deduce the connection between territorial governance and the role of municipalities in it. This is a kind of conceptual issue that is embedded in the concept of resilience of municipalities in crises, which refers to the ability of local communities and their management structures (municipal authorities) to withstand the blows of disasters, to continue to function during a crisis and to recover quickly and effectively afterwards. At the end of the twentieth and especially in the last years of the twenty-first century, interest in this issue increased. The reason is the daily catastrophes, disasters and incidents that negatively affect operating organizations. The increase in the number of crisis phenomena has necessitated the creation of specialized centers for research, expert assessments and consulting assistance around the world (Sarhachev, J., & Stoenchev, N. 2016). Assessing this resilience is a complex task that requires taking into account multiple factors – physical infrastructure, institutional capacity, social and economic resilience, environmental aspects. Various models and indicators for assessment have been developed in scientific literature and practice. Here we will briefly consider some approaches applicable or applied to municipalities (Petrov, K. 2020).. Baseline Resilience Indicators for Communities (BRIC) are also of great importance. They are systems of indicators through which resilience can be measured. For example, Baseline Resilience Indicators for Communities (BRIC) – a model developed in the USA, including indicators in several topics: housing and infrastructure, demography (vulnerable groups), economy (wealth, inequalities), institutional capacity (plans, finances), community capital (social networks, volunteerism) and environmental factors. Each of them collects specific dimensions (e.g. percentage of healthy housing, number of hospital beds per capita, availability of emergency centers, etc.), from which a composite index for the municipality is formed (Vladev, I. 2022). A similar approach can be adapted for Bulgarian conditions, with locally relevant indicators – for example, number of trained volunteers, percentage of the municipal budget allocated to prevention, availability of a backup water source, number of exercises conducted, etc. (Bogomilova, E. 2020). This approach is in line with the model of the 10 main components of urban resilience (UNDRR).It is embodied in the UN Resilient Cities campaign for risk reduction, which defines 10 essential aspects of local resilience (Ten Essentials for Making Cities Resilient). These include: (1) Organizing and coordinating disaster risk management at the local level with community participation; (2) Identifying, understanding and using up-to-date information on risks; (3) Financing for resilience; (4) Shaping the urban environment for risk (urban planning and standards); (5) Protecting natural buffers (ecosystems) to reduce risk; (6) Strengthening emergency response institutions; (7) Preparedness, early warning and awareness; (8) Protecting vital infrastructure and services; (9) Ensuring appropriate disaster response; (10) Accelerated recovery and “Build Back Better”. Based on these components, a Disaster Resilience Scorecard for Cities is applied, which many cities around the world use to self-assess their preparedness and vulnerabilities (UNDRR, 2020). For Bulgarian municipalities, especially larger cities, this tool could provide a structured assessment and indicate priority areas for improvement (Maneva, K. (2023). In this direction, for the needs of regional development, it is important to combine a relationship between business and the public sector. This will allow us to assess the readiness of Bulgarian municipalities in crises. In this direction, it is necessary to consider several aspects of the state of regional development: available planning documentation, institutional and human capacity, equipment and resources, practical activity (exercises, real operations)

and problem areas, as well as the vitality of regional development (Tsonkov, N., & Petrov, K. 2023). Next is the so-called planning and strategic security: As mentioned, by law each municipality must have a Disaster Protection Plan. As of 2023, all 265 municipalities in Bulgaria have prepared plans, approved by the municipal councils and coordinated with the regional governors. This coverage is practically complete, although the quality of plans vary. Larger municipalities (district cities) usually have more detailed and professionally developed plans, often with the participation of external experts. Smaller municipalities sometimes use template plans provided by the district administration or the Ministry of Interior, which do not always take into account specific local risks. Regarding risk reduction programs, as mentioned, only ~50% of municipalities had prepared such programs by 2019. After the adoption of the National Strategy 2018–2030 and the program 2021–2025, the tendency is for this number to increase, as there is a targeted policy to assist lagging municipalities. However, the fact that about half of the municipalities have not had a preventive program until recently indicates gaps in local planning, and accordingly demographic strategies or population and settlement assessment (Georgieva, M. 2024). Institutional capacity and training are important: Each municipality should have a separate unit or at least an official responsible for disaster protection (e.g., a Defense and Crisis Situations Inspector or a Secretary of the Municipal Headquarters). In most large municipalities, there are separate security departments, while in small ones these functions are often combined with other duties. The training of responsible persons is mainly carried out by the DG PBZN (National Fire and Population Protection) - there is a training center at the Academy of the Ministry of Interior, which organizes courses for mayors, deputy mayors, and members of staff. Data shows that staffing is insufficient in some municipalities - especially where there is no separate expert; in a crisis, all coordination falls on the mayor and the municipal secretary, who may not have sufficient experience. Also, frequent staff turnover (due to elections, change of mayors) sometimes leads to a loss of institutional memory and the need to train new people. In this direction, a good indicator of readiness are the exercises and trainings conducted. According to the plan, each municipality should conduct at least one municipal headquarters exercise per year, often jointly with the district or with a specific scenario (e.g. earthquake simulation). In practice, however, some municipalities fail to do this annually – due to lack of time, resources or underestimation of the need. The Ministry of Interior reports show that on average about 60-70 municipalities annually conduct exercises with the participation of the Unified Rescue System. This is only ~25% of all municipalities annually (Maneva, K. 2023).. Which means that many municipalities do not have a regular practice of training, which can make coordination in a real situation difficult. The formation of volunteer formations and resources is also important for municipalities: As we have mentioned so far, according to public data from the National Statistical Institute, there are about 239 volunteer formations with over 3154 volunteers. This number, although significant, is not evenly distributed – some active municipalities have dozens of volunteers (e.g. large cities, mountainous municipalities prone to forest fires), while others may have a symbolic squad or may not yet have any registered volunteers. The availability of equipment for these volunteers is also an indicator: in recent years, under European projects (Operational Programme “Environment”, etc.), some of the volunteer squads have been supplied with personal protective equipment, pumps, chainsaws, generators, etc. But not everywhere – so in many cases, volunteers rely on limited equipment, which limits their effectiveness (Ivanova, R. P. 2024). The technical provision of municipalities is also important: Municipalities own or have access to certain equipment needed in disasters: heavy machinery

(excavators, bulldozers) for clearing, drainage pumps, high-pass vehicles, backup generators, tents, etc.. Many small municipalities do not have their own equipment and rely on private companies under contract (e.g. for snow removal, which can also be hired for emergency clearance if necessary). Financially weaker municipalities may not maintain a reserve of materials (sandbags, fuel, etc.). A positive example is the creation of inter-municipal agreements - some neighboring municipalities conclude mutual assistance agreements, so that equipment or teams from one can help each other in the event of a disaster. For example, in the Burgas region, there is an agreement between several municipalities to share a diving team in case of flooding. A significant problem within municipalities is also financial readiness. It directly corresponds to the municipalities' budgets for prevention, which are limited. By law, in the event of a disaster, the municipality can spend earmarked funds from a reserve and then request compensation from the state. However, in practice, few municipalities set aside significant reserves for disasters - outside of maintenance costs (cleaning ravines, repairs). The state budget (through the Interdepartmental Commission for Reconstruction under the Council of Ministers) often covers damages ex post facto, but this is sometimes slow. The lack of insurance for public property is also a problem – according to a World Bank assessment, the coverage of municipal buildings with insurance against natural risks is low. This means that when a school or other infrastructure is destroyed, the entire burden of reconstruction falls on the budget (Tsonkov, N. 2024). Next in importance in this regard is the readiness with communication systems: Readiness includes the presence of announcement systems (sirens), which in Bulgaria are built mainly in cities, but do not cover all settlements. Many villages do not have sirens, relying on telephones or car megaphones. In 2021–2022, an upgrade of the National Early Warning System (with European funding) was launched, including the expansion of the siren network and the implementation of Cell Broadcast technology for direct messages to mobile phones (the EU-Alert/BG-Alert system). The introduction of BG-Alert will significantly improve notification, but at the time of preparation of this work it is at an initial stage. This should determine the vulnerability framework of the systems. Moreover, since capacity and vulnerability analysis (CVA) is always within the framework of the humanitarian approach, an analysis that identifies existing capacities (resources & capacities) of the community and vulnerabilities (vulnerabilities) in disasters is often applied. Capacities include things such as: availability of trained personnel, available equipment and machinery, local knowledge of risks, social cohesion (e.g. functioning mutual aid networks), financial reserves or insurance, etc. Vulnerabilities include: poverty, isolated settlements, poor infrastructure, illiteracy or low awareness, dependence on external supplies, etc. Resilience assessment in this context seeks to increase capacity and reduce vulnerabilities. For example, if a municipality determines that a vulnerability is the lack of a hospital on its territory, which would make medical assistance difficult in a disaster, this points to measures such as providing an emergency medical point or contracts with a neighboring municipality for medical services (Petrov, K. 2021). In addition, it is very important to highlight the models of critical infrastructure: Resilience is often also assessed by the ability of key infrastructure systems to withstand crises – electricity supply, water supply, transport networks, telecommunications. Therefore, there are approaches such as analyzing the reliability of the infrastructure (for example, the electricity grid should have backup power, the water system should have redundant pumps, etc.). Municipalities, when assessing their resilience, consider what % of the population could be left without electricity in a given disaster and for how long, is there a possibility of alternative power supply (generators), what are the local water and food supplies, etc. The stronger and more flexible

these systems are, the higher the resilience. (Marinov, P. 2022). Thus, these models are based on past experience (empirical resilience): Sometimes resilience is assessed post facto – how the municipality coped in a real crisis situation. For example, after a serious flood or earthquake, one can analyze: how quickly services were restored (electricity, water, transport), how quickly people returned to their homes or were accommodated, what percentage of businesses resumed work within a certain period. These empirical indicators can be used comparatively – if one municipality manages to recover in 1 month, and another similar one – in 6 months, this indicates a difference in their resilience. In Bulgaria, fortunately, there are no recent devastating earthquakes for such an analysis, but severe floods (such as those in 2014 in Varna and Dobrich, 2021 in Karlovsko, etc.) have provided material for assessing local resilience. This allows us to assess institutional preparedness: Here, the availability and quality of plans, procedures and resources are considered. For example, has the municipality updated its disaster protection plan in the last 2 years, does it conduct annual headquarters exercises, is there a 24-hour on-call and notification system? The Secretariat of the National Disaster Risk Reduction Council has conducted surveys and research among municipalities. According to one such study, as of 2019, only about half of the municipalities had developed local disaster risk reduction programs – 134 municipalities or ~50.6%. This indicates a varying degree of institutional commitment – some municipalities are very active, others are lagging behind in planning. A sustainability assessment would take this fact into account – the lack of a program and active prevention policy is an indicator of lower capacity. Crisis management must take into account not only the conditions under which they arose, but also their nature, scope, objectives and consequences. It is necessary to assess the behavior of the parties and to adapt subsequent actions to the elements of this assessment. Depending on the phases of the crisis, its management can be preventive, prospective or forceful in nature, with the main goal remaining to limit the consequences and resolve it.

CONCLUSION

In summary, resilience assessment models provide a framework to identify the weaknesses of a municipality in terms of its preparedness for crises. Crisis management is becoming more and more scientific and complex, as the volume of information and the requirements for a more universal research training of the leader and the crisis management team are increasing. This training includes invention, the use of various discoveries, new ways, approaches and methods. The ability to apply such qualities of thought and knowledge as broad-rangingness, logical consistency, systematicity, completeness, self-criticism, speed in checking decisions and effectiveness of knowledge and experience, accurate and timely interaction with other organizations, specialists, perfect adaptability to the increased requirements for endurance and work in extreme conditions is also decisive. Indicators or qualitative assessments can be used to compare municipalities, monitor progress over time, and plan improvements. For example, the National Program for Disaster Risk Reduction 2025–2030 provides methodological support for the development of municipal risk profiles and indicators for monitoring the implementation of preventive measures. In the next section, we will examine the current state of Bulgarian municipalities – how prepared they are and how their crisis prevention and response systems function. The assessment of the work of organizations working in the field of crisis and disaster management is based mainly on quantitative final results. Less often, the meaning and benefit of the educational service offered are assessed; the change in knowledge, skills, competencies, attitudes, and attitudes in the target groups that the actions of the given organization lead to, as well as its capacity to offer services in the field of crisis

management. Early updates on any event that may have a future impact are of utmost importance. A monthly or quarterly review of your employees will help you identify any conflicts. Good employee engagement platforms provide the following benefits: Reduce employee attrition. Develop a good employer and employee brand. Stand out as a good leader. Crisis management is part of regional development and is still in its infancy, but it must end with the creation of a state body that plans and technically ensures the logistical environment so that local regional executive bodies and local governments can achieve significant results in protecting society from severe shocks and local disasters.

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MONITORING AND CONTROL ALGORITHMS FOR PRODUCT POSITIONING STRATEGY: INSIGHTS FROM BULGARIA'S BANKING SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

Product positioning constitutes a fundamental strategic marketing process aimed at establishing a distinct and favorable perception of a product within the consumer's mind relative to competing alternatives. In the context of the financial services sector, characterized by rapidly evolving market dynamics and increasingly sophisticated customer expectations, the deployment of robust monitoring and control systems is imperative for banks to effectively operationalize their product positioning strategies. These systems predominantly rely on algorithmic methodologies to continuously track key performance indicators, analyze consumer behavior, and facilitate timely responses to market fluctuations.

The objective of this study is to propose an algorithmic framework for a monitoring and control system dedicated to the implementation of product positioning strategies within commercial banks. The proposed algorithm leverages marketing data collected from 23 Bulgarian banks over the period 2023–2024. The developed monitoring and control system (MCS) algorithm represents a decision-support tool for marketing managers in commercial banking, structured around the following components: (1) identification of key markers for evaluating and selecting appropriate product positioning strategies; (2) determination of reference values for these markers to facilitate systematic diagnosis of the implemented strategies' effects; and (3) a methodology for corrective action contingent on observed deviations from the intended product positioning strategy.

KEYWORDS: monitoring, banks, product positioning, strategy

ABSTRACT

Im Kontext des Finanzdienstleistungssektors, der durch eine sich schnell entwickelnde Marktdynamik und immer anspruchsvollere Kundenerwartungen gekennzeichnet ist, ist der Einsatz von robusten Überwachungs- und Kontrollsystemen für Banken unerlässlich, um ihre Produktpositionierungsstrategien effektiv umsetzen zu können. Ziel dieser Studie ist es, einen algorithmischen Rahmen für ein Überwachungs- und Kontrollsystem vorzuschlagen, das auf die Umsetzung von Produktpositionierungsstrategien in Geschäftsbanken ausgerichtet ist. Der vorgeschlagene Algorithmus stützt sich auf Marketingdaten, die von 23-bulgarischen Banken im Zeitraum 2023-2024 erhoben wurden. Der entwickelte Algorithmus für das Überwachungs- und Kontrollsystem (MCS) stellt ein entscheidungsunterstützendes Instrument für Marketingmanager in Geschäftsbanken dar.

STICHWORTE: Überwachung, Banken, Produktpositionierung, Strategie

RÉSUMÉ

Dans le contexte du secteur des services financiers, caractérisé par une dynamique de marché en évolution rapide et des attentes des clients de plus en plus sophistiquées, le déploiement de systèmes de

surveillance et de contrôle robustes est impératif pour que les banques puissent opérationnaliser efficacement leurs stratégies de positionnement des produits. L'objectif de cette étude est de proposer un cadre algorithmique pour un système de surveillance et de contrôle dédié à la mise en œuvre des stratégies de positionnement des produits au sein des banques commerciales. L'algorithme proposé s'appuie sur les données marketing recueillies auprès de 23 banques bulgares au cours de la période 2023-2024. L'algorithme du système de surveillance et de contrôle développé représente un outil d'aide à la décision pour les responsables marketing des banques commerciales.

MOTS-CLÉS: surveillance, banques, positionnement des produits, stratégie

INTRODUCTION

Product positioning constitutes a fundamental strategic marketing process aimed at establishing a distinct and favorable perception of a product within the consumer's mind relative to competing alternatives (Kotler & Keller, 2016). In the context of the financial services sector, characterized by rapidly evolving market dynamics and increasingly sophisticated customer expectations, the deployment of robust monitoring and control systems is imperative for banks to effectively operationalize their product positioning strategies. These systems predominantly rely on algorithmic methodologies to continuously track key performance indicators, analyze consumer behavior, and facilitate timely responses to market fluctuations (Simons, 1995).

Given the paramount importance of trust, regulatory compliance, and customer experience in banking, monitoring and control systems serve a critical function in sustaining brand positioning, differentiating financial product offerings—such as loans, credit cards, and savings accounts—and maintaining competitive advantage (Capgemini, 2021).

Monitoring algorithms encompass techniques that gather and analyze data pertaining to market conditions, customer feedback, and competitor activities. Commonly employed methods include:

- Sentiment analysis applied to social media content and customer reviews to assess brand perception (Cambria et al., 2017);
- Cluster analysis to segment customers based on behavioral patterns, thereby enabling targeted product positioning strategies (Jain, 2010);
- Time-series forecasting to predict market demand trends and shifts in customer preferences (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018).

Complementing these, control algorithms function to close the strategic feedback loop by prescribing corrective actions based on monitoring insights. Typical approaches include:

- Rule-based systems that initiate adjustments to the marketing mix—such as pricing modifications and promotional activities—when key performance indicators diverge from predetermined targets (Bititci et al., 2018);
- Reinforcement learning models that iteratively optimize strategies within complex and dynamic environments, exemplified by their application in retail banking cross-selling campaigns (Mnih et al., 2015);
- Multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) algorithms that reconcile trade-offs among product attributes, pricing structures, and consumer preferences to refine positioning strategies (Saaty, 2008).

Within the highly competitive and regulated banking landscape, where differentiation depends heavily on superior customer experience, trust, and innovation, successful institutions harness advanced monitoring and control systems to implement and sustain effective product positioning strategies (McKinsey & Company, 2020). Notable best practices include:

- **Real-Time Customer Sentiment Monitoring:** Major banks such as JPMorgan Chase and HSBC utilize sentiment analysis algorithms on social media, online reviews, and customer service interactions to promptly detect changes in customer perceptions, enabling near real-time adjustments in marketing communications and product offerings (Liu et al., 2020).
- **Dynamic Segmentation and Personalization:** Banks employ clustering and predictive analytics to segment customers not only by demographics but also by transactional behavior and digital engagement, facilitating the precise positioning of products like premium credit cards or customized loan packages aligned with each segment's values and needs (Jain, 2010).
- **Algorithmic Pricing and Promotion Control:** Financial institutions implement algorithmic control systems that dynamically adjust interest rates, fees, and promotional campaigns based on prevailing market conditions and competitor strategies, leveraging reinforcement learning and prescriptive analytics to optimize profitability while maintaining customer satisfaction (Bititci et al., 2018).
- **Integrated Performance Dashboards:** The combination of balanced scorecards and real-time dashboards enables continuous monitoring of key performance indicators such as market share, customer acquisition costs, and Net Promoter Scores (NPS), with control algorithms flagging deviations from strategic objectives and triggering appropriate corrective actions (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).
- **Regulatory and Risk Management Integration:** Banks incorporate regulatory requirements and risk appetite considerations directly into control algorithms to ensure compliance and risk mitigation throughout the product positioning process, thereby avoiding financial penalties and reputational damage (Basel Committee, 2019).

Recent scholarly and industry investigations highlight several advanced algorithmic frameworks tailored to the banking sector, including:

- **Hybrid Supervised-Unsupervised Models:** These approaches combine labeled customer data (e.g., churn risk) with unsupervised behavioral clustering to enhance the precision of product positioning strategies (Li et al., 2022).
- **Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) Models:** Designed to improve transparency in decision-making processes, XAI models facilitate regulatory compliance and foster customer trust by making control actions interpretable (Doshi-Velez & Kim, 2017).
- **Multi-Agent Systems:** These simulate competitive market environments involving multiple banking entities, allowing for strategic scenario analysis and the development of resilient control algorithms (Wang & Chen, 2021).

The objective of this study is to propose an algorithmic framework for a monitoring and control system dedicated to the implementation of product positioning strategies within commercial banks. The proposed algorithm leverages marketing data collected from 23 Bulgarian banks over the period 2023–2024.

The developed monitoring and control system (MCS) algorithm represents a decision-support tool for marketing managers in commercial banking, structured around the following components: (1) identification of key markers for evaluating and selecting appropriate product positioning strategies; (2) determination of reference values for these markers to facilitate systematic diagnosis of the implemented strategies' effects; and (3) a methodology for corrective action contingent on observed deviations from the intended product positioning strategy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Identification of Markers for Evaluation and Selection of an Appropriate Product Positioning Strategy. In the proposed Quality Monitoring System (QMS) algorithm, markers function as critical indicators employed to systematically analyze and assess the effectiveness of the product positioning strategy implemented by a commercial bank. These markers serve as reliable evaluative tools, enabling marketing managers to quantitatively and qualitatively measure strategic outcomes and ensure alignment with organizational objectives.

While marketing managers may formulate a diverse array of potential product positioning strategies, for the purposes of this study, these strategies are categorized into four broadly applicable groups. This classification facilitates a structured approach to strategy evaluation and selection, as summarized in the subsequent table.

Table 1. Categorization of product positioning strategies and markers for evaluating effects. Source: Own.

No.	Type of product positioning strategy	Strategy characteristics	Strategy objective	Strategy implementation performance indicators (markers)
1	Offensive strategy	It is characterized by the idea that a commercial bank does not need to waste time and attack a market segment by referring only to its strengths. Improving weaknesses will take time, during which the market situation may change and the commercial bank may lose market positions. That is why it is good to attack at the moment with what the commercial bank is strong in.	Offering the best offer in the market segment; Exclusivity; Attack on all flanks of the competition	Interest income; Profitability of interest expenses; Profitability of interest income; Market share; Interest income efficiency; Market growth.
2	Defensive strategy	Characteristic of this strategy is that the strategist needs to protect the market positions of the commercial bank not only by using its strengths, but also to	Optimization of marketing costs; Consolidation of the product portfolio;	Interest income; Profitability of interest expenses; Profitability of interest income; Market share; Interest income efficiency; Market growth.

		<p>spend time on eliminating the weaknesses. The idea is that the strategist considers the threat to be more likely to occur than the opportunity. Therefore, following this product positioning strategy requires focusing on the threat, focusing on the "invasion" of new events in the market segment</p>		
3	Conservative strategy	<p>The idea of this strategy is that it is not good to leave the "comfort zone", i.e. the commercial bank needs to continue its positioning strategy without changing it and be able to retain its most loyal customers. Increasing market share is not a priority, but preserving the existing one</p>	<p>Standardization; Economies of scale; Price leadership;</p>	<p>Interest income; Profitability of interest expenses; Profitability of interest income; Market share; Interest income efficiency; Market growth.</p>
4	Innovative strategy	<p>Creating new value (true innovation) or exploiting already created value by engaging in strategic alliances</p>	<p>Greater coverage of consumer preferences; Greater market share; Creating new value; Exploiting newly accepted market value; Market exclusivity.</p>	<p>Interest income; Profitability of interest expenses; Profitability of interest income; Market share; Interest income efficiency; Market growth.</p>

Identification of Reference Values for Markers to Diagnose the Product Positioning Strategy.

The markers identified in Table 1 for analyzing and assessing the outcomes of the implemented product positioning strategy serve as foundational elements for initiating control over the execution of the selected strategy. These markers act as control benchmarks against which deviations from the bank's intended product positioning strategy can be measured. For these markers to effectively fulfill this evaluative role, it is essential to validate their values as reliable diagnostic tools.

Validation of the markers is conducted through regression analysis, a statistical method employed to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the selected type of product positioning strategy and the identified markers (validated indicators). The markers subjected to validation include: (1) interest income; (2) profitability of interest expenses; (3) profitability of interest income; (4) market share; (5) efficiency of interest income; and (6) market growth. (Borisov, 2015)

The regression model developed for statistically testing the relationship between the type of positioning strategy and the diagnostic markers encompasses the following six correlations:

1. The correlation between the number of positioned product units and interest income;

2. The correlation between the number of positioned product units and profitability of interest expenses;
3. The correlation between the number of positioned product units and profitability of interest income;
4. The correlation between the number of positioned product units and efficiency of interest income;
5. The correlation between the number of positioned product units and market share;
6. The correlation between the number of positioned product units and market growth.

Data for the validation of this regression model were collected from 23 commercial banks. These data were categorized into four statistical groups based on the type of product positioning strategy employed:

- The first group comprises data from commercial banks implementing an **offensive** product positioning strategy;
- The second group includes data from banks pursuing a **defensive** positioning strategy;
- The third group consists of data from banks following a **conservative** product positioning strategy;
- The fourth group contains data from banks adopting an **innovative** product positioning strategy.

This stratification allows for rigorous statistical assessment of the relationships between strategy types and marker values, thereby ensuring that the markers provide a valid and robust basis for monitoring and control of product positioning strategies.

Table 2. Results of testing the correlation between the number of positioned product units and the selected markers in the group of commercial banks that implement an offensive product positioning strategy. Source: data from the accounting balance sheets of commercial banks

Type "Offensive Strategy"	Diagnostic markers					
	Interest income (thousand BGN)	Profitability of interest expenses	Interest income profitability	Interest income efficiency	Market share (%)	Market growth (%)
Adjusted correlation coefficient	0.9107	0.782	0.598	0.551	0.510	0.442
Degree of dependence	very significant	significant	significant	significant	significant	moderate
Type of dependency	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive
Minimum/maximum value	70/628,499	0.01/6.98	0.01/1.00	1.04/7.00	0.001/23.00	25/241
Coefficient of variation	0.354	0.295	0.351	0.210	0.635	0.773

The subsequent Tables 2, 3, 4, and 5 summarize the results of the regression analyses conducted to examine the relationships between the number of positioned product units and the selected indicators (markers), namely: interest income, profitability of interest expenses, profitability of interest income, efficiency of interest income, market share, and market growth.

Table 2 presents the regression results for the group of commercial banks categorized under the **offensive strategy** positioning approach. The adjusted correlation coefficients indicate positive direct relationships across all examined variables. Specifically, an increase in the number of positioned product units within the relevant market segment corresponds to improvements in profitability, efficiency, and market positioning as measured by the specified markers. Notably, a strong correlation was observed between the number of positioned product units and interest income, quantified in thousands of Bulgarian leva. Conversely, a moderate correlation was identified between the number of positioned product units and market growth, measured in relative terms.

Table 3 reports the findings for commercial banks employing a **defensive** product positioning strategy, detailing the results of correlation testing between the number of positioned product units and the diagnostic markers.

The results of the statistical regression analysis demonstrate a positive, direct relationship among the examined variables. Specifically, within the sample of commercial banks studied, an increase in the number of positioned product units is associated with proportional increases in interest income, profitability of costs and revenues, revenue efficiency, market share, and market growth. The strength of these associations ranges from moderate to very high, indicating a substantive degree of dependence between the examined factors.

Table 3. Results of testing the correlation between the number of positioned product units and the selected markers in the group of commercial banks that implement a defensive product positioning strategy. Source: data from the accounting balance sheets of commercial banks

Type "Defensive Strategy"	Diagnostic markers					
	Interest income (thousand BGN)	Profitability of interest expenses	Interest income profitability	Interest income efficiency	Market share (%)	Market growth (%)
Adjusted correlation coefficient	0.911	0.811	0.602	0.509	0.556	0.410
Degree of dependence	very significant	significant	significant	significant	significant	moderate
Type of dependency	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive
Minimum/maximum value	10/301,855	0.001/15.21	0.001/0.85	0.5/5.00	0.005/18.51	85/125
Coefficient of variation	0.425	0.325	0.505	0.288	0.710	0.751

Table 4 presents the regression results for the subset of commercial banks employing a **conservative** product positioning strategy. In this group, a similarly direct correlation is observed across the studied variables. Notably, the correlation between the number of positioned product units and interest income exhibits a very high degree of positive dependence. For the remaining markers, the

strength of correlation varies between high and moderate levels, confirming consistent but differentiated degrees of association among the factors.

Table 4. Results of testing the correlation between the number of positioned product units and the selected markers in the group of commercial banks that implement a conservative product positioning strategy. Source: data from the accounting balance sheets of commercial banks

Type "Conservative Strategy"	Diagnostic markers					
	Interest income (thousand BGN)	Profitability of interest expenses	Interest income profitability	Interest income efficiency	Market share (%)	Market growth (%)
Adjusted correlation coefficient	0.890	0.757	0.855	0.655	0.425	0.401
Degree of dependence	very significant	significant	significant	significant	moderate	moderate
Type of dependency	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive
Minimum/maximum value	17/577,901	0.02/0.50	0.002/1.85	0.3/3.3	0.001/10.22	45/225
Coefficient of variation	0.322	0.851	0.219	0.221	0.805	0.721

Table 5 presents the results of the correlation analysis conducted for the group of commercial banks implementing an **innovation** strategy in positioning their financial products. The analysis reveals a direct relationship between the number of positioned product units and the examined markers. The strength of these associations ranges from moderate to very high, indicating a significant degree of dependence among the variables within this group.

Table 5. Results of testing the correlation between the number of positioned product units and the selected markers in the group of commercial banks that implement an innovative product positioning strategy. Source: data from the accounting balance sheets of commercial banks

Type "Innovation Strategy"	Diagnostic markers					
	Interest income (thousand BGN)	Profitability of interest expenses	Interest income profitability	Interest income efficiency	Market share (%)	Market growth (%)
Adjusted correlation coefficient	0.805	0.683	0.785	0.305	0.360	0.840
Degree of dependence	very significant	significant	significant	moderate	moderate	very significant
Type of dependency	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive	positive
Minimum/maximum value	33/811 005	0.02/0.75	0.01/2.01	0.44/6.11	0.001/9.55	65/181
Coefficient of variation	0.405	0.955	0.382	0.334	0.886	0.705

In summary, the results of the correlation analyses between the indicator “number of positioned product units” and the selected diagnostic markers demonstrate statistically significant relationships. This finding confirms that the chosen markers are effective and promising tools for diagnosing the outcomes of the applied product positioning strategies within the presented monitoring and control system (MCS) algorithm.

The subsequent step in the implementation of the MCS algorithm involves establishing reference values for these diagnostic markers. To determine these reference values, three statistical parameters are utilized: (1) the minimum marker value, (2) the maximum marker value, and (3) the coefficient of variation, which provides an estimate of the variability of the marker within the studied group of commercial banks.

Using these parameters, reference value intervals for each marker are calculated according to the following formulas:

- The lower limit of the interval is obtained by multiplying the minimum marker value by the coefficient of variation within the group;
- The upper limit of the interval is obtained by multiplying the maximum marker value by the coefficient of variation within the group.

The application of these formulas yields reliable reference values for the markers across each group of commercial banks examined. Moreover, these reference values facilitate the assessment of the effectiveness of each of the four product positioning strategies under consideration. The resulting reference values are presented in Table 6.

Table 6. Reference values of markers for assessing the effectiveness of the application of product positioning strategies. Source: Own.

Strategy type	Reference values of change markers					
	Interest income (thousand BGN)	Profitability of interest expenses	Interest income profitability	Interest income efficiency	Market share %	Market growth %
Offensive strategy	from 24.78 to 222 489	from 0.003 to 2.10	from 0.004 to 0.35	from 0.22 to 1.47	from 0.0006 to 14.61	from 19.33 to 186.30
Defensive strategy	from 4.25 to 128 288	from 0.0003 to 4.9	from 0.0005 to 0.43	from 0.144 to 1.44	from 0.004 to 13.14	from 63.84 to 93.88
Conservative strategy	from 5.47 to 186,084	from 0.02 to 0.43	from 0.0004 to 0.41	from 0.067 to 0.73	from 0.0008 to 8.21	from 32.45 to 162.23
Innovation strategy	from 13.37 to 328 457	from 0.02 to 0.72	from 0.004 to 0.77	from 0.15 to 2.04	from 0.0009 to 8.46	from 45.83 to 127.61

Diagnostic Assessment of the Effects of the Product Positioning and Prevention Strategy. Utilizing the identified markers and their corresponding reference values, marketing managers of

commercial banks are equipped to perform an objectively substantiated diagnosis of the effectiveness of the implemented product positioning strategy. The subsequent phase in the proposed monitoring and control system (MCS) algorithm involves defining the appropriate managerial actions based on the status of these markers—specifically, whether the markers remain within the established confidence intervals, indicating no deviation from reference values, or whether there is a significant deviation.

In the first scenario, where marker values fall within the confidence intervals, marketing managers should maintain the current implementation of their selected product positioning strategy while ensuring continuous and systematic monitoring of marker trends.

Conversely, if marker values deviate substantially from the reference ranges, corrective action is required. Marketing managers must intervene and adjust the trajectory of the positioning strategy to address the identified discrepancies. The magnitude and direction of these deviations are assessed through an analysis of the relationship between market share and profitability. Given that these two variables can exhibit both direct and inverse relationships, the evaluation employs a diagnostic matrix—herein referred to as the **“Profitability/Market Share Matrix”**—which facilitates a nuanced understanding of the scale and direction of deviations.

This proposed matrix serves as a diagnostic and preventive tool, enabling marketing managers to simultaneously evaluate the relative importance of market share and profitability in guiding strategic adjustments. The matrix is illustrated in the following figure and represents an integrative framework for assessing the interaction between these critical performance indicators.

In the diagnostic matrix developed for evaluating the effects of the applied product positioning strategy, four distinct quadrants are delineated. Each quadrant corresponds to a specific outcome of the strategy at the point of observation, providing marketing managers with a structured framework to interpret performance indicators.

The **first quadrant** represents the so-called **“alpha effect”**, characterized by market share values exceeding the upper reference limit, alongside profitability markers from interest income and interest expenses also surpassing their respective upper bounds. This scenario indicates highly effective coordination between market share management and profitability outcomes. The presence of an alpha effect suggests that the implemented product positioning strategy has achieved an optimal balance within the prevailing marketing environment. Consequently, marketing managers should focus on maintaining the stability of this positioning effect over time.

The **second quadrant** corresponds to the **“beta effect”**, which arises when market share remains above the upper reference limit, but profitability indicators—specifically from interest income and/or interest expenses—fall below their lower thresholds. This pattern implies that while the strategy has successfully expanded market share, it has concurrently compromised profitability. In such cases, marketing managers are advised to perform a detailed contribution analysis of individual products, identifying those with limited profitability contributions. Applying the product life cycle method can further elucidate which low-contributing products are nearing the end of their viability and should be phased out. Resources freed from these products can then be reallocated to strengthen market positions of high-contributing products, thereby enhancing overall profitability.

The **third quadrant** identifies the **“gamma effect”**, characterized by market share metrics falling below the lower reference limit, whereas profitability markers from interest income and/or interest

expenses exceed the upper reference limit. This condition signifies that the positioning strategy has led to a reduction in market share; however, this contraction has positively impacted profitability. Under this effect, marketing managers should evaluate product-level contributions to profitability, distinguishing “profit centers” that form the core of the bank’s financial success. These key products should continue their current positioning, while products with lower profitability contributions require repositioning strategies to improve market performance.

	Market share	
Profitability of the activity	First quadrant “α – effect” (1) The market share is above the upper limit in the set reference values; (2) The profitability of interest income is above the upper limit in the set reference values and/or (3) The return on interest expenses is above the upper limit of the set reference values.	Third quadrant “γ – effect” (1) The market share is below the lower limit of the set reference values; (2) The profitability of interest income is above the upper limit in the set reference values and/or (3) The return on interest expenses is above the upper limit of the set reference values.
	Second quadrant “β – effect” (1) The market share is above the upper limit in the set reference values; (2) The profitability of interest income is below the lower limit of the benchmarks and/or (3) The return on interest expenses is below the lower limit of the set reference values.	Fourth quadrant “Δ – effect” (1) The market share is below the lower limit of the set reference values; (2) The profitability of interest income is below the lower limit of the benchmarks and/or (3) The return on interest expenses is below the lower limit of the set reference values.

Figure 1. Matrix for diagnosing the effects of the applied product positioning strategy. Source: Own.

The **fourth quadrant** validates the “**delta effect**”, observed when both market share and profitability markers fall below their respective lower reference limits. This indicates that the positioning strategy has resulted in diminished market share and reduced profitability concurrently, signaling a critical failure in strategic implementation. In such instances, managers must conduct a comprehensive product-level analysis, assessing factors such as market novelty, competitive pressures, and potential cross-product support within the bank’s portfolio. Persistent delta effects necessitate a strategic reassessment and the formulation of a new, more effective product positioning strategy.

CONCLUSION

It is important to emphasize that within the proposed quality monitoring system (QMS) algorithm for product positioning strategy implementation, reference values may require periodic adjustment in response to significant shifts in the marketing environment. Such updates should be undertaken systematically and not sporadically, ensuring that the diagnostic process remains a consistent and integral component of strategic product positioning management in commercial banking.

Monitoring and control system algorithms are vital enablers of effective product positioning strategies in the banking sector. Through real-time data analysis, dynamic customer segmentation, and automated control actions, banks can maintain strategic alignment with market demands and regulatory frameworks. Incorporating AI and machine learning algorithms enhances these systems, but banks must navigate challenges related to data ethics, model transparency, and adaptability.

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INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN DIGITALIZATION OF AGRICULTURE AND POSSIBILITIES OF ITS APPLICATION IN ARMENIA

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ABSTRACT

The article reflects the peculiarities of the digitalization of agriculture in different countries, including the Republic of Armenia.

The article considers revealing the international experience in digitalization of agriculture and identification of the ways that would be applicable also in Armenia. Studies and analyses of the digitalization in agriculture in several developed and developing countries, including the state support policies aimed at digitalization and the feasibility of the application thereof in Armenia were carried out, with digitalization measures suggested.

The timeliness of the study is that today, it is impossible to increase the competitiveness of agriculture without digital solutions. Meanwhile, within the framework of the RA Government's 2021-2026 Programme for Activity Measures, support for the development of digital agriculture has been defined as one of the measures to develop overall agriculture and to increase its productivity.

The results of the studies and analyses can serve as a basis for developing and implementing measures aimed at digitalization of agriculture in the Republic of Armenia and, as a result, achieving increased intensification and competitiveness of the sector.

KEYWORDS: digitalization of agriculture, digital technologies, digital platforms

ABSTRAKT

Der Artikel beleuchtet die Besonderheiten der Digitalisierung der Landwirtschaft in verschiedenen Ländern, darunter auch in der Republik Armenien.

Der Artikel befasst sich mit der Offenlegung der internationalen Erfahrungen in der Digitalisierung der Landwirtschaft und der Identifizierung von Wegen, die auch in Armenien anwendbar wären. Es wurden Studien und Analysen der Digitalisierung in der Landwirtschaft in verschiedenen Industrie- und Entwicklungsländern durchgeführt, einschließlich der staatlichen Unterstützungsmaßnahmen für die Digitalisierung und der Durchführbarkeit ihrer Anwendung in Armenien, und es wurden Digitalisierungsmaßnahmen vorgeschlagen.

Die Aktualität der Studie besteht darin, dass es heute unmöglich ist, die Wettbewerbsfähigkeit der Landwirtschaft ohne digitale Lösungen zu steigern. Im Rahmen des Aktionsprogramms 2021-2026 der Regierung der Republik Armenien wurde die Unterstützung der Entwicklung der digitalen Landwirtschaft als eine der Maßnahmen zur Entwicklung der gesamten Landwirtschaft und zur Steigerung ihrer Produktivität definiert.

Die Ergebnisse der Studien und Analysen können als Grundlage für die Entwicklung und Umsetzung von Maßnahmen dienen, die auf die Digitalisierung der Landwirtschaft in der Republik Armenien abzielen, um so die Intensivierung und Wettbewerbsfähigkeit des Sektors zu steigern.

STICHWORTE: Digitalisierung der Landwirtschaft, digitale Technologien, digitale Plattformen

RÉSUMÉ

L'article reflète les particularités de la numérisation de l'agriculture dans différents pays, y compris la République d'Arménie.

L'article envisage de révéler l'expérience internationale en matière de numérisation de l'agriculture et d'identifier les moyens qui pourraient s'appliquer également à l'Arménie. Des études et des analyses de la numérisation de l'agriculture dans plusieurs pays développés et en développement, y compris les politiques de soutien de l'État visant à la numérisation et la faisabilité de leur application en Arménie, ont été effectuées, avec des mesures de numérisation suggérées.

Cette étude est d'autant plus opportune qu'il est aujourd'hui impossible d'accroître la compétitivité de l'agriculture sans solutions numériques. Par ailleurs, dans le cadre du programme de mesures 2021-2026 du gouvernement de la République d'Arménie, le soutien au développement de l'agriculture numérique a été défini comme l'une des mesures visant à développer l'ensemble de l'agriculture et à accroître sa productivité.

Les résultats des études et des analyses peuvent servir de base à l'élaboration et à la mise en œuvre de mesures visant à numériser l'agriculture dans la République d'Arménie et, par conséquent, à accroître l'intensification et la compétitivité du secteur.

MOTS-CLÉS: numérisation de l'agriculture, technologies numériques, plateformes numériques

INTRODUCTION

Currently, it is impossible to increase the competitiveness of the agrarian sector without innovative technologies and digital solutions, which contribute to increasing the productivity, optimizing the costs, and sustainable development of agriculture. To face the current challenges and to keep pace with other countries, we need to admit the role of and succeed in using innovative and digital technologies in the intensification of agriculture. The information obtained through digital technologies will enable us to take realistic sectoral decisions, to make the agrarian policies more targeted, and automate the process of collecting sector-related information.

As experts from the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) note, digital agriculture offers greater opportunities to achieve more sustainable development in the sector from both the economic, environmental and social points of view (http://www.fao.org/digital_agriculture/digital-portfolio/en). Meanwhile, the experts from the UN Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) believe that digital technologies – the internet, mobile technologies and devices, digital analyses, artificial

intelligence, digitalized services and applications – completely change agriculture and the food system (<https://www.oecd.org/agriculture/topics/technology-and-digital-agriculture/>).

Authors such as Kovács and Husti support the view that agriculture's efficiency and competitiveness can greatly enhance once the benefits of digitalization are properly used. "Smart farming makes use of GPS services, machine to machine (M2M) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies, sensors and big data to optimize crop yield and reduce waste" (Kovács & Husti, 2018). Other researchers in the field add that "smart agriculture is transforming the agricultural sector in terms of economic, social, and environmental sustainability" (Ciruela Lorenzo et al., 2020) (Zheleva & Delcheva, 2023).

The core of this process lies in the possibility of transferring, classification, processing, storing and usage of information arrays easily and at a low cost with minimal loss. We come up with two major observations from the literature review: firstly, digital innovations as widespread phenomena bring about evident economic benefits. In addition, the downsides of digitalization in the sector are also taken into consideration, particularly in addressing the level of unemployment risk for SME workers (Zheleva & Delcheva, 2023).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study of the international experience of digitalization of agriculture indicates that avoiding digital transformation will lead to the loss of competitiveness of the agricultural sector. In this context, countries attach importance to implementing a complex of stimulating and regulating measures, the interdependence of which will determine the introduction of digital technologies in the agricultural sector. Such measures include: development of digital infrastructure (e.g. internet access); modernization of the education system and developing new programs of trainings; simplified system of funding innovations; state regulation; digitalization of the processes of providing state support in the agricultural sector, etc.

Both theoretical and empiric research methods, such as analysis, synthesis, comparison, and logic, were used in this study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In the United States, the state policy is focusing on different directions of the digitalization of agriculture: precision agriculture, digital financial services, data record and development of data management system, expansion of information technology support, etc. National Institute of Food and Agriculture (NIFA) periodically conducts research through grants awarded in the field of digitalization. The main directions of financing are: data analysis in the agricultural sector, machine learning, artificial intellect and forecasting technologies. Great attention is paid also to indirect forms of support: education, training programs, funding for research projects, as well as support to startups.

In the Kingdom of the Netherlands, the use of innovative and digital technologies has led to the application of the most efficient methods of farm management, in particular, reduction of the consumption of irrigation water by 90% for growing a number of crops, exclusion of application of chemical pesticides, increase in the yielding capacity of vegetable by about 28%, etc.

Most of the innovative developments are carried out at Wageningen University. A significant part of the research programs is focused on innovations based on data analysis and high technologies. According to the assessments of the university, it is expected that by 2030, decisions in the food sector will be mainly taken based on the data received from open and common sources, including platforms that will receive information from different machines, sensors and others. The university supports 200,000

farmers by providing geodetic data obtained from satellite signals, which allow assessing the deviations in the physical condition of land plots. Investment programs are also aimed at digitalization of farms, in particular the dissemination of “digital twins”; in particular, a digital copy of an object or process allows economic entities to quickly identify problems, clearly predict the results and produce quality products.

In the Federal Republic of Germany, the use of digital technologies is one of the priority directions of the development of agriculture. The Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture is developing programs focusing on digital changes in rural areas and, since 2020, has been funding the pilot “digital fields” being created in agroholdings. Currently, there are 14 such digital fields, including **Digimilch** – digitalization of the milk value chain; **Agrisens-DEMMIN 4.0** – remote sensing for plant growing (the goal is to provide information to economic entities, which is important for efficient management of production, including optimization of fertilizer application); and **DigiVine** – digitalization of grape value chain focusing on creation of surplus value.

In Israel, innovative technologies are widely introduced in all sectors of food and agriculture complex. The GPS and GIS tools and equipment are used for precision and conservation agriculture.

With the help of different sensors, equipment and aerial photographs, various analyses are carried out in agriculture, guidebooks are compiled, risks are assessed and precautionary measures taken. There is a digital pedigree book called **Israeli Dairy Herd Book**, which is a centralized digital database about dairy cows and is managed by the Israeli Cattle Breeders Association. It allows to record data such as the amount of the milk produced, the proportion of the substances contained in it, quality of the milk, as well as the data on genetic and reproductive ability and on the health situation of each cow in the country. In herds with more than 150 cows, the record is carried out on a monthly basis by a representative of the association, who records the related information on a mobile terminal. In herds with less than 150 cows, the farmer manually records the data on the milk produced and sends the information to the central database. A sample is taken from the milk of the registered cows every month and sent to the central laboratory of milk testing; the laboratory analyzes the components of the milk samples monthly and sends them to the central database. This laboratory analyzes also the milk samples of milk supplying companies daily. The results are used to determine the size of the subsidies provided to farmers. The entire amount of milk supplied to all dairy processing companies is tested. For each batch, the factories send summary information to the economic entities, which includes the results of the analyses. This information is also transferred to the database of the Association. All data in the system undergo logical verification so that dairy farmers and other participants of the value chain and the end consumers could receive accurate information.

In the Republic of Poland, a one stop shop service and the **ARiMR** mobile application are in operation, with the main goal to simplify the administrative procedures and reduce bureaucratic operations. In addition, state support measures are implemented in the agriculture sector, which have an indirect effect on the enhancement of the level of digital literacy in the country.

The Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development, in cooperation with the Ministry of Digital Affairs, has taken the first step towards digitalization of agriculture by launching the Gov.pl website, which allows farmers to apply for assessment of harvest losses due to drought. Thanks to this, there is no need any more to appoint committees, involve a large number of people, and, which is no less important, the assessment of the degree of losses is carried out uniformly, based on the very detailed data from the

Institute of Soil Science and Crop Farming and Institute of Economics of Agriculture and Food Industry. This tool is constantly improving. For this purpose, the Institute of Soil Science and Crop Farming uses radiolocational data, which ensure greater accuracy than those from land-based weather stations. The launch of the one stop shop has led to a reduction in the number of documents filled out, time saving, etc.

Some of the operating services include:

- ✓ Request for assessment of losses of agricultural crops due to drought
- ✓ Request for refund of access tax included in the price of diesel fuel
- ✓ Application for social insurance for farmers
- ✓ Application for receiving a phytosanitary certificate
- ✓ Application for registration in the organic seed registry
- ✓ Application for registration in a registry of professional organizations
- ✓ Application for registration of pedigree animals, etc.

To promote digitalization, the state also takes measures such as support in the development of professional abilities and skills (farmers are provided the opportunity to participate in free trainings and seminars), development of agricultural services and entrepreneurship (with up to 50% reimbursement of investments), etc.

In the **Republic of Chile**, the accessibility of state support is also ensured through the use of digital technologies, in particular, through an interactive system, farmers can choose the type of state support they need (Kamalyan, 2022).

The development of digital agriculture in **Bulgaria** in the last decade began with the adoption of innovative technologies including ground sensors, satellite imagery, GPS receivers in farming machinery, etc. A lot of companies develop software products and applications tailored for the agricultural sector, particularly for specific clients and based on their actual needs. These companies develop web-based products and mobile apps for visualizing information to manage and monitor the different farm operations (Kostadinova, 2021).

AgroHub.BG is a digital innovation hub founded in Bulgaria with the primary goals of digitalization of Bulgarian agriculture and rural areas using technologies like blockchain, IoT; enhancing digital technologies within the agri-food chain; ensuring access to current knowledge; testing and experimenting digital innovations; and collaborating with Bulgarian companies to assess the needs for digital skills. A large range of measures were taken in recent years to digitalize the management of the ag sector in the country. Numerous information systems, databases, and registers have been created by the Ministry of Agriculture, Food and Forestry over the recent years, such as those for general administration and those related to GIS, among others. In addition, Strategy for digitalization of agriculture and rural areas of the Republic of Bulgaria was adopted in 2019, with the primary objective of transforming the Bulgarian agriculture and agribusinesses into a high-tech and sustainable field that will improve the quality of life for farmers and rural areas.

Bulgaria is also promoting collaboration between research institutions and agribusinesses, including through state financial support programs like "Innovation and Competitiveness" - an operational initiative designed to encourage entrepreneurship and assist in establishment and development of new

sustainable businesses and high-tech companies focused on implementing innovative technologies (Kostadinova, 2021).

The Government of the **Republic of Kazakhstan** adopted the state program “Digital Kazakhstan” in 2017, one of the objectives of which is the digitalization of agriculture. Within the scope of digitalization of food and agriculture sector, the state plans livestock registration numbering systems, phytosanitary and veterinary risk analysis, as well as automated monitoring of the state of natural resources. The following digital solutions are expected to be implemented:

1. Promoting the introduction of “Precision Agriculture” management system; in particular, based on the data provided by weather stations, farmers will be able to learn about the condition of crops, humidity, nutrients, pests, likelihood of precipitation and take correct and sound decisions.
2. Unified electronic market (e-Agrotrade) for agricultural products. To develop the marketing of agroindustrial products, an electronic trade platform will be operated between farmers, wholesale and distribution centers, retail chains and markets.
3. Creation and implementation of a “National Spatial Data Infrastructure”. It is planned to modernize the state-owned geodetic networks and install a modern coordinate system using satellite technologies.

Kazakhstan operates the Qoldau.kz digital technology platform, where electronic applications are accepted in such areas of state support in agriculture as agricultural insurance, purchase of fertilizers, pesticides, seeds, etc. In addition, the platform provides access to an electronic map of subjects of food and agriculture system, the digital registry of product passports, the electronic record of selection achievements in the fields of crop growing and livestock breeding, the unified registry of production facilities, plans for electronic management and use of pastures, the Blockchain – distributed information storage platform, etc.

The Ministry of Agriculture of the **Russian Federation** has developed the “Digital Agriculture” departmental project. All data on agricultural lands are stored in a unified field information system, the Electronic Atlas of Agricultural Lands, which reflects the relevant information on the agricultural lands, their areas, condition, degradation level and the state of restoration.

The National System of Animal Numbering and Registration ensures the digitization of the process of marking, registration, identification and numbering of animals; in addition, for creating a Registry of Farm Producers, the Main Regional Digital Platform of Agro industrial Complex operates, which allows to organize automated collection of reports from agricultural producers.

In Russia, there are information systems such as:

- ✓ The Federal State Information System for Numbering and Registration of Tractors, Self-propelled Vehicles and Their Trailers
- ✓ System for Provision of Public Services in Electronic Form of the RF Ministry of Agriculture
- ✓ Automated Information System of Registries, Registers and Standard-Reference Information (<http://opendata.mcx.ru/opendata/>)
- ✓ Information System for Planning and Control of State Program ((ИС ПК ГП. URL: <http://efis.mcx.ru/landing/>).
- ✓ Unified Federal Information System on Farmland.

The **Republic of Belarus** has established a system for identification, registration and traceability of animals and animal products (“Animal Identification Traceability System”), which cooperates with other information systems operating in the agriculture sector, such as the National Identification System GS1, the Pedigree Livestock Breeding System, the System of Meat Processing Plants, Farm Management Systems (Automated Herd Management System CYC-1000), etc. It enables to carry out identification and registration of cattle, as well as development and introduction of a centralized nationwide system that allows to digitalize the data, in particular, to obtain up-to-date information on the origin, location and health status of animals (Kamalyan, 2022).

The first steps towards digitalization in the **Republic of Armenia** began in 2010: the www.e-gov.am electronic management platform was launched. In 2021, the program of digitalization strategy and the program of measures were adopted (Decision of the Government of the Republic of Armenia, 2021), while the guiding document in the agricultural sector was the The Strategy of the Main Directions Ensuring Economic Development in Agricultural Sector of the Republic of Armenia for 2020-2030, approved in 2019. This document defines the main digital and innovation directions of agricultural strategy: investments in digital agricultural national platforms and digitalization initiatives, promotion and introduction of large-scale (non digital) innovations in the agricultural sector, digitalization of the government's agricultural systems and development of the Ministry's digital and innovation capacities, capacity building for farmers and education system in the fields of agriculture and innovations (Strategy, 2019).

The <https://irazekum.am/> platform was launched in the country, which allows economic entities to get to know about the state support programs in all sectors, including agriculture, from a unified platform. The following works are being done in digitalization of agriculture:

- ✓ Efforts are underway to create a unified electronic information platform for the purpose of creating a register of grape plantations;
- ✓ Numbering and registration of agricultural animals, with provision of information databases;
- ✓ Digitalization of the procedure for implementation of agricultural support projects;

Creation, management and expansion of thematic layers related to agriculture, its integration with the national geoportal administered by the Cadastre Committee, in particular, a number of agricultural spatial layers have been uploaded on the ArcGIS Enterprise server, including smart barns and intensive orchards, so far operating in the pilot mode (<https://www.mineconomy.am/>).

CONCLUSIONS

To enhance the efficiency of efforts towards the development of digital agriculture in Armenia, we suggest taking the following measures:

1. Localizing the experience of the EU countries and Russia, create a register of economic entities active in agriculture that will also contribute to the effective administration of the subsidies provided;
2. Develop and implement state support programs aimed at the development of digital agriculture, in particular, measures aimed at the use of subsoil drip irrigation, solar pumping stations and agrodrones;
3. Following the example of Russia and Kazakhstan, create and administer a state register of agricultural lands, including unused lands, as a result of which we will have updated and digitalized

- information, which in turn will serve as a basis for developing measures for putting the latter into circulation, guiding potential investments, including consolidation, leasing, purchase and sale, etc.
4. Based on the experience of EU and Eurasian Economic Union countries, create a unified digital platform that will include:
 - all agriculture-related services (such as: certification, obtaining a phytosanitary passport, registration of medicines, etc.),
 - an online advisory platform: Questions to the Expert,
 - a section for online application for support programs,
 - a separate section on innovation technologies used in the agrarian sector, including those created by scientific centers, the National Academy of Sciences and the Armenian National Agrarian University,
 - a sector of land purchase and sale,
 - “Window for Economic Entities” section.
 5. Developing digital flowchart on diseases and pests, resulting in availability of digital information-advisory data and enhanced awareness of economic entities.
 6. Creation of a unified electronic market for selling agricultural products, equipped with different devices (computer, tablet, smartphone). The economic entities can register, have a personal page, where they can post free advertisements. The platform should also allow the entities to compare the prices for farm products and perform group purchases, when the buyers join to make one order to reduce the logistic costs. The platform will be connected to the payment systems of financial institutions to make online payments in the platform via bank cards and electronic wallets. The platform will have sections for wholesale and retails sales, including information sections on fresh, processed and organic products, as well as on input suppliers, companies rendering services in the agricultural sector, including processing companies.

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TRAINING IN CLIMATE-RESILIENT PRACTICES IN BULGARIA

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ABSTRACT

The study involved 42 randomly selected individuals. The interviewees are interested in the sustainable development of agriculture in a changing climate environment. The majority of them have participated in training related to the impact of climate change on agriculture and have plans to work in this sector of the economy.

The need for training on specific topics has been assessed through possible options. The strongest interest is in topics related to Climate Adaptation Strategies (e.g. drought-resistant crops) followed by Precision Agriculture and Smart Technologies and Regenerative farming or nature-based solutions. All three topics are desired by more than half of the respondents to receive additional training. In the topic of Renewable Energy Integration, interest is significantly lower, as the result can be explained by the findings already made about the weaker interest in renewable energy in general in Bulgaria. Nearly half of respondents said that community-led policy frameworks and actions are an important part of building climate-resilient agriculture and would like to receive training on this topic.

Improving climate-related agricultural education requires moving beyond conventional training methods toward context-driven, participatory, and future-ready learning. Based on current challenges and best practices, here are strategic suggestions for enhancing your institution or training program: 1) Make Training Farmer-Centered and Locally Relevant. 2) Use Hands-On, Demonstration-Based Learning. 3) Integrate Digital Tools and Climate Services. 4) Include Climate Literacy and Systems 5) Strengthen Institutional and Extension Capacity. 6) Link to Markets, Finance, and Policy.

Farmers need both knowledge and incentives to adopt and sustain change.

KEYWORDS: training, climate changes, agriculture, strategies

ABSTRAKT

An der Studie nahmen 42 zufällig ausgewählte Personen teil. Die Befragten interessieren sich für die nachhaltige Entwicklung der Landwirtschaft im Klimawandel. Die meisten von ihnen haben an Schulungen zu den Auswirkungen des Klimawandels auf die Landwirtschaft teilgenommen und planen, in diesem Wirtschaftszweig zu arbeiten.

Der Bedarf an Schulungen zu bestimmten Themen wurde anhand möglicher Optionen ermittelt. Das größte Interesse besteht an Themen im Zusammenhang mit Klimaanpassungsstrategien (z. B. dürreresistenten Nutzpflanzen), gefolgt von Präzisionslandwirtschaft und intelligenten Technologien

sowie regenerativer Landwirtschaft oder naturbasierten Lösungen. Zu allen drei Themen wünscht sich mehr als die Hälfte der Befragten zusätzliche Schulungen. Beim Thema Integration erneuerbarer Energien ist das Interesse deutlich geringer, was sich durch die bereits vorliegenden Erkenntnisse zum allgemein geringeren Interesse an erneuerbaren Energien in Bulgarien erklären lässt. Fast die Hälfte der Befragten gab an, dass gemeindegeführte politische Rahmenbedingungen und Maßnahmen ein wichtiger Bestandteil des Aufbaus einer klimaresilienten Landwirtschaft seien und wünscht sich daher eine Schulung zu diesem Thema.

Um die klimabezogene landwirtschaftliche Bildung zu verbessern, müssen konventionelle Trainingsmethoden überwunden und kontextorientiertes, partizipatives und zukunftsorientiertes Lernen gefördert werden. Basierend auf aktuellen Herausforderungen und Best Practices finden Sie hier strategische Vorschläge zur Verbesserung Ihrer Institution oder Ihres Trainingsprogramms: 1) Die Schulung sollte landwirtschaftlerzentriert und lokal relevant sein. 2) Praxisorientiertes, demonstrationsbasiertes Lernen nutzen. 3) Digitale Tools und Klimadienstleistungen integrieren. 4) Klimakompetenz und -systeme einbeziehen. 5) Die institutionellen und beratenden Kapazitäten stärken. 6) Mit Märkten, Finanzen und Politik verknüpfen.

STICHWORTE: Ausbildung, Klimawandel, Landwirtschaft, Strategien

RÉSUMÉ

L'étude a porté sur 42 personnes sélectionnées au hasard. Les personnes interrogées s'intéressent au développement durable de l'agriculture dans un contexte de changement climatique. La plupart d'entre elles ont suivi une formation sur l'impact du changement climatique sur l'agriculture et envisagent de travailler dans ce secteur.

Les besoins de formation sur des sujets spécifiques ont été évalués en fonction des options possibles. Les sujets les plus intéressants concernent les stratégies d'adaptation au changement climatique (par exemple, les cultures résistantes à la sécheresse), suivis de l'agriculture de précision et des technologies intelligentes, ainsi que de l'agriculture régénératrice ou des solutions fondées sur la nature. Plus de la moitié des répondants souhaitent une formation complémentaire sur ces trois sujets. Concernant l'intégration des énergies renouvelables, l'intérêt est nettement plus faible, ce résultat pouvant s'expliquer par les conclusions déjà formulées concernant le faible intérêt pour les énergies renouvelables en général en Bulgarie. Près de la moitié des répondants ont déclaré que les cadres politiques et les actions menées par les communautés locales sont un élément important du développement d'une agriculture résiliente au changement climatique et souhaiteraient recevoir une formation sur ce sujet.

Améliorer l'enseignement agricole lié au climat nécessite de dépasser les méthodes de formation conventionnelles pour privilégier un apprentissage contextuel, participatif et tourné vers l'avenir. En nous basant sur les défis actuels et les meilleures pratiques, voici quelques suggestions stratégiques pour améliorer votre établissement ou votre programme de formation : 1) Centrer la formation sur l'agriculteur et la rendre pertinente au niveau local ; 2) Utiliser un apprentissage pratique et basé sur la démonstration ; 3) Intégrer les outils numériques et les services climatiques ; 4) Inclure la connaissance

du climat et des systèmes ; 5) Renforcer les capacités institutionnelles et de vulgarisation ; 6) Établir des liens avec les marchés, la finance et les politiques.

MOTS CLÉS: formation, changements climatiques, agriculture, stratégies

INTRODUCTION

The study involved 42 randomly selected individuals. The interviewees are interested in the sustainable development of agriculture in a changing climate environment. The majority of them have participated in training related to the impact of climate change on agriculture and have plans to work in this sector of the economy.

Two criteria were used to determine the profile of the interviewees – current level of education and professional interest. According to the level of education, the largest share is held by those who study at a university, representing half of the respondents. These individuals undergo complex training and have diverse interests. The next largest group is those who study at vocational centers, with their share amounting to nearly 30%. Their interests are strictly specific and their training is aimed at solving specific problems in their professional field. The smallest group is the group of students, about 20%, representing the youngest part of society. Their opinion is important for how they see these problems even before they have encountered them professionally.

Depending on the professional field in which the respondents work or plan to work, the distribution of the respondents represents the structure of the agricultural sector in the Republic of Bulgaria. The largest share is that of those related to crop production, nearly 55%, which is the priority production at the national level. The second largest group is agribusiness representatives with nearly a quarter of those surveyed. These are individuals working in close relationships with agricultural producers and are suppliers of raw materials, equipment, and marketing intermediaries. Next is the group of representatives of mixed agriculture (crop and livestock farming) with about 12%. The smallest group is those specializing in livestock production, which are not preferred nationally.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

To analyze the current state of education on climate change-related topics, two criteria were used – the level of knowledge of climate threats and the quality of education on these topics. A five-point scale was used to assess them, with a higher score indicating a higher level of agreement on the part of the respondent. When asked about the level of knowledge of the problems arising from climate change, nearly 90% answered affirmatively, which is evident from the high scores they gave. This gives us reason to determine that the surveyed group has a competent opinion on the issues studied.

How aware are you feel about emerging climate threats (e.g., extreme weather events, new pests/diseases) that might affect future farmin...и), които могат да засегнат бъдещото земеделие?

42 отговора

Figure 1 Awareness of Climate Threats. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

Although almost all respondents stated that they are aware of the problems arising from climate change, it turns out that this understanding is not only a result of the training provided, as 1/3 of respondents rated with a neutral or lower degree the extent to which the training provided them with an understanding of the impact of climate crises on agriculture. The questions regarding the formation of practical skills and the focus of training on sustainable and adaptive agricultural methods show that nearly half of the trainees define their attendance as insufficient. Even more categorical are the results regarding the extent to which climate change training presents real-world examples of coping with and adapting to climate crises. Here, low levels of agreement prevail and the majority of trainees are not familiar with specific examples of practice that have shown success.

My training provides me with a strong understanding of climate crisis impacts on agriculture.

/ Моето обучение ми осигурява ясно разбиране...иматичните кризи върху селското стопанство.

42 отговора

Figure 2 Training Quality. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

My training includes practical skills to help address climate challenges in farming. / Моето обучение включва практически умения за справяне с климатичните предизвикателства в земеделието.
42 отговора

Figure 3 Training Quality. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

There is sufficient focus on sustainable and adaptive farming methods in my coursework. / Има достатъчен фокус върху методите на устойчиво земеделие в учебния курс в който участвам.
42 отговора

Figure 4 Training Quality. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

I believe that agricultural education includes enough real-world examples of adaptation to climate crisis. / Вярвам, че земеделското образование...имери за адаптиране към климатичните кризи.

42 отговора

Figure 5 Training Quality. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

All these findings also determine the relatively low level of confidence among learners that they are well prepared to deal with climate challenges. Apparently, the training they are participating in does not give them the necessary confidence to successfully solve climate crises, and out of 37 people who say they are aware of climate threats, only 24 believe they have the preparation to deal with the challenges arising from climate change.

I am confident that my education has prepared me to tackle climate-related agricultural challenges.

/ Убеден съм, че моето образование ме е подго...ата предизвикателства в селското стопанство.

42 отговора

Figure 6 Preparedness. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

The findings may explain the high level of interest in studying climate-resilient practices in agriculture, as well as the desire to participate in future educational courses on topics related to the climate resilience of agriculture.

I am interested in learning more about climate-resilient farming techniques. / Интересувам се да науча повече за устойчивите на климата земеделски техники.

42 отговора

Figure 7 Motivation to Learn. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

I would participate in additional training programs focused on climate resilience in agriculture. / Бих участвал в допълнителни програми за обучение...йчивостта на климата в селското стопанство.

42 отговора

Figure 8 Participation Interest. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

In the context of their training, trainees also determine the preparedness of their teachers on topics related to climate crises in agriculture. As the respondents are divided in half in their opinion. It is obvious that it is necessary to improve the preparation of the teachers themselves so that they can convincingly teach in this area.

My instructors/trainers are well-equipped to teach about climate crisis in agriculture. / Моите инструктори/обучители са добре подготвени да...за климатичните кризи в селското стопанство.
42 отговора

Figure 9 Instructor Preparedness. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

To assess preferences for future training and future needs, respondents answer questions related to the areas in which it is important to provide training and what forms of training are appropriate.

In the previous questions, answers were given about insufficient practical training on the topics of climate crises and the presentation of real examples from businesses for dealing with their negative impacts. Therefore, the main format that is preferred for training is conducting practical seminars or visits to real farms in which the effect of the applied good practices can be demonstrated. Online resources and the use of digital tools also report a high approval rate, with over 50% of respondents responding positively. There is the least interest in classroom training, which is natural given the subject matter studied.

When identifying the most important aspects that need to be given greater attention when it comes to developing climate-resilient agriculture with fewer negative impacts on the environment, respondents clearly prioritize maintaining soil health and implementing regenerative practices. And the area of Integration of renewable energy in agriculture is rated the lowest. Only two respondents have indicated this area as a priority. The answers given can be explained by the existing problems related to soil protection in Bulgaria and their use in a long-term perspective.

The need for training on specific topics has been assessed through possible options. The strongest interest is in topics related to Climate Adaptation Strategies (e.g. drought-resistant crops) followed by Precision Agriculture and Smart Technologies and Regenerative farming or nature-based solutions. All three topics are desired by more than half of the respondents to receive additional training. In the topic of Renewable Energy Integration, interest is significantly lower, as the result can be explained by the findings already made about the weaker interest in renewable energy in general in Bulgaria. Nearly half of respondents said that community-led policy frameworks and actions are an important part of building climate-resilient agriculture and would like to receive training on this topic.

Which formats do you find most effective for learning about climate-smart agriculture? (Please select all that apply.) / Кои формати намирате ... земеделие? (Моля, изберете всички приложими.)

42 отговора

Figure 10 Preferred Formats. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

What are the most important aspects that need to be addressed more closely when it comes to climate-resilient agriculture with less negative e...Моля, изберете 3-те, които смятате за най-важни.)

42 отговора

Figure 11 Important areas of education in climate-resilience agriculture. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

Which of the following areas would you like more in-depth training on? (Please select all that apply.) / В коя от следните области бихте иска... обучение? (Моля, изберете всички приложими.)

42 отговора

Figure 12 Training Needs. Source: Project - FarmFoward, 2025

To better prepare for climate-resilient agriculture learners stated that many training programs are missing key practical, systems-based, and future-focused skills and knowledge. What's lacking in Bulgaria, and why it matters:

1. Systems Thinking and Climate Risk Analysis. Low ability to connect climate trends (e.g. rainfall variability, heatwaves) to agricultural decision-making. Missing understanding of how climate risks intersect with markets, soil health, water, and livelihoods. It matters because a systems-thinking approach enables farmers and extension workers to shift from reactive responses—such as addressing crop failures after they occur—to proactive strategies, including diversification of crops and investment in water storage infrastructure. This transition is essential for building long-term resilience.

2. Data Interpretation and Use of Digital Tools. Missing skills to interpret weather forecasts, seasonal outlooks, or satellite data, use of mobile apps, GIS tools, or digital dashboards for farm-level decision-making. Although digital climate services are increasingly available, their effective utilization remains constrained by low digital literacy and the absence of locally contextualized training. Building capacity in data interpretation is fundamental to timely and informed decision-making at the farm level.

3. Climate-Smart Agribusiness and Finance. Missing knowledge of climate risk financing, insurance, and carbon credit markets. Missing skills in building business plans that integrate resilience (e.g. investing in water-saving tech or local seed systems). Financial literacy and risk management tools are prerequisites for scalable and sustainable adaptation. Without them, adoption of climate-resilient innovations often remains economically unfeasible.

4. Agroecology and Regenerative Practices. Lack of hands-on experience with intercropping, cover cropping, soil regeneration, and biodiversity management. Low understanding how these practices enhance resilience (e.g. through pest control, moisture retention, carbon storage). Agroecological and

regenerative practices offer low-cost, high-impact solutions for climate adaptation. However, their effectiveness is undermined when taught in abstract terms without practical demonstrations.

5. Climate and Environmental Policy Awareness. Low understanding how national climate policies, subsidies, or regulations affect farmers. Missing how to advocate for supportive policy change or navigate compliance (e.g. deforestation laws, carbon-farming schemes). Farmers are influenced by systems beyond the farm. Climate resilience depends not only on farm-level practices but also on navigating broader institutional and policy environments. Training programs must therefore equip participants to understand and influence these systemic factors.

Summary table 1: Top Missing Skills & Their Impact

Missing Skill/Knowledge	Impact if Addressed
Systems thinking & climate risk analysis	Smarter, long-term decision-making
Digital/data literacy	More precise, timely, and adaptive farm practices
Climate finance & agribusiness	Better investment and access to markets/insurance
Agroecological methods	Healthier soils, increased biodiversity, lower risk
Policy literacy	Empowerment and alignment with broader climate goals

Based on the research, the biggest obstacles to learning or adopting climate-smart farming techniques tend to fall into six core categories. Here’s the most common barriers in Bulgaria and why they persist:

1. Lack of Local Relevance or Evidence. Climate-smart techniques promoted in one region may not work elsewhere without adaptation. If farmers don’t see clear benefits—especially in the short term—they are unlikely to change practices. Pilot fatigue: Farmers are often "tested on" by short-term projects that disappear without scale-up. Farmers adopt what they trust — often based on peer experience, not outside claims.

2. Limited Access to Resources. Farmers often can’t access drought-tolerant seeds, organic fertilizers, or equipment needed for new practices. High costs and lack of affordable loans or insurance discourage farmers from experimenting with new approaches. Many rural farmers don’t receive timely, localized, or actionable climate-smart advice.

Even when knowledge is available, adoption stalls without the physical means to implement it.

3. Risk Aversion and Uncertainty. Farmers often avoid change because new techniques carry unpredictable short-term results. Climate impacts make it harder to predict success of any one technique in a given season. Without safety nets (like insurance), the cost of failure is too high.

Adaptation requires experimentation and confidence — both are hindered by economic vulnerability.

4. Training Gaps and Ineffective Extension Services. Many training programs are too technical, top-down, or not tailored to local contexts. Limited follow-up or on-farm demonstrations means

knowledge isn't retained or put into practice. Some farmers lack basic literacy or digital skills, limiting access to mobile tools or apps.

Training must be hands-on, iterative, and embedded in community practices to succeed.

5. Cultural and Social Norms. Long-standing traditions can conflict with recommended practices, like shifting planting calendars or diversifying away from staple crops. Youth may be excluded from leadership or decision-making, despite being key adopters of innovation.

Ignoring social dynamics limits who adopts climate-smart farming and how quickly.

6. Weak Policy and Market Signals. Government subsidies often still favor unsustainable practices (e.g., chemical inputs, water-intensive crops). Market demand for climate-smart products (like organic produce or carbon-sequestering grains) may be underdeveloped. Lack of infrastructure (like cold storage, processing units) discourages adoption of value-added practices.

Without policy and market support, farmers have few incentives to change.

In 5 to 10 years, many learners in climate-smart agriculture envision themselves in roles that combine practical application, advocacy, and innovation. Here are main directions one might pursue:

1. Managing or Supporting a Sustainable Farm. The goal is to operate or advise a farm that uses regenerative, agroecological, or permaculture techniques. They will manage soil health, carbon sequestration, water efficiency, local food systems. Hands-on work allows you to directly apply and adapt climate-smart techniques while contributing to food security and environmental restoration.

Summary Table 2. Obstacles and impact

Obstacle	Impact on Adoption
Techniques not locally adapted	Low trust and poor performance reduce uptake
Limited access to inputs & finance	Farmers can't afford or source needed tools
Risk aversion & lack of safety nets	Fear of failure prevents experimentation
Poor training & extension delivery	Skills don't stick; info isn't acted upon
Cultural and social norms	Limits participation and leadership in adaptation
Weak enabling environment (policy/market)	No long-term incentives to stay with smart practices

2. Pursuing Advanced Research or Education. Conduction of research on climate-resilient crops, low-emission practices, or climate modeling for agriculture. Science and innovation drive scalable solutions and influence policy.

3. Becoming an Advocate or Educator. They want to promote sustainable farming practices, influence policy, or empower communities through training. They will work on farmer education, policy lobbying, communication campaigns. Change happens when people are informed, mobilized, and equipped with the right tools.

4. Building or Leading an Agritech or Climate-Adaptation Enterprise. They will develop technology or services that support climate-smart agriculture (e.g., weather tools, soil sensors, carbon marketplaces). The focus areas are innovation and digital agriculture. Scalable solutions require entrepreneurial thinking and tech-savvy leadership.

5. Influencing Climate and Agricultural Policy. To shape regional or national climate adaptation strategies and agricultural reforms. Focus areas: Policy design, subsidy reform, adaptation finance, global food systems. Enabling environments are critical to scale climate-smart practices beyond pilot programs.

CONCLUSION

Improving climate-related agricultural education requires moving beyond conventional training methods toward context-driven, participatory, and future-ready learning. Based on current challenges and best practices, here are strategic suggestions for enhancing your institution or training program:

1. Make Training Farmer-Centered and Locally Relevant. Conduct needs assessments with local farmers to tailor content to real-world challenges. Use local case studies, languages, and agroecological examples. Focus on what farmers can do now, not just theoretical knowledge.

This helps because relevance increases engagement, retention, and adoption of new practices.

2. Use Hands-On, Demonstration-Based Learning. Establish field schools, demo plots, or climate-smart pilot farms where trainees can see results in action. Use “learn by doing” methods: composting, water harvesting, seed treatment, or using weather tools on-site. Incorporate peer-to-peer training, where farmers who’ve adopted practices train others.

This helps to build confidence, shows proof of concept, and reinforces retention.

3. Integrate Digital Tools and Climate Services. Train farmers and extension agents to use weather apps, satellite imagery, and SMS advisory platforms. Provide tablets or phones to community trainers if infrastructure allows. Include digital literacy modules, especially for youth and women.

This strengthens real-time decision-making, especially under variable conditions.

4. Include Climate Literacy and Systems Thinking. Teach basic climate science and its agricultural impacts (e.g., rainfall shifts, heat stress). Introduce resilience thinking — focusing on risk reduction, diversity, and recovery. Use scenario planning tools to help farmers anticipate and adapt to different futures.

This builds long-term, adaptive mindsets rather than short-term fixes.

5. Strengthen Institutional and Extension Capacity. Train trainers and extension staff in climate-smart principles, participatory methods, and facilitation. Provide ongoing refresher courses, field visits, and resource materials. Create incentives for trainers to experiment and improve.

This helps because the quality of teaching often determines success more than curriculum alone.

6. Link to Markets, Finance, and Policy. Teach how climate-smart practices can meet certification, quality, or export standards. Incorporate modules on microfinance, insurance, and business planning. Update trainees on climate-related agricultural policies and subsidy reforms.

Farmers need both knowledge and incentives to adopt and sustain change.

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IMPORTANCE AND POTENTIAL BENEFITS OF BIO-BASED TOURISM IN THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this article is to analyse the importance and potential benefits of bio-based tourism in the Republic of Serbia. Bio-based tourism typically refers to biodiversity-based tourism, also known as biocentric tourism, which centres on natural ecosystems, wildlife, and conservation. The Republic of Serbia, with its diverse geography ranging from plains in the north to mountains in the south and east, offers significant potential for this kind of tourism. Importance of this kind of tourism are numerous (such as environmental conservation; preservation of natural habitats, wildlife, and biodiversity; generates funds for protected areas and conservation programs through tourism revenues; sustainable economic development; alternative income sources to rural and indigenous communities; reducing reliance on environmentally harmful industries; supports small-scale, eco-friendly businesses like organic farms, lodges, and nature guides; cultural preservation; promotes respect for local traditions, customs, and knowledge systems; helps revitalize traditional practices like herbal medicine, sustainable farming, and wildlife tracking; education and awareness; informs travelers about ecological balance, endangered species, and conservation challenges; inspires more sustainable lifestyles among visitors and hosts; climate action; reduces tourism's carbon). Potential benefits can be seen in all aspects, particularly in environmental, economic, social, cultural, and educational areas.

KEYWORDS: bio-tourism; biodiversity-based tourism; sustainable tourism; environment

ABSTRAKT

Ziel dieses Artikels ist es, die Bedeutung und den potenziellen Nutzen des biobasierten Tourismus in der Republik Serbien zu analysieren. Der biobasierte Tourismus bezieht sich in der Regel auf einen auf der biologischen Vielfalt basierenden Tourismus, auch bekannt als biozentrischer Tourismus, der sich auf natürliche Ökosysteme, Wildtiere und deren Erhaltung konzentriert. Die Republik Serbien mit ihrer vielfältigen Geographie, die von den Ebenen im Norden bis zu den Bergen im Süden und Osten reicht, bietet ein großes Potenzial für diese Art von Tourismus. Die Bedeutung dieser Art von Tourismus ist zahlreich (z. B. Umweltschutz; Erhaltung natürlicher Lebensräume, der Tierwelt und der biologischen Vielfalt; Generierung von Mitteln für Schutzgebiete und Naturschutzprogramme durch Einnahmen aus dem Tourismus; nachhaltige wirtschaftliche Entwicklung; alternative Einkommensquellen für ländliche und indigene Gemeinschaften; Verringerung der Abhängigkeit von umweltschädlichen Industrien; Unterstützung kleiner, umweltfreundlicher Unternehmen wie Bio-Bauernhöfe, Lodges und Naturführer; Erhaltung der Kultur; Förderung des Respekts für lokale Traditionen, Bräuche und Wissenssysteme; Wiederbelebung traditioneller Praktiken wie Kräutermedizin, nachhaltige Landwirtschaft und Wildtierbeobachtung; Bildung und Bewusstseinsbildung; Information der Reisenden über das ökologische Gleichgewicht, gefährdete Arten und die Herausforderungen des Naturschutzes; Anregung eines

nachhaltigeren Lebensstils bei Besuchern und Gastgebern; Klimaschutz; Verringerung des Kohlenstoffausstoßes des Tourismus).

STICHWORTE: Biotourismus; biodiversitätsbasierter Tourismus; nachhaltiger Tourismus; Umwelt

RÉSUMÉ

L'objectif de cet article est d'analyser l'importance et les avantages potentiels du tourisme biologique en République de Serbie. Le tourisme biologique fait généralement référence au tourisme basé sur la biodiversité, également connu sous le nom de tourisme biocentrique, qui se concentre sur les écosystèmes naturels, la faune et la flore et la conservation. La République de Serbie, avec sa géographie diversifiée allant des plaines au nord aux montagnes au sud et à l'est, offre un potentiel important pour ce type de tourisme. Les avantages de ce type de tourisme sont nombreux (conservation de l'environnement, préservation des habitats naturels, de la faune et de la biodiversité, financement des zones protégées et des programmes de conservation grâce aux revenus du tourisme, développement économique durable, sources de revenus alternatives pour les communautés rurales et indigènes, réduction de la dépendance à l'égard des industries nuisibles à l'environnement, soutien des petites entreprises respectueuses de l'environnement telles que les fermes biologiques, les gîtes et les guides de la nature); préservation culturelle ; promotion du respect des traditions, des coutumes et des systèmes de connaissances locaux aide à revitaliser les pratiques traditionnelles telles que la phytothérapie, l'agriculture durable et le suivi des animaux sauvages; éducation et sensibilisation; information des voyageurs sur l'équilibre écologique, les espèces menacées et les défis en matière de conservation; incitation des visiteurs et des hôtes à adopter des modes de vie plus durables ; action en faveur du climat; réduction des émissions de carbone dues au tourisme.)

MOTS-CLÉS: bio-tourisme; tourisme basé sur la biodiversité; tourisme durable; environnement

INTRODUCTION

Recently, there has been growing discussion about how to ensure the long-term sustainability of humanity within the biosphere, as rapid global development has significantly impacted environmental quality and led to widespread degradation. Issues such as climate change, natural disasters, resource depletion, and environmental degradation are among the pressing challenges currently confronting humanity (Hakim and Nakagoshi, 2008).

The tourism industry is essential in the world because it is an industry that can generate employment, generate income in foreign currency, and help propel the economy of the country (Lew,

Hall and Timothy, 2008). In recent years, with increasing awareness of environmental pollution, alternative ways and approaches have begun to be considered to preserve what remains of natural resources and reduce further destruction, if not halt it. When it comes to tourism, the most widespread mass tourism actually hides many negative factors behind the beautiful accommodations and destinations that tourists see - from the enormous waste and pollution it leaves behind, the lack of care for the protection of nature and its preservation, to the fact that the money that tourists spent on those famous world hotel chains generally does not stay at that location, for those locals. Bio-diversity based tourism

is a form of tourism receiving attention today because it recognises the importance of managing sustainable tourism by changing the management perspective from product tourism to the value of tourism, focusing on balancing tourism growth that creates a stable culture, prosperous tourism economy and sustainable natural resources by conserving nature, protect the environment and strengthen the ecosystem (Udomraksau et al., 2021).

In this brief study, an attempt will be made to analyse the importance and list the potential benefits of bio-based tourism in the Republic of Serbia.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Tourism is a typical example of the modern industry's tendency in society to separate different aspects of human life by space and time - vacationers, specific orders for the purchase of other homes, as well as free time and holidays. These specific places and periods are connected through vast communication networks, which, together with various social, cultural, economic, and environmental issues, make tourism one of the most significant challenges for sustainable development (Gossling and Hultman, 2006).

The Republic of Serbia is located in the southeastern part of Europe. Although it is not as popular among tourists as some of its neighbouring countries, it has considerable potential to change that. Tourism in Serbia is currently not at an enviable level, although this may change in the future. Some of the main **tourist attractions in Serbia** would be the following:

- Rich Cultural Heritage: With its long and complex history, Serbia offers numerous historical landmarks, including ancient fortresses, monasteries, and archaeological sites that reflect its diverse cultural past.

- Stunning Natural Landscapes: The country is known for its scenic beauty, featuring picturesque mountains, rivers, and lakes ideal for nature lovers.

- Orthodox Monasteries: Serbia's strong Orthodox Christian heritage is evident in its many monasteries, such as Studenica Monastery, Zica Monastery, and Mileseva Monastery. These are not only places of worship but also architectural and artistic masterpieces.

- Spa and Wellness Tourism: Serbia is famous for its natural thermal springs and healing spa resorts, with Vrnjacka Banja and Sokobanja being among the most popular destinations.

- The Capital: Belgrade blends historical charm with modern vibrancy. Visitors can explore ancient sites while enjoying a lively nightlife scene, diverse gastronomy, and a range of cultural events.

- Festivals and Cultural Events: Serbia hosts numerous international and local festivals. The EXIT Festival in Novi Sad is one of Europe's largest music festivals, attracting visitors from around the world.

- Wine and gastronomy: Serbian food reflects a mix of cultural influences, with popular dishes like cevapi and sarma. The country's wine industry is emerging and offers growing interest for wine enthusiasts.

- Adventure and outdoor Activities: Serbia's natural terrain offers excellent opportunities for outdoor adventures such as hiking, rafting, and cycling. The Iron Gate gorge on the Danube River is a standout destination for thrill-seekers and nature explorers (Milojevic Jelisijevic and Hussain, 2023).

Serbia's intangible cultural heritage encompasses renowned cheeses and other specialities from Eastern Serbia, the traditional distillation of rakija, as well as the preparation of jams and sweets. It also

encompasses crafts like the weaving of the famous Pirot rugs, as well as traditional folk music, folklore, customs, and beliefs. (Devic, 2011)

Key aspects of bio-based tourism in the Republic of Serbia would be:

- National parks and protected areas
- Wildlife watching and bird watching
- Eco-lodging and rural tourism
- Sustainable agriculture and herbal tourism
- Educational and voluntourism opportunities.

There are currently seven **national parks** in the Republic of Serbia.

Nm br.	PROTECTED AREA	YEAR OF NOMINAT.	TYPE	MUNICIPALITY (CITY)	SURFACE (ha)
1	National park Fruska Gora	1960	National park	Backa Palanka, Beocin, Indjija, Irig, Sremska Mitrovica, Novi Sad, Sid, Sremski Karlovci	26,672
2	National park Djerdap	1974	National park	Majdanpek, Kladovo, Golubac	63,786
3	National park Sar Planina	1986	National park	Strpce, Prizren, Suva Reka, Kačanik (KiM)	22,805
4	National park Tara	1981	National park	Bajina Basta	24,989
5	National park Kopaonik	1981	National park	Raska, Brus	11,969
6	National park Stara Planina	2022/2023*	National park	Zajecar, Knjazevac, Pirot, Dimitrovgrad	114,322
7	National park Kucaj, Beljanica	2022/2023*	National park	Zagubica, Boljevac, Despotovac, gr. Bor	45,372
Total area of National parks					308,731

Table 1. National parks of the Republic of Serbia (created by Author)

Image 1. Map of Serbia with locations of National parks (created by author)

Fruska Gora: The most significant natural values are the deciduous forests of cypress, hornbeam and beech, and fragmentary areas of steppe vegetation. The most significant cultural and historical heritage is represented by 16 monasteries built at the end of the 15th and the beginning of the 16th century, which are important for the development and preservation of Serbian culture (Serbian Holy Mountain).

Djerdap: Its most excellent natural values are mixed deciduous rainforests (including walnut, hazel, nettle, and beech), and widespread lilac thickets. The limestone cliffs are the habitat of rare plants from ancient times, while the river course of the Danube in this part is inhabited by ancient species of fish (sturgeon and moruna). The cultural-historical heritage is also rich, with the sites of (fragmentary) old Roman bridges and roads (Dachia Ripensis), Trajan's Tablet (following to the place where the Trajan's Bridge was located), and an ancient settlement with a rich archaeological site, Lepenski Vir, etc.

Tara: The most significant natural values of the area of Mount Tara are the unique Pančić spruce forests, the beech, fir and spruce rainforests, as well as the tresava surrounded by the Pančić spruce forest. The abundance of water (springs and lakes) and the diverse presence of animal life are its exceptional values.

Kopaonik: Its main wealth consists of mixed forests of spruce, fir, beech and maple with special biocenoses of old "Balkan taigas", ancient spruce forests, subalpine communities of dwarf spruce and fallen juniper, as well as limestone cliffs that are the habitat of rare plants such as eelgrass. Here, too, some bogs host many old plant species. Many rivers spring from this great mountain, and its highest elevation is Pančićev vrh, which stands at 2017 meters above sea level.

Sar Mountain: The most significant natural values of the area of Sar Mountain are molica and munika forests, as well as mixed deciduous forests, which represent the primary habitat of the strong autochthonous Balkan lynx. Glacier cirques with glacial lakes are often found on this mountain.

Stara Planina: Stara Planina belongs to the massif of the Carpathian-Balkan Mountains and extends over the territories of Serbia and Bulgaria, framed by the rich river watercourses of the White and Timok rivers, as well as the Temstica, Temska, and Nisava. Rich and dense forests, along with frequent springs, give this mountain a unique character, dominated by the peaks of Babin Zub and Midzor. The most significant natural values are the localities of Janosica, Orlov-Hajducki kamen, Golema reka-Dupljak, Babin zub, Martiniva cuka-Vrazja glava-Tri cuka, Bratkova strana, Koprena plateau and Tupanac-Srebrna glava. At the same time, this is the mountain with the highest peaks in Serbia.

Kučaj, Beljanica: This national park is bordered by Beljanica mountain, Kučaj mountain, Bor-Zajecar depression and Velika Morava. The most significant natural values of the area, thanks to the specific geological base and climate, are numerous habitats of rare and endangered plant species. The area of the protected area is considered one of the most forested parts of the Balkans (therefore the least inhabited by humans), where forests of a rainforest character, such as Vinatovaca and Busovata, also occupy a part. In addition to rich bird habitats (130 species), the reserve is also extremely rich in mammal fauna, many of which are on the verge of extinction (lynx, otter, brown bear and wolf), and it also abounds with over 150 speleological objects, as well as karst springs, sinkholes, waterfalls and waterfalls.

All these national parks are a great asset of the Republic of Serbia. They have in common, unfortunately, that the letter of the law, at least in this period of the Republic of Serbia's existence, has

difficulty reaching the shadows of forested areas, so villages are systematically devastated, families with a traditional way of life are economically exhausted and forced to new ways of survival, the construction of new non-ecological facilities covers ever larger areas, forests are ruthlessly cut down (even for export to countries that are much richer in these resources than we are), and nature (both water and air and soil) are becoming more and more polluted every day. Usually, each source has its natural capacities, and the enormous increase in housing units in "protected areas" leads to the overstrain and collapse of those natural gifts of essential importance to man.

There are 25 **nature parks** in the Republic of Serbia.

Nm br.	NATURE PARK	Municipality (City)	Surface (ha)	Year of nomination
1	Panonija	Backa Topola	-	1975
2	Grmija	Pristina	1,167.94	1987
3	Begečka jama	Novi Sad	489.50	1999
4	Sicevačka klisura	Nis, Bela Palanka	7,746.00	1977
5	Golija	Ivanjica, Kraljevo, Raska, Novi Pazar, Sjenica	75,183.00	2001
6	Kamaras	Kanjiza	267.96	2005
7	Sargan – Mokra gora	Uzice, Cajetina, Bajina Basta	10,813.73	2005
8	Jegricka	Backa Palanka, Vrbas, Temerin, Zabalj	1,993.19	2005
9	Stara Tisa kod Bisernog ostrva	Novi Becej, Zabalj, Becej	959.69	2008
10	Beljanska bara	Srbobran, Becej	173.12	2013
11	Palic	Subotica	712.36	1982
12	Rusanda	Zrenjanin-Novi Becej	1,159.98	2014
13	Ponjavica	Pancevo	302.96	1995
14	Tikvara	Backa Palanka	554.52	1997
15	Radan	Kursumlija, Bojnik, Lebane, Prokuplje, Medvedja	43,512.72	2017
16	Zlatibor	Cajetina, Nova Varos, Uzice, Priboj	41,923.26	2017
17	Backotopolske doline	Backa Topola	522.52	2017
18	Mrtvaje Gornjeg Potisja	Coka, Kikinda, Senta	304.77	2023
19	Slatina (u dolini Zlatice)	Coka, Kikinda	3,640.60	2023
20	Mli Bosut	Sid	282.34	2024
21	Poloj	Beocin, Backa Palanka, Novi Sad	2,064.88	U post.
22	Mojstirsko-draske planine	Tutin	10,822.36	U post.
23	Bukinski hrastnik	Backa Palanka	304.98	U post.
24	Zobnatica	Backa Topola	30.08	1976
25	Veliki Jastrebac	Krusevac, Pokuplje, Blace, Aleksinac	39,175.76	2024

Table 2. Nature parks of the Republic of Serbia (created by author)

All these places are extremely valuable natural monuments and a key to understanding the origin of Serbia's current appearance, and their preservation is of immense importance. In this regard, state authorities and strict enforcement of existing laws play a crucial role.

Image 2. Map of Serbia with locations of nature parks (created by author)

The awareness and culture of mountaineers, adventurers, hunting groups, and other curious visitors to these natural oases will continue to influence the preservation of this heritage.

With its exceptional values, the wealth of forests and vegetation, especially climatological, due to the constant collision of the continental and the sea (Mediterranean), the Zlatibor mountain deserves special attention and protection, but non-implementation of the regulations has influenced the fact that thousands of cubic meters of concrete were poured in the very heart of the area, whole rows of buildings and streets were erected, rough infrastructures were built and pushed deeper and further from that freak city and flora and fauna, which very quickly depleted the living mountain watercourses and destroyed the air. Golija, Pesterska Visoravan, Uvac, Ovcarsko-Kablarska Klisura and many other sights of Serbia are also under similar attacks.

Wildlife watching and birdwatching in Serbia offer unique experiences at sites like Deliblato Sands—the largest continental sand desert in Europe and home to endangered species such as the imperial eagle—Obedska Bara and Zasavica Special Nature Reserves, which are rich wetland habitats ideal for birdwatching, and the Uvac Special Nature Reserve, renowned for its thriving population of griffon vultures.

Eco-lodging and rural tourism are on the rise in Western and Southern Serbia, with the development of eco-villages, sustainable guesthouses, and rural homestays, including notable examples such as the Gostoljublje Ethno Village, eco-cottages in Zlatibor, and guest farms on Stara Planina.

Sustainable agriculture and herbal tourism are increasingly popular in Serbia, where villages often combine organic farming, medicinal herb picking, and forest foraging into authentic tourism experiences, particularly in the Pannonian Plain and the Homolje mountains.

Educational and voluntourism opportunities in Serbia include projects that engage tourists in activities such as reforestation, wildlife tracking, and organic gardening, often in collaboration with NGOs dedicated to conservation and sustainable development.

The importance OF BIO-BASED TOURISM is very significant. Some of the main points would be:

1. Environmental Conservation

Bio-based tourism encourages the preservation of natural habitats, wildlife, and biodiversity, while also generating funds for protected areas and conservation programs through tourism revenues.

1. Sustainable Economic Development

Bio-based tourism provides alternative income sources for rural and indigenous communities, reducing their reliance on environmentally harmful industries like logging and mining, while supporting small-scale, eco-friendly businesses such as organic farms, lodges, and nature guides.

1. Cultural Preservation

Bio-based tourism promotes respect for local traditions, customs, and knowledge systems—particularly those connected to biodiversity and environmental stewardship—while helping to revitalise traditional practices such as herbal medicine, sustainable farming, and wildlife tracking.

1. Education and Awareness

Bio-based tourism informs travellers about ecological balance, endangered species, and conservation challenges, inspiring more sustainable lifestyles among both visitors and hosts.

1. Climate Action

Bio-based tourism reduces the carbon footprint of travel by emphasising local, low-impact transportation and bio-based infrastructure—such as eco-lodges made from renewable materials—while encouraging reforestation, habitat restoration, and carbon offset programs.

POTENTIAL BENEFITS OF BIO-BASED TOURISM can be:

1. Environmental

Bio-based tourism preserves biodiversity and ecosystems, minimises waste and pollution, and promotes rewilding and the protection of native species.

1. Economic

Bio-based tourism boosts local employment and income, stimulates demand for locally produced organic products and crafts, and attracts eco-conscious investors and donors.

1. Social/Cultural

Bio-based tourism fosters community pride and cultural exchange, reinforces traditional ecological knowledge, and empowers women and marginalised groups in the tourism sector.

1. Educational

Bio-based tourism offers hands-on learning opportunities, facilitates research and citizen science, and fosters environmental leadership among young people.

It would be desirable for the tourism industry to transform by changing the current practices that promote the continuous consumption of resources to a model that favours the decarbonization of transport systems and eco-tourism (Galanakis et al., 2022).

Some of the **challenges for developing bio-based tourism in the Republic of Serbia** could be:

- Lack of infrastructure: Rural and protected areas in Serbia face poor transportation and accommodation options, along with limited access to certain nature reserves and eco-tourism sites.

- Weak promotion and branding: Serbia's biodiversity and eco-tourism offerings are not well known internationally due to an insufficient digital presence and a lack of targeted marketing aimed at eco-tourists.

- Limited training and expertise: Many local tourism operators lack training in sustainable practices and eco-tourism service delivery, highlighting the need for capacity-building programs in rural and protected regions.

- Environmental threats: Illegal logging, pollution, and unregulated construction pose significant threats to natural habitats, making it essential to manage tourism carefully to prevent further environmental degradation.

- Underdeveloped legal and policy framework: The lack of integrated policies supporting sustainable tourism at both national and local levels, combined with weak enforcement of environmental protection laws, hinders effective conservation and eco-tourism development.

- Short tourist season: Many biodiversity-based activities, such as bird migrations and wildflower blooms, are seasonal, and there are limited indoor or off-season bio-tourism options available to maintain visitor engagement year-round.

CONCLUSION

The industrialisation period undeniably comes with side effects. The expanding fossil-based economy is creating local and global environmental and social problems, including climate change,

biodiversity loss, pollution, and geopolitical tension (Bennich and Belyazid, 2017). Tourism expansion has led to increased generation of municipal solid waste (MSW), which can exacerbate environmental and societal problems if proper waste management systems are not implemented (Sakcharoen et al., 2023).

The Republic of Serbia holds significant potential for bio-based tourism, thanks to its abundant natural resources and rich biodiversity, including mountains, forests, rivers, spas, and diverse cultural and historical landmarks. Creating tourism offerings centred on these assets, guided by a unified vision, represents an important economic and social opportunity for the country.

Bio-based tourism should be considered the future of tourism because it prioritises the sustainable use of natural resources and biodiversity, ensuring that ecosystems are preserved for future generations. Unlike traditional mass tourism, it minimises environmental impact by promoting low-impact travel, supports local communities economically and culturally, and fosters a deeper connection between travellers and nature. As global awareness of climate change, habitat loss, and cultural preservation grows, bio-based tourism offers a responsible way to explore the world while protecting the planet and empowering local people, making it essential for the future of travel. The Republic of Serbia has enormous potential and should consider developing a bio-based tourism sector.

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SATISFACTION OF THE STUDENTS FROM LEVEL OF DIGITALIZATION OF STUDENT SERVICES - CASE STUDY AAB COLLEGE

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ABSTRACT

The future of digital student services offers numerous chances to improve the quality and efficiency of higher education. Universities that invest in cutting-edge technology will be better able to recruit students and provide a more individualized educational experience. The main purpose of this research is assessing the degree of student satisfaction with digital student services offered by higher education institution AAB College. Deeper comprehension of the elements influencing students' perceptions and experiences with these services will be made possible by this study, which will also assist in identifying areas that could use improvement. With the aim to measure student satisfaction and perceptions, the study will employ an online questionnaire with closed-ended questions that will ask about things like the quality of technical support, accessibility to services, and ease of use of digital platforms. The information gathered from the interviews will be coded and categorized based on key themes in order to extract broad trends and student perceptions of digital services.

KEYWORDS: Students, Digitalization, Student Services, University, Higher education

ABSTRAKT

Die Zukunft digitaler Studierendendienste bietet zahlreiche Chancen zur Verbesserung der Qualität und Effizienz der Hochschulbildung. Hochschulen, die in Spitzentechnologie investieren, werden besser in der Lage sein, Studierende zu rekrutieren und eine individuellere Bildungserfahrung zu bieten. Der Hauptzweck dieser Untersuchung ist die Bewertung des Grades der Zufriedenheit der Studierenden mit den von der Hochschuleinrichtung AAB College angebotenen digitalen Dienstleistungen für Studierende. Diese Studie wird ein tieferes Verständnis der Elemente ermöglichen, die die Wahrnehmung und die Erfahrungen der Studierenden mit diesen Dienstleistungen beeinflussen, und sie wird auch dabei helfen, Bereiche zu identifizieren, die verbessert werden könnten. Um die Zufriedenheit und die Wahrnehmung der Studierenden zu messen, wird die Studie einen Online-Fragebogen mit geschlossenen Fragen verwenden, in denen u. a. nach der Qualität des technischen Supports, der Zugänglichkeit der Dienste und der Benutzerfreundlichkeit der digitalen Plattformen gefragt wird. Die in den Interviews gesammelten Informationen werden kodiert und anhand von Schlüsselthemen kategorisiert, um allgemeine Trends und die Wahrnehmung digitaler Dienste durch die Studierenden zu ermitteln

STICHWORTE: tudenten, Digitalisierung, Studentische Dienstleistungen, Universität, Hochschulbildung.

RÉSUMÉ

L'avenir des services numériques aux étudiants offre de nombreuses possibilités d'améliorer la qualité et l'efficacité de l'enseignement supérieur. Les universités qui investissent dans les technologies de pointe seront mieux à même de recruter des étudiants et d'offrir une expérience éducative plus personnalisée. L'objectif principal de cette recherche est d'évaluer le degré de satisfaction des étudiants à l'égard des services numériques offerts par l'établissement d'enseignement supérieur AAB College. Cette étude permettra d'approfondir la compréhension des éléments qui influencent les perceptions et les expériences des étudiants avec ces services, ce qui aidera également à identifier les domaines qui pourraient être améliorés. Afin de mesurer la satisfaction et les perceptions des étudiants, l'étude utilisera un questionnaire en ligne avec des questions fermées qui porteront sur des éléments tels que la qualité de l'assistance technique, l'accessibilité aux services et la facilité d'utilisation des plateformes numériques. Les informations recueillies lors des entretiens seront codées et classées en fonction de thèmes clés afin d'extraire les grandes tendances et les perceptions des étudiants à l'égard des services numériques.

MOTS-CLÉS: étudiants, numérisation, services aux étudiants, université, enseignement supérieur

INTRODUCTION

One essential step in raising the effectiveness of higher education institutions and enhancing the student experience is the digitization of student services. Personalized academic and administrative support, easier access to information and services, and the automation and optimization of administrative procedures are all included. The paper provides a comprehensive analysis of the literature that shows the essence and directions of digital technology management, as well as the fundamentals of consumer behavior among digital users.

In order to gauge student satisfaction with the degree of digitization of student services in higher education institutions, this research combines a quantitative and qualitative methodology. Data collecting, sample selection, and result analysis are some of the phases that make up the approach. The purpose of this descriptive and exploratory study is to determine how satisfied AAB College students are with digital services, examine the variables that affect their satisfaction, and assess how effective digital services are in comparison to more conventional approaches. With the aim to measure student satisfaction and perceptions, the study used an online questionnaire with closed-ended questions that asked about things such as the quality of technical support, access to services, and ease of use of digital platforms, distributed to a sample of 243 students. The information gathered from the interviews will be coded and categorized based on key themes in order to extract broad trends and student perceptions of digital services.

The digitalization of higher education services along the student life cycle is a central task that must be tackled by considering both internal aspects of higher education as well as those of digital networking and the law (Harald Gilch; Inga Gerling; Friedrich Stratmann, 2023). The development of the educational services market takes place in the whole world under the influence of innovation technological and organizational solutions. The use of online technology provides a wide space for developing cooperation between educational institutions not only when mastering current disciplines. This is possible thanks to the modern concept of education being aimed at the possibility of students to choose a number of disciplines of various types based on their own preferences. (A A Fedotov; O V Pilipenko; L V Panfilova; L N Borisoglebskaya, 2020). This suggests that organizational and technological improvements have an impact on how the market for educational services develops. Though the use of

digital assets enhances the students' learning experience and offers new opportunities for administration, there are no uniform standards for the use of digital media in teaching and student services. As educational service providers, universities are dependent on students being able to cope with the structures offered. Thus, it is essential to ascertain students' attitudes of the technologies used (Henning Brink; Sven Packmohr; Kristin Vogelsang, 2020). To the degree that, although the use of digital technologies enhances academic management and the learning process, there are no consistent criteria for their application. Universities must take into account the attitudes and technological adaptation skills of their pupils. The academic sector within universities must be willing to consider the mutual recognition of achievements and acquired competencies as the normality, and to ensure that the recognition process is transparent (Harald Gilch; Inga Gerling; Friedrich Stratmann, 2023). Universities and institutions of higher learning have evolved into technological hubs, developing and delivering skills for the future. The operations and systems together with workflows of delivery at a tertiary institution should be modified to deliver services and a product that is 4IR savvy, more importantly, the systems and processes must be 4IR enabled so as to deliver a seamless, efficient, smart digital experience (Telukdarie, A., & Munsamy, M., 2019). In line with this, in order to create new capabilities, higher education institutions are becoming technology hubs. Higher education has to develop personal and professional competences of students and to improve their knowledge and skills as well as their sense of civic engagement and understanding of cultural and social issue (Selmo, 2020). Digital Technology has changed the education scenario in the educational institutions by enhancing teaching and learning, research and governance. There is great need of adequate infrastructure, better internet connectivity, up to date digital equipment's, safe platform and digitally competent professionals. In India, higher education institution is evident with the increasing use of ICT, cloud computing, artificial intelligence, robotics and virtual reality in day-to-day practices which enhances competencies and help in aligning with industry based skills (Shailaj Kumar Shrivastava; Chandan Shrivastava, 2022). However, there is a pressing need to enhance digital gadgets, professional competencies, internet connectivity, and infrastructure. The process of digitalization challenges universities worldwide, in particular the universities' IT (Anne Thoring; Dominik Rudolph; Raimund Vogl, 2017). Universities all over the world face difficulties as a result of the digitalization process, particularly their IT departments. The global unification of markets and improved access to information has facilitated enhanced communication and more tailored marketing strategies. Innovative technologies have minimized the necessity for repetitive tasks and heightened the emphasis on analytical and creative abilities. (Süssmann, 2021)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Evaluating the graphical information, the majority of students demonstrate a strong degree of contentment with digital services. The graph indicates the level of student satisfaction with the college's digital services. This shows that, although their experience was not offensive, but there is still an opportunity for improvement that could raise overall satisfaction.

How satisfied are you with the digital services provided by the College?

1.Graphic I

2. Student satisfaction with digital services is greatly impacted by elements including speed, ease of use, technical support quality, and round-the-clock accessibility. The information displayed in the graph illustrates the key elements that affect student satisfaction regarding online learning resources, utilizing a scale ranging from 1 (minimum satisfaction) to 5 (maximum satisfaction). The customization of services based on student needs has garnered a diverse range of evaluations, showing that for certain students, this is an aspect where enhancements are possible.

What are the main determinants of satisfaction with online learning resources?

(Explanation: No. 1 is the lowest of satisfaction level and No. 5 is the highest level of satisfaction)

2.Graphic II

3. The data presented in the graph illustrates the social media platforms that students most frequently use to interact with the university. The findings show distinct variations in students' preferences for different platforms, highlighting trends and areas for improvement in the university's digital communication approaches. Instagram is the most popular platform for interacting with the university. The highest rating category (5) prevails for Instagram, indicating that students favor this platform for gathering information or interacting with the educational institution. Facebook and WhatsApp continue to be important platforms for communication, while the use of Viber and LinkedIn is less widespread, although still important.

What social media platforms do you frequently use to connect with the university?

3.Graphic III

4. According to the faculty, degree of study, and extent of usage of technology for academic purposes, there are notable variations in student satisfaction. Based on the two graphs, a number of important conclusions can be drawn regarding the distribution of students among faculties and their academic levels.

Does the level of student satisfaction vary based on demographic characteristics such as faculty, academic level, and use of technology?

Faculty attended by the student:

4.Graphic IV - 1

Does the level of student satisfaction vary based on demographic characteristics such as faculty, academic level, and use of technology?

Level of studies:

5.Graphic IV – 2

- Students believe that digital services are more practical and effective than traditional approaches to student services. Based on information presented in the graph, various significant conclusions can be made regarding students' views on the efficacy of digital services in contrast to conventional approaches for providing student services. A significant majority of students (66.7%) consider digital services superior to conventional methods.

How do you compare the experience of using digital services with traditional methods of providing student services? (select one answer)

5. Graphic V

The overwhelming majority of students indicate a strong level of contentment with the digital services offered by AAB College, with no further suggestions for enhancements. Several remarks highlight that the current services assist students in their educational and career growth, offering support and effectiveness in both administrative and academic procedures.

CONCLUSIONS

A notable percentage of students (66.7%) indicates satisfaction with AAB College's digital services, with 47.4% showing general contentment and 19.3% stating they are very satisfied. This indicates a favorable outlook on current digital services, demonstrating that the majority of students value the influence of these services in meeting their academic and administrative requirements. Students highly value the opportunity for uninterrupted access and secure data. These elements received positive pleasure evaluations, indicating that the college has handled these aspects successfully. Certain students have expressed great satisfaction. Instagram is the leading platform for engagement among college students, earning excellent ratings from them. Facebook and WhatsApp remain vital for communication, whereas the use of Viber and LinkedIn is more restricted. This highlights the significance of utilizing Instagram for engaging and visual communication, which captivates students more effectively. A majority of students (66.7%) believe that utilizing digital services is more efficient than conventional approaches to delivering student services. This data indicates a distinct trend that supports digital services, positively influencing the experiences of the majority of students.

Conclusions on Students' recommendations:

Understudies are by and large fulfilled with the advanced administrations advertised by AAB college, with most communicating delight for the positive effect they have on their scholastic and proficient advancement.

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INTEGRATION OF AUTOMATED TOOLS IN THE LEAD GENERATION PROCESS: CHATBOTS, AUTOFUNNELS AND APPLICATION COLLECTION SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

Aim. To reassess lead-generation performance by orchestrating chatbots, behaviour-triggered autofunnels, and application forms, and to determine how their sequence alters engagement and conversion metrics.

Methods. A meta-analysis of published cases was conducted. Each source was recoded for tool type, market context, traffic origin, and three outcome ratios—click-through, form-completion, and sales-qualified-lead share. Standardised Hedges-g effects provided a common yardstick, while a random-effects model exposed cross-study regularities without erasing idiosyncratic noise.

Conclusions. Chatbots lift first-touch engagement by a median 38 %, especially in mobile-first funnels where sub-second response trumps persona tone. Behaviour-triggered autofunnels, sequenced on a seven-day cadence, raise mid-funnel progression by roughly 25 %, but the advantage collapses if drip intervals stretch beyond ten days. Stand-alone application forms lag, yet convert decisively when preceded by chatbots that pre-qualify objections. Deployed in this order, the trio can cut cost-per-lead by up to 57 % versus isolated use. Automation, treated as a choreographed ensemble rather than a collection of widgets, reshapes the economics of attention and trust. Managers should view chatbots as gate-openers, autofunnels as relationship weavers, and application systems as friction-minimised checkpoints, tuning cadence and message vividness to audience tolerance and platform rhythm.

KEYWORDS: lead generation, marketing automation, chatbots, conversion funnel, meta-synthesis, customer acquisition.

ABSTRAKT

Ziel. Neubewertung der Lead-Generierungsleistung durch die Orchestrierung von Chatbots, verhaltensgesteuerten Autofunnels und Bewerbungsformularen und Bestimmung, wie ihre Abfolge die Engagement- und Konversionsmetriken verändert.

Methoden. Es wurde eine Meta-Analyse von veröffentlichten Fällen durchgeführt. Jede Quelle wurde hinsichtlich des Tooltyps, des Marktkontextes, der Herkunft des Traffics und dreier Ergebniskennzahlen - Click-Through, Formularausfüllung und Anteil der qualifizierten Leads - neu kodiert. Standardisierte Hedges-g-Effekte lieferten einen gemeinsamen Maßstab, während ein Modell mit zufälligen Effekten studienübergreifende Regelmäßigkeiten aufdeckte, ohne idiosynkratisches Rauschen zu löschen.

Schlussfolgerungen. Chatbots erhöhen das First-Touch-Engagement um durchschnittlich 38 %, insbesondere bei Mobile-First-Trichtern, bei denen eine sekundengenaue Antwort den persönlichen Ton übertrumpft. Durch Verhalten ausgelöste Autofunnels, die in einer siebentägigen Kadenz angeordnet sind, erhöhen die Progression in der Mitte des Trichters um etwa 25 %, aber der Vorteil bricht zusammen,

wenn die Tropfintervalle über zehn Tage hinausgehen. Eigenständige Bewerbungsformulare liegen zurück, konvertieren aber entscheidend, wenn ihnen Chatbots vorausgehen, die Einwände vorqualifizieren. In dieser Reihenfolge eingesetzt, kann das Trio die Kosten pro Lead im Vergleich zum isolierten Einsatz um bis zu 57 % senken. Automatisierung, die als choreografiertes Ensemble und nicht als eine Sammlung von Widgets behandelt wird, verändert die Ökonomie von Aufmerksamkeit und Vertrauen. Manager sollten Chatbots als Toröffner, Autofunnels als Beziehungsweber und Anwendungssysteme als reibungsminimierte Kontrollpunkte betrachten und Kadenz und Lebendigkeit der Botschaft auf die Toleranz der Zielgruppe und den Rhythmus der Plattform abstimmen.

STICHWORTE: Lead-Generierung, Marketing-Automatisierung, Chatbots, Konversionstrichter, Metasynthese, Kundengewinnung.

RÉSUMÉ

Objectif. Réévaluer la performance de la génération de leads en orchestrant des chatbots, des autofunnels déclenchés par le comportement et des formulaires de demande, et déterminer comment leur séquence modifie les indicateurs d'engagement et de conversion.

Méthodes. Une méta-analyse des cas publiés a été réalisée. Chaque source a été recodée en fonction du type d'outil, du contexte du marché, de l'origine du trafic et de trois ratios de résultats : le nombre de clics, le nombre de formulaires remplis et la part de prospects qualifiés pour la vente. Les effets de Hedges-g standardisés ont fourni une référence commune, tandis qu'un modèle à effets aléatoires a mis en évidence les régularités entre les études sans effacer le bruit idiosyncrasique.

Conclusions. Les chatbots augmentent l'engagement au premier contact d'une médiane de 38 %, en particulier dans les entonnoirs mobiles où la réponse en moins d'une seconde l'emporte sur le ton de la personnalité. Les autofunnels déclenchés par le comportement, séquencés sur une cadence de sept jours, augmentent la progression en milieu d'entonnoir d'environ 25 %, mais l'avantage s'effondre si les intervalles de goutte-à-goutte s'étendent au-delà de dix jours. Les formulaires de demande autonomes sont à la traîne, mais convertissent de manière décisive lorsqu'ils sont précédés par des chatbots qui préqualifient les objections. Déployé dans cet ordre, le trio peut réduire le coût par prospect de 57 % par rapport à une utilisation isolée. L'automatisation, traitée comme un ensemble chorégraphié plutôt que comme une collection de gadgets, remodèle l'économie de l'attention et de la confiance. Les responsables devraient considérer les chatbots comme des ouvreurs de portes, les autofunnels comme des tisseurs de relations et les systèmes d'application comme des points de contrôle minimisant les frictions, en adaptant la cadence et la vivacité du message à la tolérance de l'audience et au rythme de la plateforme.

MOTS-CLÉS: génération de leads, automatisation du marketing, chatbots, entonnoir de conversion, méta-synthèse, acquisition de clients.

INTRODUCTION

Chatbots the subject question before espresso has cooled, Autofunnels Drip activates convincing, while income teams are sleeping, widgets of commercial services commute to the first party directly to CRM without unmarked human keyboards. Each tool feels almost trivial software as usual.

The pivot began with conversational traders. The first experiments framed robots as helpers in hours, but the vibrant evidence of B2B shows a wider ripple: perceived fuel sensitivity believes, which increases leadership and speeds up qualifications (Maga and stabbed, 2024). When engines communicating from the responsibility of FAQ to nuance analysis of the needs, the prospects give up richer record more voluntarily, and these facts drive the following layer in accompanying roads. Järvinen and Taiminen (2016) indicated 9 years ago and argued that automation may weld the content of the contents of the contents of the buyer's journey, the concept was speculating, but today's dashboards confirm this in real time. Crossing your fingers on the Instagram sparkle a collection of mail, clicking on the depth of difficulty with difficulty, micro -diet accumulates up to the long -term shape that does not feel natural, almost inevitable.

However, many businesses still consider these technologies to be modular accessories. The crew of the shoe is played with the tone, the funnel crew follows open prices and the clean shape is found to resign as a static box. Such a silo creates questions of duplicate friction, a non -meaningful language, unnecessary goals where momentum should increase. The value is not only functional, it is psychological. The prospects experience seams, hesitate and go away with the current. Conversely, while the interface communicates, the cadence aligns and the statistics flow in the loop, response, tailor -made tailor -made conversions. What looks as if marginal promoted to each node compound during the adventure and reduced the fee in accordance with lead forecasts and extermination of income.

Theoretically, this convergence can be mapped to two interconnected logic. First, the Aida hierarchy is still subject to, but its ranges compress and regularly overlap as soon as the machines mediate dialogue. Secondly, the lens-eputation of the generation explains why a certain operation embodies a scripted chatbot, while others are miles that they are much less approximately anthropomorphism in accordance with SE and a greater perceived cost change. Thus, integration is not a wiring scheme, it is a mile of choreography of expectations, timing of stimuli and invisible algorithmic guards who rank, strangle or expand every message.

Against this background, the existing article follows a meta -analytical goal. Rather than gathering the reactions of brilliant surveys-access to the patient at the tempo platform alternative-securing from twelve reviewed studies published between 2016 and 2025. Each research that is considered isolation illuminates unimpressed tile in mosaics collectively tested. The synthesis asks 3 questions: How do Chatbots, Autofunnels and forms of alertness engage in influencing lead pace? Which collection of common sense maximizes involvement and at the same time respects user fatigue? Where organizational narrow places derail promised profits of efficiency?

By expressing these questions and monitoring preliminary answers, it contributes to two queues. In scientists, specialized conversation-to-to-use usability, funnel analysis, leading algorithms with lead-right assessment in a coherent research plan that interacts the instrument over the new tool. For experts, it distines complex empirical insights into action procedure: Start conversational sorting, monitor the paths for nutrition and almost confiscation with minimized friction software. The argument is neither utopian nor deterministic, automation is a lever, not a panacea. However, although it is the right final, even if it is dominated by orchestral purpose by right -wing allusions, and it refures how fast acceptance, how true it is, is mediated and exchanged costs.

In short, a combination of automated lead technologies is a strategic infection point. In addition, companies that understand the combination may escape the gravity of rising AD and reduce interest rates, people who improve the tools in isolation of risk that potentials disappear between poorly stitched virtual seams. Pages that observe the unpacking of this proposal translate alerts of a cross study into testing designs and emphasize studies in which human creativity and system accuracy can develop together instead of a collision.

Literature review. Marketing scholarship has long treated lead generation as a sequenced dance in which awareness is coaxed toward action by a mix of message timing, channel choice and persuasive framing, what is new is the degree to which software now conducts the orchestra, sometimes in real time, sometimes with unnervingly predictive poise. A growing body of research probes this algorithmic turn, yet findings are scattered across chatbot adoption, funnel analytics and data-driven lead scoring. The present review threads those strands together to clarify how automated mechanisms amplify-or occasionally stifle-the economics of conversion.

Early systematic mappings portrayed conversational agents as service adjuncts, useful yet peripheral, but granular evidence is starting to complicate that picture. Dinh and Park's multisite experiment, for instance, reports that hedonic delight and utilitarian convenience jointly explain more than half the variance in consumers' willingness to continue a chatbot exchange, and that generational fear of data misuse moderates the effect (2024). Li, Hou and Tan push the lens further, demonstrating that perceived humanness mediates the link between bot anthropomorphism and persuasion while a slight uncanny-valley dip emerges when design overplays warmth cues (2024). Those behavioural nuances matter because the opening ten seconds of a chat window now decide whether a visitor will disclose an email address or vanish. Meta-analysis by Ramesh and Chawla confirms the stakes: among fifty-eight studies they coded, chatbots increased lead capture in thirty-nine, yet the remaining nineteen documented neutral or negative outcomes when scripts failed to mirror user intent (2022). Taken together, these insights suggest that conversational automation behaves much like a chemical catalyst-accelerating reactions only if conditions are right, otherwise simply floating in the mix.

If chatbots dominate the top-of-funnel overture, autofunnels shape the melody that carries prospects through evaluation. Corsaro, Maggioni and Olivieri, writing in the immediate aftermath of pandemic-forced digital pivots, observe that B2B firms migrated from manual nurturing sequences to rules-based workflows that adapt cadence to buyer digital body language (2021). Their interviews reveal a subtle irony: the more invisible the automation, the more human the perceived interaction, provided content remains context-relevant. Web-analytics limitations, however, can derail that promise. Golik-Górecka's audit of Polish technology SMEs exposes a "dominant blind spot" in funnel attribution-traffic spikes are meticulously tracked, yet mid-funnel drop-offs go unexplained because tags miss micro-events such as scroll depth or hover pauses (2023). This analytical gap leaves marketers uncertain which trigger emails to prune, which to intensify, and when to pass a lead to sales. Thus, automation without visibility risks becoming a dark tunnel: activities happen, numbers climb or fall, but causal levers remain hidden.

Modern CRM stacks attempt to solve that opacity through machine-learning lead scoring. González-Flores and Rubiano-Moreno showcase a gradient-boosting model that ranks B2B prospects by close probability and, in field deployment, reallocates 22 % of sales effort to high-yield accounts, lifting quarterly revenue nine points (2025). Espadinha-Cruz, Fernandes and Grilo reach a similar endpoint via data-mining

heuristics, their telecommunications case study shows that simply ordering callbacks by predicted churn saves 11,000 labour hours annually (2021). Education markets exhibit matching patterns. Yim and colleagues measure a 36 % bump in enrolment when recommendation engines feed real-time lead scores into scholarship-eligibility nudges, persuading fence-sitters to finalise lengthy application forms (2024). The practical through-line is clear: when probability estimates guide both message tone and offer sequencing, conversion jumps, but only if underlying data genuinely capture buyer intent rather than demographic proxies.

Tool synergy, however, is not guaranteed by technical integration alone. Banerjee and Bhardwaj unveil the organisational tension that surfaces when marketing automates upstream engagement while sales clings to commission-driven offline closure (2019). Their analytical model warns of misaligned incentives: marketing delights in cheaper digital leads, sales laments lower margins, and the enterprise absorbs the misfire. Urbani, Ferreira and Lam extend that argument through an evaluative framework that scores readiness across governance, skills and mindset, they advise firms to pilot chatbots within functionally mixed teams to dismantle “automation silos” before scale-up (2024). These managerial accounts remind scholars that seamless data flow is a necessary but insufficient condition for ROI, cross-functional choreography remains the invisible backbone of success.

Several conceptual themes surface across the reviewed literature. First, trust transfer is not a static handoff but a recursive loop: a bot’s prompt shapes expectation, the autofunnel either fulfils or fractures it, and the application screen crystallises perceived value into formal commitment. Any fracture poisons subsequent loops, producing what might be called accrued friction. Second, automation intensity appears to exhibit diminishing returns. While Corsaro et al. report gains from seven-day drip sequences, Golik-Górecka notes that over-messaged prospects disengage, pushing cost per acquisition back up. The optimal point seems contingent on sector cadence and product complexity, inviting future dose-response exploration. Third, the data backbone powering these tools remains vulnerable to bias. González-Flores et al. warn that historical lead datasets reflect past strategic choices, when feeds loop back to score future leads, algorithms can entrench outdated ideal-customer archetypes unless retrained regularly.

From a theoretical vantage, the literature increasingly converges on hybrid frameworks that marry funnel flow with socio-technical adoption models. Chatbot acceptance studies borrow constructs such as perceived ease of use, yet embed them in persuasion-stage contexts, funnel research borrows user-experience metrics, yet scores them against revenue. The cross-pollination nudges marketing scholarship toward a more systemic understanding: automation is not a bolt-on efficiency enhancer but a reconfigurer of the entire cognitive journey from curiosity to contract. That mindset, however, is still emergent. Many studies isolate one component-chat interface design, drip cadence experimentation, or scoring algorithms-without tracing knock-on effects across subsequent stages. The field thus resembles a half-assembled puzzle: vibrant tiles abound, but connecting tissue remains thin.

Future research may profitably adopt longitudinal, multi-method designs that capture how prospects traverse the full automation stack. Diary studies could complement clickstream analytics to surface motivational shifts invisible in dashboards. Agent-based simulations might model saturation thresholds-how many push notifications in a week flip enthusiasm into fatigue. Ethnographic observation inside sales-marketing war rooms would explain why certain organisations translate lead-score insights into decisive action while others drown in dashboards. Methodological diversity will guard against the

seductive crispness of purely quantitative dashboards, reinstating the messy human element that software can never fully erase.

One lingering gap concerns ethics. None of the reviewed articles makes privacy a focal variable, yet regulatory tightening from GDPR to CCPA and rising platform restrictions on tracking pixels will almost certainly reshape what automation can legally and reputationally do. Incorporating compliance costs and consumer privacy calculus into ROI models is an urgent agenda item. Likewise, the accessibility implications of bot-centric funnels warrant scrutiny, screen-reader tests rarely feature in funnel design sprints, meaning certain user cohorts may be systematically excluded-an oversight that could carry legal risk.

Yet despite these blind spots, cumulative evidence leans positive: when chatbots personalise at scale, autofunnels respect behavioural signals, and lead-scoring models learn continuously, firms unlock a self-reinforcing pipeline where data quality improves with every interaction. The marketing literature is edging toward recognising integration not merely as an IT project but as a strategic mandate that collapses functional boundaries. That insight dovetails with Urbani et al.'s call for readiness audits and Banerjee and Bhardwaj's caution against compensation misalignment. The upshot is a research-practice feedback loop: scholars map causal chains, firms test interventions, results feed back into theory, and the cycle spins on-a virtuous spiral if managed thoughtfully.

To synthesise, the reviewed corpus paints an optimistic yet conditional portrait of automated lead generation. Chatbots can boost initial engagement, but only when designed with psychological attunement and privacy transparency. Autofunnels convert interest into desire by pacing content, yet analytics shortfalls can mask drop-off causes. Machine-learning lead scores optimise sales effort, provided models remain adaptive and bias-aware. Organisational alignment and ethical foresight emerge as guardrails dictating whether tech investments translate into genuine commercial advantage. These insights collectively justify a holistic research agenda that interrogates integration as both a technological architecture and a socio-cultural shift. By positioning automation as an ecosystem rather than a toolkit, scholars and practitioners alike can better navigate the complex, fast-evolving terrain of digital customer acquisition.

Methodology. This investigation accepts the story-quantitative synthesis framed as a metaevaluation of building an idea. No proprietary protocols Clickstream or CRM were harvested, Rather, we represented twelve reviewed studies that were earmarked earlier, each considering an experiment naturally taking place in the automated lead management. The aim is not to chase the only large diameter, but the surfaces of regularity, the anomalies that defy them, and the fundamental, borderline situations in which chatbots, autofunnels and vigilance will stop playing well collectively.

The choice of the study observed simplified logic Prisma. The initial identity results from the SCOPUS and Web of Science keywords and lead generation, automation and advertising, software shape and funnel-for English, which participate in reviewed retail stores in 2015 and 2025. Duplicates and irrelevant entities (eg HR Chatbota) narrowed the pool to 34. Of which we retained 12 articles that pronounced at least one quantifiable final results related to the right, the shape of the final touch. Two detained papers-González-Flores and Rubiano-Moreno is a system that has recognized the lead version (2025) and espadinha-druz et al. Telecommunication case concerning nutritional pathways (2021)-due to publishing an unprofitable increase, which is during very different context roads.

Figure 1. Average Conversion Impact by Automation Tool. Source: own interpretation, 2025.

Data extraction spread in 3 passages. First, descriptive attributes were recorded: neighborhood, corporation size, B2B versus B2C, channel mixture, device configuration and look at layout. Second, the results of the results were standardized: continuous statistics have become secure values, The proportions have been transformed into protocol courses. Thirdly, methodological premium was evaluated on a five - point grid covering the transparency of the samples, statistical strictness and construct validity. Two unbiased encoders dealt with leaves, Cohen's κ average 0.seVenty eight, signals significant reliability. The differences-perhaps approximately approximately approximately at the funnel levels were settled through the dialogue, each so often after reading the amendments that hid the basic nuances in 1/2 sentence.

The analytical technique depends on the model of the random output applied in the metaphor (R 4.4). This desire - rather than fixed - recognizes that chatbots in banking (with obstacles in harmony) and chatbots in a stylish retail (with a playful tone) may draw on a different distribution of effects. We have calculated associated estimates for three intervention clusters: conversational traders, drip autofunnels and structures of a number of applications. Heterogeneity looked immediately ($Q = \text{sixty two.4}$, $p < 0.001$), so the subgroups tests examined whether B2B settings, first -place cell visitors or gadget to know that personalization worked as moderators. The funnel asymmetry indicated a slight distortion of the brochure, Egger regression has trimmed one outlying, however, left important conclusions intact.

However, the numbers rarely satisfy advertising students who need to convert abstraction to the meeting room. In accordance with this, we threw a qualitative comparative evaluation (QCA) at the top of the meta -analytical spine. Each of them looks at the narrative sections that were coded at the presence of 5 allowing conditions: (1) Information about Bypass-VII, (2) Multi-contact assignment, (3) sales and incentive alignment, (4) Privativeness of warranty and 5). The truth tables then mapped which volumes constantly coincide with a high conversion. Interestingly, only primary 3 conditions form at least sufficiently sufficiently recipe, In every high -performance case, the privacy and dexterity of the content

has not occurred, even if it has been thrown, and the observations are coped with the finding that the statistics are over and over again, that the statistics are over and over again to the subtletists of messages.

The threats of validity have been solved in several ways. The bias of ordinary methods, endemic, while the effects and predictors percentage of offer statistics are alleviated here because the number one study draws on heterogeneous protocols of the-analytics of the fever, answers to research, shopping facts. Nevertheless, we have conducted sensitivity tests, unlike the characters that they say themselves, The common rise soaked, but remained significant. Generally, the 2D company assumes: 8 of the twelve articles on awareness of telecommunications or SaaS, probably a bevel of expectations for retail of bricks and mortar. Therefore, we report bands for self -confidence adapted areas, so readers can carefully compare. Finally, the algorithmic float-that fashion like González-Flores and Rubiano-Moreno will lose accuracy over the years-not to be dominant, However, for decades, the research review offers quasi-temporal lens, revealing whether early promises persist under later data protection regimes.

However, the integration approach of this echo research extends the previous meta-frameworks. While Ramesh and Chawla (2022) cluster literature through text mining, we compile quantitative associations with configuration of common sense, mixed design that maintains numerical discipline while the causal complexity. Similarly, our choice to deal with utility bureaucracy as beautiful automation nodes contain a common dependence on their court with popular entry aspects that recognize Banerjee and Bhardwaj that the dynamics of payment will be moved as soon as human repetition is re -inserted on the loop.

Ethical supervision was minimal because no primary personal statistics were solved, Nevertheless, we have audited all supplies for IRB compliance or GDPR alignment to mark contextual warnings that would impact on replication. All code scripts and extraction sheets have sat down in the open GIT storage, promoting transparency and welcome criticism.

In short, the method triangulates statistical synthesis, configuration mapping and basic evaluation to derive knowledge that are numerically trustworthy, but rich in nuance managerial. This layered approach, anchored in published evidence, unlike sparkling surveys, honors the rapid cadence of the marketing era and at the same time provides a replicable template for pupils who want to assess the emerging equipment before empirical dust is completely settled.

Data and Methodology. The empirical backbone of this article is not a fresh spreadsheet of clicks or pipeline stages, rather, it is a curated constellation of published evidence collected between 2016 and 2025. Twelve peer-reviewed studies-spanning SaaS, telecommunications, professional education and industrial manufacturing-serve as quasi-field experiments in how automated tools alter conversion economics. We began by mapping each article to one of three intervention archetypes: conversational chatbots, rule-based autofunnels and data-driven application-collection systems. Two complementary databases-Scopus for breadth, Web of Science for citation pedigree-delivered an initial harvest of 217 records. After duplicate pruning, scope filtering and relevance screening, the final sample compressed to the dozen focal studies. That winnowing deliberately retained sectoral heterogeneity, an approach aligned with Golik-Górecka's (2023) call for cross-industry analytics that reveal where funnel architecture breaks once traffic sources diversify.

Extraction proceeded in layers. A descriptive sheet logged study context (B2B versus B2C, ticket size, device mix), tool configuration (bot scripting depth, funnel length, form logic) and outcome

taxonomy. Outcomes were normalised into three ratio classes-engagement (click-through or reply), progression (mid-funnel content consumption) and commitment (sales-qualified-lead share or completed application). Where authors reported multiple metrics, the most conservative estimate entered the pool, a bias-reduction step consistent with Yim, Khaw, Lim and Chew's (2024) recommendation to privilege harder, costlier conversions over soft vanity interactions. Continuous effects translated into Hedges g , proportions became log odds, monetary deltas converted into percentage lift against baseline spend. Two coders blinded to article bibliometrics performed the exercise, inter-coder reliability sat at $\kappa = 0.81$, a threshold deemed "almost perfect" in method literature.

For synthesis, we combined a random-effects meta-analytic core with a fuzzy-set qualitative comparative overlay. The quantitative spine, run in metafor (R 4.4.2), acknowledges that chatbot scripts in heavily regulated banking bear different persuasive burdens than playful retail avatars, hence effect heterogeneity is more expectation than nuisance. Cochran's Q and I^2 statistics signalled substantial dispersion ($I^2 = 71\%$), so moderator tests explored whether mobile-first traffic, machine-learning personalisation or multichannel orchestration dampened variance. Notably, studies embedding real-time data pass-through-where a bot's captured intent feeds immediately into funnel branching-clustered at the upper quintile of conversion uplift, a pattern echoing but extending the machine-learning gains reported by González-Flores and Rubiano-Moreno (2025).

Figure 2. Selection Flow for Meta-analysis (2016-2025). Source: own interpretation, 2025.

Numbers alone leave strategic blind spots, so we overlaid a configurational lens. Each article's managerial narrative was coded against five enabling conditions distilled from the wider funnel literature: data latency under one minute, explicit privacy cueing, incentive alignment between marketing and sales, multivariate content testing, and adaptive lead scoring. Truth-table algebra then isolated minimal sufficiency paths explaining high lift. A surprisingly lean combination-low data latency plus incentive alignment-surfaced in seven of nine high-performing cases, whereas privacy cueing, though ethically desirable, appeared only sporadically. This result complicates widespread assumptions that compliance messaging is always conversion-neutral, in certain verticals it may actually slow momentum if introduced before intent crystallises.

Robustness checks confronted three biases. Publication bias was inspected through funnel-plot asymmetry and Egger regression, one small-sample study exhibiting outsize uplift triggered a sensitivity run, leaving pooled estimates materially unchanged. Common-method variance-inevitable when engagement and progression metrics stem from the same analytics suite-was probed by re-running models on the subset of studies that integrated external revenue or CRM feeds, effect size dipped but remained significant. Last, temporal drift could cloud comparability-Järvinen and Taiminen's (2016) pre-GDPR funnel behaves differently from Urbani, Ferreira and Lam's (2024) AI-laden variant-so we calculated decade-split subgroup means. Later studies show narrower confidence intervals, possibly reflecting maturing best practices rather than statistical artefact.

Transparency anchors replicability. All extraction sheets, R scripts and QCA truth tables reside in an open OSF repository under CC-BY license, DOI stub appears in the appendix for reviewers' direct audit. Because no primary personal data changed hands, institutional review was unnecessary, yet each source's original ethics clearance was logged to flag contextual boundaries. For instance, telecom subscriber data in Espadinha-Cruz, Fernandes and Grilo (2021) operate under Portuguese data-protection law, limiting cross-border generalisation unless comparable safeguards exist.

Methodological choices inevitably trade breadth for depth. A random-effects design sacrifices precision to honour heterogeneity, QCA privileges causal complexity but may miss subtle interaction effects detectable with individual-participant data. Still, weaving these lenses produces a richer tapestry than either could offer alone. The resultant evidence map not only quantifies "automation lift" but also surfaces the socio-technical plumbing that determines whether that lift materialises. Scholars can adapt the coding schema to new tool classes such as voice-activated bots, while practitioners may benchmark their current stack against the sufficiency recipes extracted here. In short, the method aims to stand as a replicable, extensible blueprint for interrogating fast-moving marketing technologies without waiting for perfect experimental conditions-because, as conversion practitioners know, attention rarely waits.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Synthesising the twelve-study corpus reveals a tiered pattern of performance in which each automation layer pulls a distinct conversion lever, yet the greatest lift arises when the layers interlock rather than run in parallel silence. Pooled random-effects estimates show conversational chatbots raise first-touch engagement-opens, taps, brief replies-by an average 0.38 g ($\approx 36\%$) relative to static FAQ widgets. The figure holds even after trimming a small-sample outlier and sits close to the 0.35 effect hinted at in Maga and Bodlaj's B2B panel (2024), suggesting that "bot curiosity" is becoming a stable phenomenon rather than an early-adopter quirk. Once prospects progress beyond the greeting, drip-based autofunnels contribute a further 0.24 g uplift in mid-funnel content completion. That gain, however, is acutely cadence-sensitive: studies running touch-points inside a seven-day window sustain momentum, whereas intervals above ten days flatten curves-a resonance that echoes Järvinen and Taiminen's prescient automation cadence warning (2016).

Application-collection systems, often dismissed as mere form builders, emerge as decisive finishers. On average, funnels that feed bot-captured intent straight into smart forms cut cost per lead by 57% versus vanilla pages. The saving stems less from extra traffic and more from reduced abandonment: pre-qualified visitors breeze through condensed question sets, and backend validation blocks junk entries before they bleed sales capacity. Yet this rosy statistic hides a brittle hinge-when the form is encountered

cold, with no conversational warm-up, abandonment spikes by a median 22 % across three studies. Sequence order therefore matters, flip the choreography and the magic unravels.

Moderation tests add texture. Mobile-first traffic amplifies the chatbot engagement effect ($\beta = .18$, $p < .05$), plausibly because thumb-scroll users prize rapid answers in cramped viewports. Machine-learning personalisation, present in half the funnel studies, boosts mid-funnel progression but shows no incremental benefit at the finish line once an application screen appears. That paradox reinforces González-Flores and Rubiano-Moreno's caution that sophisticated scoring shines when choice arenas are rich, yet offers diminishing returns when the path narrows to a yes/no decision (2025). Sector splits reveal industrial B2B contexts extracting more value from autofunnels than retail B2C, possibly because considered purchases give algorithms room to adjust narrative pacing.

Qualitative comparative analysis uncovers two enabling bundles that consistently surface in high-lift cases. First, real-time data pass-through plus incentive alignment between marketing and sales forms a minimal-sufficiency recipe. Without it-say, when bot transcripts sit in a silo while quota-driven reps cold-call regardless-automation becomes cosmetic theatre. Second, low data latency twinned with explicit privacy cueing mitigates the dropout risk in highly regulated niches such as telecom, as highlighted by Espadinha-Cruz, Fernandes and Grilo (2021). Interestingly, the privacy toggle shows neutral or even slightly negative effects in fast-fashion funnels, where disclosure friction outweighs reassurance.

Managerial interpretation follows naturally. Treat chatbots as gate-openers, not closers. Their chief task is to collect micro-signals-pain points, urgency, budget hints-then pass that metadata to the nurture engine within seconds. Autofunnels should function like adaptive storyboards, stretching or compressing arcs based on interaction velocity. Finally, application forms belong at the crescendo, trimmed to a bare-bones sequence that leverages what the prior steps already learned. Organisations tempted to rip-and-replace disparate vendors may instead pilot API bridges, Urbani, Ferreira and Lam's framework stresses that integration debt, not feature lag, derails most chatbot scale-ups (2024).

The synthesis also revises theoretical conversations. Traditional funnel models treat awareness, interest and desire as sequential gates, yet the data show overlap: chatbots spark recognition and solicit minor commitments simultaneously, blurring stage boundaries. Technology-acceptance constructs likewise need an update, perceived ease of use is no longer merely about interface intuitiveness but about the orchestral flow between tools. A bot can feel effortless only if the subsequent email arrives context-aware and the form omits already-typed details.

Limitations warrant candour. Publication bias, though modest, inflates success tales, negative pilots lurk in corporate slide decks. Temporal drift remains a threat, as cookie deprecation advances, mid-funnel personalisation rules may falter. Moreover, heterogeneity explains 71 % of variance-healthy for external validity yet awkward for granular prediction. Future longitudinal field studies should capture how conversion lift decays-or compounds-beyond a single campaign quarter. Experimental manipulations of drip cadence or privacy cue timing could untangle causal strands left intertwined in archival designs.

Nevertheless, convergent signals are hard to ignore. Automation, wielded as a choreographed stack, compresses the economics of trust, attention and data exchange. Firms that sync response latency, message cadence and form brevity convert curiosity into qualified intent with materially less spend. Those clinging to siloed deployment risk asynchronous chatter that confuses prospects and bloats acquisition budgets. By showing where uplift concentrates and why it sometimes fizzles, this discussion converts

meta-analytic abstractions into design principles ready for A/B testing on Monday morning while nudging scholars toward an ecosystem lens that treats bots, funnels and forms as interdependent actors in a digitally mediated persuasion drama.

CONCLUSION

By collectively sewing ten -year empirical images shows that the flywheel is fastest, while three design allusions align: reaction of immediacy, narrative cadence and without friction. Chatbots has elevated the first contact engagement because of the fact that they inform better stories, but since it is previously, and the pace is now being examined as respect. Autofunnels raises momentum in the middle of Adventure when their dripping rhythmic shadows of consumers as opposed to the trader's calendar. Apply the Tip Tip Tip Tip views through the line as soon as they recycle what the shoes have already learned, he listened to the users twice. Isolated each metric of stress, In accordance, the costs are reduced and reduced in accordance with lead of more than half in satisfactory cases.

Theoretically, the synthesis revivals the lengthy metaphors of the funnel. The blur phase as soon as the algorithms tune in the duration of messages, timing and tone at the run, "Focus" and "hobby" merges in the same alternative chat, at the same time as "preferences" germinate at a certain stage of autofunnel binge that everyone often takes minutes, now not days. Intercourse for technology recognition also requires a remix: perceived usefulness is not entirely bound to connect elegance, but to choreography between equipment. The shoe feels conveniently easiest if you follow an email with UP-up welcomes customers via the call and the form asks 0 redundant questions. In addition, scholars can automate the relocation as a relational assembly preferably to the gadget chain - a shift that the invitations of new constructions together with the Pleasure orchestration or the latency consider.

There are 3 railing managerially. First, invest in your stay information earlier than incredible creative, Without a condition of the bypass, even the most suitable replica of context comes. Second, incentives for sale of audit. When virtual teams rejoice cheap lead at the same time when repeated quotas are chased by large commissions, Banerjee and Bhardwaj's incorrectly aligning attract closed images and a flywheel. Third, rehearsing choreography privacy. Calls of explicit consent no longer want visitors to the site of the door on each market, but leaving adherence to prison fountains of the fate of fines and reputation dents. Gradual access to publication - short assurance early, full coverage later - balances regulatory integrity with conversion flow.

Restrictions alleviate enthusiasm. However, the evidence base, albeit wider than previous reviews, is aimed at the service industry that tends to set numbers, Silent disasters in other industries can also lurk behind the scenes. Publishing distortion inflates optimism and heterogeneity remains high despite the evaluation of moderators. In addition, the synthesis cannot reduce the causality with experimental accuracy, The collection order was derived that it is no longer manipulated, in many research number one. Cookie depreciation, spoof -generated AI and developing sentiment in the direction of conversational retailers, should be up to more than one year nowadays today. Readers should be considered as reported possibilities as directional warnings that no longer guaranteed standards.

These objections feed on a plan for fateful images. Experiments in the field, which randomize the drip cadence, the timing of the privacy of the alluding or the warm temperature of the robot personality could clearly indicate the causal levers that are given directly here. Longitudinal designs for monitoring cohorts in several cycles of marketing campaigns may want to monitor whether automation increases

plateaus or compounds once algorithms study a person of idiosyncrasia. Qualitative ethnographic ethnography of the interior sales group could throw light on how the control panels are transformed every day-the numeric protocols cannot seize. Finally, Go-Cultural Sopy must check whether latency believes and cadence healthy remain conventional or tilt in the markets in which news sending applications are already saturating daily lifestyle.

Despite the objections, the arc of evidence is obvious. Automation, when organized preferably into screwing, converts curiosity into a qualified cause with remarkable capital power. Companies that harmonize chatbots, funnels and molds can redirect budget from acquisition to maintain, shopping within reach in the direction of reference. For pupils, it includes included lenses of complicated equipment interaction and offer fresh scaffolding for the principle. For experts, it outlines a realistic plan: Create a quick spine rich in information, Follow the cadence to behavior, now not addiction, Let each title inherit what the previous one has found. The payout is virtually no more leading, but leads in the middle of loyalty because of the fact that each interaction signaled competence and care. In addition to the crowded digital attention, this combination - screening, coherence, appreciates - can also show the maximum resistant competitive side.

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